

FIRST VERSION OF THE ACTIVITY PLANS

[Deliverable 4.1]

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ER4STEM - EDUCATIONAL ROBOTICS FOR STEM

TABLE OF CONTENTS

1	Executive Summary	9
1.1	<i>Role, Purpose and Objectives of the Deliverable</i>	<i>9</i>
1.2	<i>Correlation to Other ER4STEM Deliverables.....</i>	<i>9</i>
1.3	<i>Structure of THE DELIVERABLE</i>	<i>9</i>
2	ACTIVITY TEMPLATE FIRST VERSION	10
2.1	<i>ACTIVITY PLAN TEMPLATE.....</i>	<i>10</i>
	Focus, Set up and Requirements of the activity	10
	Students and space.....	12
	Social Orchestration	12
	Teaching and Learning Procedures.....	12
	Sequence and description of activities.....	13
	Assessment Procedures.....	15
3	ACTIVITY PLANS: OVERVIEW AND REFLECTION	16
3.1	<i>Main objectives</i>	<i>16</i>
3.1	<i>Multi-disciplinarity.....</i>	<i>17</i>
3.2	<i>Student age, setting and connection to the curriculum.....</i>	<i>17</i>
3.3	<i>Constructions in activity plans.....</i>	<i>18</i>
	Digital constructions.....	18
	Physical constructions	18
	Teaching Methods to support constructionist activity.....	18
3.4	<i>Argumentation, discussion and maker culture.....</i>	<i>19</i>
3.5	<i>Main Activities – in teaching and learning sequence</i>	<i>20</i>
	Introductory activities	20
	Programming oriented activities	21
	Engineering and design oriented activities.....	21
	Evaluation activities.....	22

4	FIRST VERSION OF ACTIVITY PLANS	22
4.1	<i>Introduction to Dash and Dot</i>	22
	Focus, Set up and Requirements of the activity	22
	Students and space	23
	Social Orchestration	24
	Teaching and Learning Procedures	24
	Sequence and description of activities	25
	Assessment Procedures	27
4.2	<i>Introducing Robotics with Arduino, Scratch and MindMaps</i>	27
	Focus, Set up and Requirements of the activity	28
	Students and space	29
	Social Orchestration	29
	Teaching and Learning Procedures	30
	Sequence and description of activities	31
	Assessment Procedures	33
4.3	<i>Learning the Basics of Programming with Thymio II</i>	33
	Focus, Set up and Requirements of the activity	33
	Students and space	34
	Social Orchestration	34
	Teaching and Learning Procedures	35
	Sequence and description of activities	36
	Assessment Procedures	38
4.4	<i>Crazy robots – Robotic Product Development</i>	39
	Focus, Set up and Requirements of the activity	39
	Students and space	40
	Social Orchestration	40
	Teaching and Learning Procedures	41

Sequence and description of activities 42

Assessment Procedures..... 45

4.5 *ECER-Botball-Preparation-Workshop* 45

 Focus, Set up and Requirements of the activity 46

 Students and space..... 47

 Social Orchestration 47

 Teaching and Learning Procedures..... 47

 Sequence and description of activities..... 48

 Assessment Procedures..... 50

4.6 *European Conference on Educational Robotics (ECER)*..... 50

 Focus, Set up and Requirements of the activity 50

 Students and space..... 51

 Social Orchestration 52

 Teaching and Learning Procedures..... 52

 Sequence and description of activities..... 53

 Assessment Procedures..... 54

4.7 *Making a robot “smart” (introducing programming structures)*..... 55

 Focus, Set up and Requirements of the activity 55

 Students and space..... 56

 Social Orchestration 56

 Teaching and Learning Procedures..... 56

 Sequence and description of activities..... 57

 Assessment Procedures..... 58

4.8 *Robotic “Safe Swing” and a seesaw* 59

 Focus, Set up and Requirements of the activity 59

 Students and space..... 60

 Social Orchestration 60

Teaching and Learning Procedures..... 61

Sequence and description of activities 62

Assessment Procedures..... 63

4.9 *Constructing & controlling a robot-painter* 64

 Focus, Set up and Requirements of the activity 64

 Students and space..... 65

 Social Orchestration 65

 Teaching and Learning Procedures..... 66

 Sequence and description of activities 67

 Assessment Procedures..... 69

4.10 *Solving the maze problem with Lego EV3*..... 69

 Focus, Set up and Requirements of the activity 70

 Students and space..... 70

 Social Orchestration 71

 Teaching and Learning Procedures..... 71

 Sequence and description of activities 72

 Assessment Procedures..... 74

4.11 *My First Robot* 74

 Focus, Set up and Requirements of the activity 74

 Students and space..... 75

 Social Orchestration 76

 Teaching and Learning Procedures..... 76

 Sequence and description of activities 77

 Assessment Procedures..... 80

4.12 *ROBOTS AND WALKING MECHANISMS* 80

 Focus, Set up and Requirements of the activity 80

 Students and space..... 81

Social Orchestration	82
Teaching and Learning Procedures.....	82
Sequence and description of activities.....	83
Assessment Procedures.....	84
4.13 A ROBOTIC INSECT.....	85
Focus, Set up and Requirements of the activity	85
Students and space.....	86
Social Orchestration	86
Teaching and Learning Procedures.....	87
Sequence and description of activities.....	88
Assessment Procedures.....	89
5 EVALUATION OF ACTIVITY PLANS BY SCIENTIX AMBASSADORS	90
5.1 Overview and Reflection on the evaluators' comments	90
Replicability	91
Adaptability	93
Form and structure of activity plans.....	95
Appealing elements of activity plans.....	96
Controversial elements of activity plans	96
Suggestions.....	96
5.2 Summary of Scientix Ambassadors' Comments.....	98
1 st Review – Bosnia Herzegovina	98
2 nd Review - Poland	100
3 rd Review - Sweden	102
4 th Review - Denmark	103
5 th Review - Slovakia	105
6 Considerations for the second version of activity plans.....	107
7 Glossary / Abbreviations.....	110

8	BIBLIOGRAPHY.....	110
9	APPENDIX 1: EVALUATION DOCUMENTS BY SCIENTIX AMBASSADORS.....	112
9.1	<i>Scientix Ambassador Project Support – Review Template.....</i>	<i>112</i>
	Workshop 1a-c:	112
	Workshop 2:	112
	Workshop 3:	113
	Workshop 4:	113
	Workshop 5:	113
	Workshop 6:	114
	Workshop 7:	114
	8. Conference:	114
9.2	<i>Scientix Ambassador reviews</i>	<i>115</i>
	1 st Review: Ivan Derek Primary School Teacher - Bosnia Herzegovina.....	115
	2 nd Review: Malgorzata Zajackowska Poland.....	122
	3 rd Review: Jennie Malmberg - Sweden	128
	4 th Review: Thorbjørn Hartelius – Denmark	133
	5 th Review: Zuzana Christozova – Slovakia	140

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1 EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

1.1 ROLE, PURPOSE AND OBJECTIVES OF THE DELIVERABLE

This deliverable addresses the first year of work in Work-package 4: “Pedagogical Design and Innovation for Educational Robotics”. In accordance to the Description of Work (DoW), D4.1 reports on the first version of activity plans developed for ER4STEM and implemented in the first round of workshops. This version of activity plans has been designed with the use of an activity plan template developed by UoA- ETL aiming to provide tools to the stakeholders of educational robotics to design activity plans that integrate key learning activities like the following:

- transition from individual to collaborative learning perspectives
- an identification of key skills including collaboration, argumentation, taking individual responsibility in groups, creativity and innovation, constructionism, coding/programming robot behaviours, interactions, field properties
- a focus on skill development through the sharing of productions
- a focus on problems which the students perceive as real world
- the encouragement for students to come up with robotics ideas to solve real problems
- teacher roles and strategies encouraging the generation of meanings and self-regulation

The activity plan template was generated from a study of best practices in Educational Robotics (see D.1.1) and from ETL’s experience in designing innovative activity plans for digital learning environments (the method followed for the design of activity plan template is described in detail in D.2.1).

1.2 CORRELATION TO OTHER ER4STEM DELIVERABLES

WP4 is developed in relation to developments in WP1 (framework) and in relation to Evaluation (WP6) (see DoW, WP4). Specifically, D4.1 has drawn from D.1.1 for the development of the activity plan template (see section 2) and from D.6.1 and D.6.2 for the evaluation activities included in all activity plans reported here. WP4 provided a design instrument (activity plan template) and the activity plans for the implementation of workshops in WP2 and ECER conference in WP3. Furthermore, the methodology for the development of activity plans informed the process of designing a generic curriculum for ER in D.2.1. The refinement of the activity plans for the next year of the project will be also based (apart from the work reported in D.4.1) on the analysis of the evaluation data, which will be reported in D.6.3.

1.3 STRUCTURE OF THE DELIVERABLE

This document begins by describing the activity template, which was the design instrument for the ER4STEM partners to develop the first version of activity plans (section 2). Next we present a critical overview on the characteristics of the thirteen (13) activity plans developed for the first year of the project (section 3) and then we include the actual activity plans (section 4). In Section 5 we provide an overview and a summary of an evaluation of the activity plans. This evaluation was done by five

external evaluators, which were STEM teachers from the Scientix network (Scientix ambassadors). The review template and the actual comments are integrated in Annex 1 section 9 of the deliverable. The final section of the deliverable outlines the main considerations that will direct the work in WP4 during the second year of the project (D.4.2). These considerations are grounded on the reflection on the first version of activity plans (section 3) and on the external evaluation of these plans (section 5).

2 ACTIVITY TEMPLATE FIRST VERSION

As we mentioned earlier the activity plans presented in this deliverable were developed with the use of an activity plan template. The template provides a generic design instrument that identifies critical elements of teaching and learning with robotics based in theory and practice and is expected to contribute to the description of effective learning and teaching with robotics. Thus, this template is in essence, an abstraction of what we have identified as essential and transferrable elements of learning with robotics. Our aim is to find a balance between a) a level of abstraction that it will make the template adaptable to different settings and b) a level of detail that will demonstrate the influence of a specific pedagogical approach, it will address the particularities of Robotics and it will augment the affordances of the specific robotic kit used in each activity plan. The template was designed with the purpose to function as a mediating artefact between the pedagogical experts (ETL) and the ER4STEM partners interested in designing activity plans for ER.

The basic pedagogical theory underlying its design is constructionism (Papert, 1980), where learning is connected to powerful ideas inherent in constructions with personal meaning for the students. Another aspect underlying our design rationale is the emphasis on the social dimension of the construction process aiming to cultivate a specific learning attitude growing out of sharing, discussing and negotiating ideas. Specifically, the Activity plan template addresses the following aspects: a) the description of the activity plan with reference to the different domains involved, different types of objectives, duration and necessary material; b) contextual information regarding space and characteristics of the participants; c) social orchestration of the activity (i.e. group or individual work, formulation of groups etc.); d) a description of the teaching and learning procedures where the influence of the pedagogical theory is mostly demonstrated; e) expected student constructions; f) description of the sequencing and the focus of activities; g) means of evaluation. Next we present the first version of the activity plan template

2.1 ACTIVITY PLAN TEMPLATE

Provide the title of the activity as it is mediated to students

AUTHOR:

Name(s) of teacher (s), designer(s), researcher(s)..

Focus, Set up and Requirements of the activity

CURRICULUM

Select NO if the scenario is not aligned with the curriculum of your country and YES if it is. Please mention the relevant subject matter.

NO YES Subject:**CONTENT**

Choose categories and give a rating of the level of emphasis on concepts from each of the following domains

Science Technology Business Engineering Arts Mathematics
(0-10) (0-10) (0-10) (0-10) (0-10) (0-10)
0 10 0 6 0 0

OBJECTIVES

<i>Subject related</i>	e.g. Study the angle and position of all materials (servo motors, circuits, sensors), as well as the construction of the legs in order for the robot - insect to be autonomous and move correctly
<i>Technology use related</i>	e.g. Programming with Arduino, or with in LEGO EV3 programming environment
<i>Social and action related</i>	e.g. Develop collaborative skills, take roles within groups, communicate with other groups to exchange ideas and tips, advice
<i>Argumentation and fostering of maker culture:</i>	e.g. practice making conjectures about how the robot will react to external stimuli based on the program given or formulate and define an authentic problem, make assumptions, test possible solutions, choose the best solution, communicate with other “makers”.

TIME**Duration:** e.g. 4 weeks**Schedule:** e.g. 2 hours per week**MATERIALS AND ARTIFACTS**

<i>Digital artifact</i>	e.g. programming language (Lego EV3 programming environment), visual interface, robot simulation
<i>Robotic artifact</i>	i.e. The technology and the robot form: LEGO WEDO – form: 'an insect', 'a car' ... 'a simple vehicle'
<i>Student's workbook and manual</i>	e.g. Manual with step-by-step instructions for the electronic part and programming part too, activity sheets, Lego electronic manual, evaluation sheet
<i>Teacher's instruction book and manual:</i>	e.g. Teacher's notes with a template of e.g. three incisive stages and five steps for the first two stages.

Students and space

STUDENTS (TARGET AUDIENCE)

<i>Sex and Age:</i>	e.g. boys & girls, 12-15 years old
<i>Prior knowledge:</i>	e.g. little if any knowledge of Arduino but experts on electronics; basic knowledge of programming concepts (like if-then concepts)
<i>Nationality and cultural background</i>	e.g. 5 pupils are from Albania and 10 from Greece
<i>Social status and social environment</i>	e.g. underprivileged area OR mainstream public school OR elite private school
<i>Special needs and abilities</i>	e.g. ADD, dyslexia, Soc. Em. Behavior Disorders, gifted, other OR Lego programming environment is in English. English is not native language for participants

SPACE INFO

Organizational and cultural context: For example: in school at the technology laboratory; OR during project time in/after school; OR established voluntary club activity; OR after school activity at Computer Lab.

Physical characteristics: indoors/outdoors

Social Orchestration

POPULATION

Students: e.g. 9

Tutors: e.g. 2; **Assistants:**3

GROUPING:

<i>Grouping criteria</i>	e.g. mixed ability, mixed gender OR mixed specialties (for Vocational Schools)
<i>Setting:</i>	e.g. Students in a normal classroom OR around light mobile tables OR looking at the blackboard or in small groups OR students in front of computers with one lego EV3 kit available for each group

INTERACTION DURING THE ACTIVITY (EMPHASIS)

<i>Actions</i>	e.g. Exchange ideas, dialogue, negotiation, debate
<i>Relationships</i>	e.g. Collaborative, competitive
<i>Roles in the group</i>	e.g. pre-defined roles; emergent roles; role exchange in the group
<i>Support by the tutor(s)</i>	e.g. Intervene, monitor, facilitate

Teaching and Learning Procedures

TEACHER'S ROLE

Function: (what is the teacher doing?) facilitator, mentor, co-researcher, mentor, consultant co-researcher, lecturer,...

TEACHING METHODS

Teacher's approaches: e.g. demonstrate, engage by example, guide (e.g. setting initial program status), trigger investigation, orchestrate discussion

EXPECTED STUDENT ACTIVITY

Students during the activity are expected to engage in the following actions: construct, observe, communicate, create, present their work in a blog, exchange ideas, etc.

STUDENT LEARNING PROCESSES

<i>Designed Conflicts and misconceptions</i>	Do the activity designers wish to bring students in conflict with mistaken conceptions documented in educational research or their teaching practice?
<i>Learning processes emphasized:</i>	e.g. emphasis on analyzing robot behavior in order to refine and reflect on the code that defines this behavior
<i>Expected relevance of alternative knowledge</i>	e.g. students are expected to investigate the structure of an insect's body (biology) in order to construct their robot

STUDENT PRODUCTIONS

PRODUCTION	DESCRIPTION
<i>Artifacts - robots</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Assignment: What tasks should the robot perform (e.g. entertain, bring stuff, call help, vacuum clean etc.) ▪ Interaction: What are the means of communication with the robot (e.g. speech, gesture, mind control, buttons, app etc.)? ▪ Morphology: How does the robot look like? What material is it made of (e.g. machine-like, zoomorphic, anthropomorphic, cartoon-like etc.)? ▪ Behavior: Which should be the behavior of the robot (e.g. butler, friend, pet, protector, teacher etc.)? ▪ Material: What parts are needed for the construction of the robot (e.g. electronics, software, mechanics etc.)?
<i>Programs - code</i>	Structure of code-commands: Elements (e.g. iteration, selection, variables) Conditionals (e.g. event handling) OR For example: One "scenario" in Lego programming environment with nested structures; Iteration, selection, nested structures, optionally variable usage; Non-event programming. Conditions are embedded into structures.
<i>Discussions – arguments</i> (Describe the emphasis of the activity plan in one or more types of discussion provided in the next cell)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Descriptive - explanatory: description of a situation, a construct or an idea for others to understand and /or to implement ▪ Alternative: provision of solutions to problems, provision of alternatives if a dead end is reached ▪ Critical - objection: revision of other's constructs and ideas, identification of problems, challenge of ideas ▪ Contributory - extending: sharing of resources, provision of ideas towards improving an existing construct or initial idea

Sequence and description of activities

In this section of the activity plan we describe how we expect the teaching and the learning process to evolve. We might use phases or activities for this description. The phases or activities should support the objectives stated and make use of the materials, tools and teaching and learning processes mentioned earlier in the activity plan. Next we provide an example of phase description

PHASE 1: INTRODUCTION AND EXPERIMENTATION

Duration: 2 hours

Orchestration: group work

Description: Children are engaged in discussion about robotic behaviors and how the creator-programmer can give the desired functionalities and characteristics to a robotic device. Students are introduced to available parts, sensors, motors. They experiment with different values and settings and observe the results on the class floor.

PHASE 2: SEQUENTIAL PROGRAMMING

Duration: 2 hours

Orchestration: group work

Description: Students implement their first programs that have programming blocks in a row. No loops or selection structures are needed. The first program should move the robot on a predefined path on the floor. The robotic vehicle is pre-assembled so students have to focus on programming and debugging their own programs. After a successful first program, they are asked to enhance the program by repeating the movements on the floor and ensuring that the robot returns to the initial position.

PHASE 3: USING LOOPS

Duration: 2 hours

Orchestration: group work

Description: Students try to find a way to simplify their programs by avoiding using the same sequence of blocks many times in the same program. Almost spontaneously they try to use loops with programming blocks. With teacher assistance, they recognize the usage, the conditions and the characteristics of the new programming structure and also the role of the sensors in executing a loop block.

PHASE 4: GIVING “SMART” BEHAVIOR: THE USAGE OF SELECTION/SWITCH BLOCKS

Duration: 2 hours

Orchestration: group work

Description: A robot in order to be “smart” (autonomous) has to avoid any obstacle that could be in its path. Students discuss the new problem and are introduced with a new programming block: “switch block”. Firstly they use the new block once to avoid one obstacle. Very soon they realize that this is not a very “smart” behavior and of course this is not a real-life solution. So, they are

encouraged to combine the “switch block” with the “loop block” to have a permanent solution. Students experiment with the position of the two blocks in the program as well as with the various settings that read and control the sensors and motors.

PHASE 5: FEEDBACK AND EVALUATION

Duration: 30 minutes

Orchestration: individual and class work

Description: In addition with the activity sheets that students complete during activity phases, finally they discuss in classroom the difficulties, the different solutions, the limitations that may have found in every step. They also fill in an evaluation questionnaire and teacher gets short informal open interviews from students that want to share their experience.

Assessment Procedures

Suggestions¹ for procedures, methods and tools that can facilitate teacher reflection and collection of student feedback:

RESEARCH QUESTION/ASSESSMENT	ASSESSMENT METHOD OR TOOL
<i>Are popular gender stereotypes about STEM held?</i>	Draw a scientist
<i>Past experience and existing attitudes to STEM subjects and careers</i>	Pre-questionnaire
<i>Past experience and existing attitudes to STEM subjects and careers Includes questions about the activities to help understand learner’s experiences of the workshop as a whole, what participants feel they have learned and what their future intentions are</i>	Post-questionnaire
<i>Understand the experience of participants and their reasons for particular actions</i>	Interview with focus group
	Peer assessment
	Essays- Tests-Student productions (code-robots-textual communication – presentations,)
	Observation notes
	Reflection Sheet

¹ This part of the activity plan template has been created in collaboration and with reference to the evaluation process of ER4STEM led by the University of Cardiff. Detailed descriptions of the assessment methods and tools are provided in the deliverables of Workpackage 6 (D.6.1 and D.6.2)

3 ACTIVITY PLANS: OVERVIEW AND REFLECTION

In this section of the deliverable we present an overview of the activity plans designed for the first year workshops of ER4STEM and we attempt a reflective presentation. For the first year we designed 13 activity plans covering a wide range of technologies, student ages settings and objectives. In the table below we present the activity plans created per partner, the technologies they employ and the primary domain they cover² although all activity plans are multidisciplinary with their themes and tasks belonging to STE(A)M.

No	Partner	Activity Plan	Technology	Domain - emphasis
1	AL -Malta	Introduction to Dash and Dot	Dash and Dot	Programming- mathematics
2	ESI-CEE	Introducing Robotics with Arduino, Scratch and Mindmaps	Custom set developed by ESI CEE	Programming – Engineering – creative thinking
3	TU-Wien	Learning basics of programming with Thymio II	Thymio II	Programming
4	TU-Wien	Crazy Robots	Mattie – custom set developed by TU-Wien	Engineering – Design - Business
5	PRIA	ECER-Botball Preparation Workshop	BotBall	Programming - Engineering
6	PRIA	European Conference on Educational Robotics	BotBall and any other robotic kit	Programming - Engineering
7	UoA-ETL	Making a robot “Smart” (introducing programming structures)	LEGO –NXT kit	Programming
8	UoA-ETL	Robotic “Safe Swing” and Seesaw	LEGO WEDO	Programming - Mathematics
9	UoA-ETL	Constructing and controlling a robot painter	LEGO –NXT - G	Programming - mathematics
10	UoA-ETL	Solving the maze problem with Lego EV3	Lego EV3	Programming
11	UoA-ETL	My first Robot	Lego WeDo 2.0	Programming, Engineering
12	UoA-ETL	Robots and walking mechanisms	LEGO Mindstorms	Programming – Engineering
13	UoA-ETL	A Robotic insect	Arduino	Engineering

Table 1: List of the first year activity plans, their technologies and the domains they cover per partner

3.1 MAIN OBJECTIVES

The main objectives pursued with the activities designed for the first year of the project primarily focused on the domain of Technology and Engineering. Secondary subjects that were involved in

² The emphasis of the activity plan is derived mainly from the description of the teaching and learning sequence and does not rely exclusively on the objectives selected by the authors. This has happened due to a discrepancy identified between the domains selected and the teaching sequence described.

the robotic constructions were Mathematics, Science, and Business. In fewer cases Art was mentioned and in one case (Ionidios – UoA) it was subject related (construction of a robot painter). However, the construction of the robot painter did not actually focus on aspects of painting as the robot mainly drew colored geometrical shapes (like lines, squares etc.) and in another case (ESI CEE) robotics was combined with creativity thinking based on mind-maps. Furthermore, Language and Arts in lessons created for robotics (see for example the TUFTS curriculum³ unit on programming and robotics) primarily involve activities around a construction – like the Engineer’s journal and not the actual robotic constructions.

3.1 MULTI-DISCIPLINARITY

Multi-disciplinarity is one of the special characteristics of robotics activities (Yiannoutsou, Nikitopoulou, Kynigos, Gueorguiev, & Fernandez, 2016) and as we mentioned earlier it was part of the design of the first version of the activity plans presented here. However, with the exception of “Mathematics” and physics laws, which are seamlessly integrated, mainly in the way robot vehicles function, other domains are superficially covered. We already mentioned the example of Arts. Similarly in the “Robotic insect” (see section 4.13) the activity plan makes connections with biology because it requires that students obtain some knowledge about the structure of the body of an insect but there is no need for students to do something more than recall the knowledge they already have about how insects look like. Furthermore, if the structure of the body of a real insect is not correctly represented this has little impact in the final result as the main point of the task is to construct a robot which will be able to walk with more than two modular feet.

An exception to this observation is the “Crazy robots” activity plan (see section 4.4) where aspects of design, sales and marketing are very well integrated in the task and in the final design of the robot (determining materials, creating an appealing look and feel etc.). In the second year of ER4STEM we will investigate ways and suggest methods to seamlessly integrate in activity plans domains such as business, arts, biology etc.

3.2 STUDENT AGE, SETTING AND CONNECTION TO THE CURRICULUM

Student age ranged from 6 year olds to 17 year olds (for an overview of the statistics of workshops see D.2.1 section 5.1). The settings covered by the activity plans range from formal school settings where the activities are integrated to the school schedule to non-formal settings as it is the case of ECER – Conference and the preparation for ECER workshop (See sections 4.5 and 4.6). However, the activity plans describe situations where the robotics activity can be implemented in something like a gray zone: i.e. in the school in the context of extra –curricular activities which take place after school or during school hours (if there is a slot for extra curricular activities) especially in cases of primary schools which seem to have more freedom.

Not all the activities created are connected to a formal national curriculum especially those that are designed for non-formal settings and those implemented in the context of extra – curricular school activities. Even though there are activity plans declaring connection to the curriculum, the specific

³ [http://ase.tufts.edu/devtech/tangiblek/Classroom Curriculum Version 1.02 Nov 8 2010.pdf](http://ase.tufts.edu/devtech/tangiblek/Classroom%20Curriculum%20Version%201.02%20Nov%208%202010.pdf)

concepts of the curriculum are not included in the plan. This is an issue that needs to be addressed in the next version of activity plans especially because connection to curricula in some cases is a criterion for implementing an activity in the classroom. This is not to say that activity plans should always be connected to a specific curriculum. On the contrary activity plans that are not aligned to a specific curriculum might contribute in exploring new ways of thinking and learning around robotics.

3.3 CONSTRUCTIONS IN ACTIVITY PLANS

Digital constructions

Some activity plans focus on constructing the behavior of the robot through programming and in these cases the teachers provide the robot already constructed. This for example was a choice made by a UoA researcher (Making a robot “smart”) due to organizational issues (number of students, availability of robotic kits, scheduling of the activity). In other cases this might be an option if the teacher decides that robotics provide an excellent context for teaching programming and focuses the activity exactly on this aspect. In other cases the activity plan includes a visual guide for students to follow in order to create their robot or provide a semi-constructed robot where students add specific parts (like sensors). In the conference and contest preparation workshop students construct and program their own robot. Digital constructions (i.e. programs defining the robot’s behavior) can be driven by brainstorming sessions about the tasks robots can perform (see for example section 4.3).

Physical constructions

Some activity-plans focus on the process of constructing a robot from scratch where the morphology of the robot is a parameter influencing its behavior. This is the case of the ECER conference (see section 4.6 and 4.5). The robotic Insect (see section 4.13) is a similar case where the emphasis is on concepts of electrical engineering. An activity plan that focuses and supports with concrete steps the design process is the “Crazy robots”. In this case students engage in designing and prototyping a robot. Specifically the first phase consists of a set of steps that it is based on the characteristics of robotic constructions: Robot task (assignment); Robot Interaction; Robot morphology (looks and materials); Robot behavior; Robot parts. Prototyping simulates the design process as it is undertaken by groups with different interests and expertise: Sales and marketing group, Engineering, Human Robot Interaction group, Research and development group, Design group. We consider this as an activity plan that it is fine-tuned to the characteristics of constructions with robotics and it has a very strong social dimension fostering by design communication and discussion between the groups.

The Botball preparation workshop (see section 4.5) although it doesn’t support a specific construction helps students to familiarize with the physical parts of Botball and with their functionalities through small tasks and examples. This seems to be a good introductory process for supporting student acquaintance with a robotic kit in order for the students to further engage with physical constructions. In the next version of the activity plan template we will include a more detailed description of small tasks and examples supporting the familiarization with a robotic kit.

Teaching Methods to support constructionist activity

A close look at the activity plans reveals that they demonstrate an implicit methodology for supporting student constructionist activity. In some cases activity plans use one of the methods below or a mix and match.

INCLUDING TASKS WITH GRADUAL COMPLEXITY

Activity plans which include tasks with gradual complexity, start with simple procedures or physical constructions and in consecutive steps new elements are added in the process. For example the activity plan “Making a robot smart” (see section 4.7) includes the following programming tasks: move a robot four blocks, detect an obstacle and stop, detect an obstacle make a U- turn and move for 4 floor plates, detect an obstacle avoid it and continue to the initial route. In case of physical constructions they provide a basic construction and then students are expected to add parts (like sensors)

PROVIDING EXAMPLES FOR ANALYSIS AND HYPOTHESIS TESTING

Instead of employing direct instruction (i.e. introducing loops) to introduce a concept or explain an example, constructionist methodology might focus on providing students with an example and ask them to test it and observe the behavior of the robot with the aim of identifying the role of specific programming concepts and structures like loops. This is a teaching and learning process which makes use of the affordances of digital constructionist environments where the observation of the generated behavior (i.e. feedback) its analysis provide the grounds for the formulation of a hypothesis about how things work (Yiannoutsou & Mavrikis, 2012). This method is demonstrated in section 4.7 where students are expected to find out the role of the loop and its parameters in a program, which results in moving the robot until it detects an object at 20 cm away.

MODIFYING AND EXTENDING GIVEN EXAMPLES

Another approach encountered in the activity plans that can support student constructionist activity is for the teacher to provide a ready made example and ask from the students to change it so that it demonstrates a slightly different behavior. This method allows students to focus on concepts that are relevant to the specific learning objectives (white box) and without struggling with complexities that are not relevant to the specific activity plan (black box) (For a detailed discussion of the black and white box approach see Kynigos, 2004). The Educational Technology Lab of the University of Athens has developed a theoretical construct in the design of digital learning environments (technologies and learning activities) which extends the idea of modifying given examples to modifying half-baked digital constructs (Kynigos, 2007). The term “half – baked” is coined by Kynigos (ibid) to describe exploratory digital environments conceived, by design, to call for modification and change supporting targeted learning. This approach of “half-baked” designs will be explored in the second year of ER4STEM.

3.4 ARGUMENTATION, DISCUSSION AND MAKER CULTURE

Orchestration of work in the organized workshops - irrespectively of context (formal non formal)-involved group work and whole classroom discussions (assembly discussions). Collaborative work and sharing of ideas and constructions was a central issue: a) in the design rationale of the activity plans for robotics (see for example D.2.1 and Yiannoutsou, Nikitopoulou, Kynigos, Gueorguiev, & Fernandez, 2016) b) in the discussions with ER4STEM partners and UoA teachers regarding the

implementation of the workshops c) in student reflections and d) in the evaluation of Scientix ambassadors (see section 5). Specifically, before the implementation of the workshops it was suggested that teachers should include a social dimension in their design where students in the middle of the workshops should describe to other students in the same class what they have created up to the moment and what where their problems and their future plans. The same process was supposed to be repeated at the end of the process where groups should share an image of their robot, their code a short description of what their robot does. For the group of Greek teachers it was suggested to use Edmodo⁴. Edmodo was selected for the following reasons: a) it is free b) it allows collaboration and post view among different teachers c) follows the familiar facebook interaction of posting comments and attachments. The idea of introducing a blog to describe and present final constructions was also introduced to other ER4STEM partners through the pre-evaluation kit (D.6.1) shared among the participants for the standardization of the evaluation process. The rationale behind this suggestion was to stress the social dimension of constructions and especially to foster aspects of the maker culture where ideas are explained and shared, help is sought and advice is provided. However, an overview of the activity plans shows that although orchestration of the students involved almost exclusively group work and discussions in the classroom the sequence of teaching activities does not include time for sharing constructions providing advice and help. Thus, as we will show in the relevant section of this deliverable, future refinement of the activity plan template will include a structuring of orienting collaborative work towards the maker culture.

3.5 MAIN ACTIVITIES – IN TEACHING AND LEARNING SEQUENCE

In this section we attempt to group and briefly describe the activities integrated in the activity plans to support the teaching and learning process with robotics. The first version of the activity plans includes combinations of the activities describe next.

Introductory activities

Introductory sessions usually include presentations, discussions, short hands –on activities with robots and even robot simulation activities with the students simulating the behavior of a robot. Specifically introductory sessions might include one of or a combination of the following activities:

Presentations might refer to: a) the task; b) aspects about robots, their uses, their design; etc. c) the robotic kit that is going to be used ;d) the rules of working with robots and e) collaborating with other students and researchers.

Presentations might be followed or replaced by discussions that develop around a central question like: what is a robot, what tasks a robot can perform, are robots part of our lives etc.

Introductory sessions quite often, especially when they include presentation of the robotic kit, include a short hands on experimentation with the robot like making the robot move towards a specific direction, make a sound, turn etc.

⁴ <https://www.edmodo.com/home>

An interesting introductory activity involved the simulation of the robot's behavior (see activity plan "learning the basics about programming with thymio II" section 4.3. This introductory activity involves the simulation of two main roles per group of students: one student will be the robot and the rest of the group will be the designer of the robot. Specifically, the rest of the group will design a maze in which the robot – student should navigate blindfolded. The group should provide to the robot-student the directions for the navigation of the robot before entering the maze. Then the teacher uses the experience from this activity as a basis to introduce concepts related to the way robots function and the importance of robotic parts like sensors.

Programming oriented activities

Programming oriented activities focus on specific concepts like sequential programming, loops, event handling etc. The emphasis of these activities is on engaging students with the programming language in order for the students to be able to use the programming concepts as instruments to define the robot behavior. Robot behavior is used as a feedback mechanism for the students to make conjectures and refine their understanding of the programming concepts. Usually, programming activities are followed by tasks, which focus on the robot behavior and make use of the programming concepts introduced. Examples of such activities are the following: Don't fall off the table; Going straight; Avoid crash; Trip in a corridor; Friendly pet; Bright colors; Line follower etc. (for a detailed description of these activities see section 4.3. Examples of such activities can be found in most activity plans)

Engineering and design oriented activities

Engineering and design oriented activities focus mainly on the robot (physical construction) and its characteristics. This set of activities might include:

- Construction of the robot using a visual guide (this is an activity suggested for beginners)
- Construction of the robot with reference to a specific morphology (e.g. construct an insect) without other help
- Play with and explore the robot's behavior, using ready-made pieces of code
- Enhance the behavior of a pre-constructed robot with adding new parts

Construction of the robot might be structured according to the following design activities

- Robot task (assignment)
- Robot interaction
- Robot morphology (looks and materials)
- Robot behavior
- Robot parts

Another approach to the construction of a robot is suggested in "Crazy Robots" (see section 4.4) where prototyping is following the actual design process of a robotic company including tasks that refer to: a) Sales and marketing; b) Engineering; c) Human Robot Interaction; d) Research and development; e) Design and f) Evaluation of the product (from the "sales department" and from the user's perspective)

All activity plans include a combination of programming and engineering activities. The activity plan designed for the contest preparation workshop includes a nice balance of engineering and programming activities: First prototype: construct a simple robot (beginners use a guide);

Programming principles - simple movements; Complex programming structures, using sensors; Experimentation with parts of a robotic kit using short assignments and examples. Similarly the conference includes a set of competitions which integrate programming and engineering activities (see section 4.6)

Evaluation activities

For the purposes of the project evaluation followed a standardized process, which was the same for all activity plans. However, evaluation activities like peer-reviewing which were expected to happen in the context of construction activities and during student's social interaction were not documented in sufficient detail in the activity plans.

4 FIRST VERSION OF ACTIVITY PLANS

In this section we present the actual activity plans designed according to the activity template presented in section 2. In order for workshop organizers to use the activity plan template to design their activity plans, UoA discussed explained and refined the dimensions of the template a) in project meetings with ER4STEM partners and b) in a one day workshop with teachers (in UoA-ETL). To further illustrate and clarify each aspect of the template, UoA – ETL provided to the ERW organizers an example of activity plan designed with the specific template.

4.1 INTRODUCTION TO DASH AND DOT

AUTHORS

Annalise Duca, Angele Giuliano, Joanna Pullicino (Designers)

Partner: Across Limits, Malta

Focus, Set up and Requirements of the activity

CURRICULUM

Select NO if the scenario is not aligned with the curriculum of your country and YES if it is. Please mention the relevant subject matter.

NO YES Subject: Mathematics and ICT

CONTENT

Choose categories and give a rating of the level of emphasis on concepts from each of the following domains

<input type="checkbox"/> Science	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Technology	<input type="checkbox"/> Business	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Engineering	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Arts	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Mathematics
(0-10)	(0-10)	(0-10)	(0-10)	(0-10)	(0-10)
0	10	0	6	2	5

OBJECTIVES

<i>Subject related</i>	Introducing basic programming and applying them to mathematical concepts e.g. constructing a right angled triangle, directions and motion, drawing various shapes etc.
<i>Technology use related</i>	Dash and Dot and the applications that come with it. Namely: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Blockly – A drag and drop tool to program ▪ Path – Drawing tool that allows for drawing a path and the robot will follow ▪ Go – A remote control app
<i>Social and action related</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Discussions between the students to find the best solutions for the activity ▪ Teamwork ▪ Exploration to find solutions
<i>Argumentation and fostering of maker culture:</i>	Groups assisting each other to work out activities

TIME**Duration:** 2 half days**Schedule:** 4 hours per session - total of 8 hours**MATERIALS AND ARTIFACTS**

<i>Digital artifact</i>	Visual interface
<i>Robotic artifact</i>	The robot is prebuilt
<i>Student's workbook and manual</i>	Activity sheets detailing the activity to be solved. No manual needed as Robot is already built.
<i>Teacher's instruction book and manual:</i>	Powerpoint presentation showing the students the activity to be undertaken. Tutors had the solution on powerpoint too which was kept away from the students until they reasoned it out.

Students and space**STUDENTS (TARGET AUDIENCE)**

<i>Sex and Age:</i>	Boys & girls, 8-10 years old
<i>Prior knowledge:</i>	No prior knowledge is required. However exposure to digital literacy helps
<i>Nationality and cultural background</i>	The majority were Maltese. At the church school all students were Maltese At the public school, one student was Muslim At the private school, there was a mix of nationalities and around one quarter of the students was foreign. Nationalities not taken note of.
<i>Social status and social environment</i>	For example: underprivileged area OR mainstream public school OR elite private school 1 church school

	1 state school 1 private, independent school
<i>Special needs and abilities</i>	All schools cater for mainstream teaching; however in every class there was a learning support assistant for between 1 - 3 students who had delay issues with learning or ADD or ADHD or dyslexia amongst others

SPACE INFO

Organizational and cultural context: In schools within a hall or a gymnasium during school hours on school days.

Physical characteristics: indoors

Social Orchestration

POPULATION

Students: 20-26 students per workshop

Tutors: 3-4 per workshop

GROUPING:

Grouping criteria	Mixed ability, mixed gender
<i>Setting:</i>	Students sitting on the floor in a hall or gymnasium facing a screen during presentations and holding a tablet and a robot during the robotic activities. Each group of between 2 - 3 students had a tablet and a robot. Each group had a "mat" to be able to stay within their space and avoid running around.

INTERACTION DURING THE ACTIVITY (EMPHASIS)

Actions	Exchange ideas, dialogue, negotiation, debate
<i>Relationships</i>	Collaborative, competitive
<i>Roles in the group</i>	Constant roles- instructed students to equally share the robot and tablet, and discuss activities for solving together
<i>Support by the tutor(s)</i>	Support, intervene, facilitate, teaching

Teaching and Learning Procedures

TEACHER'S ROLE

Function: presenting, teaching and facilitating.

TEACHING METHODS

Teacher's approaches: demonstrate, setting the challenges, intervening if students got stuck

EXPECTED STUDENT ACTIVITY

Students during the activity are expected to engage in the following actions: Writing, observing, constructing, discussing, negotiating, exploring, solving.

STUDENT LEARNING PROCESSES

<i>Designed Conflicts and misconceptions</i>	Not applicable
<i>Learning processes emphasized:</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Focusing on analyzing how the robot behaves based on the instructions given. ▪ Introducing “If..then..else” and Loops ▪ Emphasis on how different programs can have the same result on the robot.
<i>Expected relevance of alternative knowledge</i>	Students were expected to reason out how they would behave in everyday situations to program the instructions and get the robot to move accordingly

STUDENT PRODUCTIONS

PRODUCTION	DESCRIPTION
<i>Artifacts - robots</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Assignment: Robot needed to move around a track without hitting it. ▪ Interaction: Robot needed to hear a clap and action accordingly ▪ Morphology: N.A. ▪ Behavior: N.A. ▪ Material: N.A.
<i>Programs - code</i>	<p>Race Track: This programming task encourages students to think and arrive to the conclusion that the robot needs to detect that there is an obstacle, and use the correct “If then else” loop, nested in the correct order to make sure robot keeps working, even on another track.</p> <p>Clap Race: This task requires the student to make use of variables and also making use of nested “if then else: in order to make the Robot generate a number, multiply that number and move accordingly.</p>
<i>Discussions – arguments</i> (Describe the emphasis of the activity plan in one or more types of discussion provided in the next cell)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Descriptive - explanatory: description of a situation, a construct or an idea for others to understand and /or to implement ▪ Contributory - extending: sharing of resources, provision of ideas towards improving an existing construct or initial idea

Sequence and description of activities

PHASE 1: INTRODUCTION AND EXPERIMENTATION

Duration: 30 minutes

Orchestration: Presentation by the tutor and individual experimentation

Description: Tutors give a presentation to the students about robots, and non-robotic machines/appliances in everyday life. Uses of robots, advantages and disadvantages are discussed and students are asked to give their opinion. An explanation of the Dash and Dot robots and their functionalities is presented to the students. Following this the robot was handed out to the

student; they are allowed time to get over their excitement to hold, turn it around in their hands etc. Students are then asked to have a look at it well by turning it on and off, seeing it move etc. An introductory exercise is given to students where they are allowed to experiment by using a tablet to draw a right angled triangle, learn more about the robot menu such as sounds, directions etc.

Students are working together in groups of 2 and 3 and it was emphasised that they should discuss and work together to find solutions to their challenges.

PHASE 2: SEQUENTIAL PROGRAMMING

Duration: 3 hours

Orchestration: group work

Description: Students implement their first programs that have programming blocks in a row. No loops were needed. The first 6 activities focused on exploring how the robot could move - backwards, forwards, nod its head, shake its head, look left or right etc. Another task focused on its ability to talk. Students also got the robot to turn its eyes on and off through programming it. All these exercises were achieved by the students themselves - they discussed and helped each other and tried out solutions to find the right one.

PHASE 3: USING IF THEN/ LOOPS

Duration: 2 hours

Orchestration: group work

Description: We started with an explanation of Loops and If Then Else Statements. We made use of a real scenario – What would the robot do if it's raining outside and wants to go and play. How would you make him arrive to a destination without having to repeat the same thing.

Students then try to find a way to simplify their programs by avoiding using the same sequence of blocks many times in the same program. Almost spontaneously they try to use loop programming blocks. With teacher assistance, they recognize the usage, the conditions and the characteristics of the new programming structure and also the role of the sensors in executing a loop block.

PHASE 4: DETECTION AND LOOP

Duration: 2 hours

Orchestration: group work

Description: A robot in order to be “smart” (autonomous) has to avoid any obstacle that could be in its path. In puzzles 7 to 9 students are faced with tasks related to detection of sounds, movement and further movement. To solve these puzzles students need to make sure that they find the right “block” to use, and also make sure that they learn how to test and that the programme is really working as instructed. Finally in puzzle 10, we ask them to make use of a loop in an indirect way.

PHASE 5: - CLAP RACE / RACE TRACK

Duration: 1-2hours each

Description: One of the above challenges is done in the class. In the clap race, students need to explore variables. They are instructed to make the robot generate a number, multiply that number and make the robot move forward according. This is particular challenging especially for students who have not been exposed to programming beforehand.

In the race-track activity, students are instructed to built a race track. They need to program the robot to navigate through this track without hitting the “obstacles”. Students are told that their program should be able to work on any track, and therefore they need to make use of IF...then else...

PHASE 6: FEEDBACK AND EVALUATION

Duration: 5-10 minutes

Orchestration :group work

In addition to the activity sheets that students complete during activity phases, they also create a postcard for their friend to let them know what they experienced during the 2 workshops. A group of between 2 - 3 students was also interviewed.

Assessment Procedures

FOCUS	ASSESSMENT METHOD OR TOOL
<i>Are popular gender stereotypes about STEM held?</i>	Draw a scientist
<i>Past experience and existing attitudes to STEM subjects and careers</i>	Pre-questionnaire
<i>Past experience and existing attitudes to STEM subjects and careers Includes questions about the activities to help understand learner’s experiences of the workshop as a whole, what participants feel they have learned and what their future intentions are</i>	Post-questionnaire
<i>Understand the experience of participants and their reasons for particular actions</i>	Interview with focus group
	Peer assessment
	Essays- Tests-Student productions (code-robots-textual communication – presentations,)
	Observation notes
	Reflection Sheet

4.2 INTRODUCING ROBOTICS WITH ARDUINO, SCRATCH AND MINDMAPS

Practical Educational Robotics Workshop.

AUTHORS:

ESI CEE Team: Ivaylo Gueorguiev with the support and direct contribution of Pavel Varbanov, Petar Sharkov, Prof. Galina Momcheva, Dr. George Sharkov, Prof. Maria Nisheva, Christina Todorova and Georgi Georgiev

Partner: ESI CEE, Bulgaria

Focus, Set up and Requirements of the activity**CURRICULUM**

Select NO if the scenario is not aligned with the curriculum of your country and YES if it is. Please mention the relevant subject matter.

NO YES Subject: N.A.

CONTENT

Choose categories and give a rating of the level of emphasis on concepts from each of the following domains

<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Science	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Technology	<input type="checkbox"/> Business	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Engineering	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Arts	<input type="checkbox"/> Mathematics
(0-10)	(0-10)	(0-10)	(0-10)	(0-10)	(0-10)
4	10	0	6	2	0

OBJECTIVES

<i>Subject related</i>	Learn the key robotics elements (technology); construct a robot (technology & engineering) , develop a visual program to control the robot and to execute tasks (technology and maths); develop the creative thinking skills needed to find different applications of robotics in other fields (science, arts & business)
<i>Technology use related</i>	Arduino controllers; motor drivers; ultrasonic sensors; scratch or snap visual programing
<i>Social and action related</i>	Teamwork skills in a groups of 3-4 students; creative thinking of the whole class; ideas generation by individuals and achieving consensus in a team and in a class; and presenting results by the teams
<i>Argumentation and fostering of maker culture:</i>	Formulate and express ideas; listening skills; decision-making within a team, etc.

TIME

Duration: 2-6 weeks

Schedule: 2 or 3 workshops 4 hour each; 4 – 6 workshops 2 hours each

MATERIALS AND ARTIFACTS

<i>Digital artifact</i>	Students will work with Scratch or Snap; Arduino IDE; python s2a_fm and pymata program are used to connect the robot to a computer and to control it with visual interfaces. Optional hummingbird server could be used if Finch robot is used for the programming classes and Choreograph could be used to demonstrate the NAO humanoid robot.
<i>Robotic artifact</i>	Custom set developed by ESI CEE: gearbox; chassis; chains and wheels; Arduino controller; motors driver; breadboard; jump wires; ultrasonic module; Bluetooth module or USB cable; batteries and batteries holders. NAO and Finch robots for demonstration are optional.
<i>Student's workbook and manual</i>	Visual Guide how to construct the robot; tasks and illustrations.
<i>Teacher's instruction book and manual:</i>	Manual How to connect and program the robot.

Students and space

STUDENTS (TARGET AUDIENCE)

<i>Sex and Age:</i>	Boys & girls, 8-12 years
<i>Prior knowledge:</i>	No prior knowledge required
<i>Nationality and cultural background</i>	Bulgarian, cultural background diverse, capital city and other cities
<i>Social status and social environment</i>	Mainstream public schools and private schools
<i>Special needs and abilities</i>	N.A.

SPACE INFO

Organizational and cultural context: Workshops in school, either in classroom or computer room during regular school time.

Physical characteristics: indoors.

Social Orchestration

POPULATION

Students: 20-30 students in a class.

Tutors: 1 or 2 researchers + 1 or 2 assistants.

GROUPING:

<i>Grouping criteria</i>	No specific criteria are applied – teachers formulate the groups
<i>Setting:</i>	One table and one PC per team of 3-4 students (max 5 students per

	team) , 1 robotic set for 1 team
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INTERACTION DURING THE ACTIVITY (EMPHASIS)

<i>Actions</i>	Learn the basics of robotics through demonstrations and games; construct an Arduino robot using visual instructions and guidance by the instructor, if needed; 2-hour creative workshop based on Tony Buzan's mind-mapping concept; programming and controlling Arduino robots or Finch robots through visual programming to complete simple tasks (task could be closely related to mathematics, algebra or geometry)
<i>Relationships</i>	Collaborative
<i>Roles in the group</i>	The roles are not predefined as we encourage the students to shift their roles between team leader, programmer, robot developer and presenter.
<i>Support by the tutor(s)</i>	Facilitator and consultant for robot construction; teacher and instructor for teaching of basics of robotics and creative thinking.

Teaching and Learning Procedures

TEACHER'S ROLE

Facilitator and consultant for robot construction; teacher and instructor for teaching the basics of robotics and creative thinking.

TEACHING METHODS

Demonstrate, engage by example, guide (e.g. setting initial program status), trigger investigation, orchestrate discussion.

EXPECTED STUDENT ACTIVITY

Students during the activity are expected to engage in the following actions: learning; analysing, creating, discussing, observing.

STUDENT LEARNING PROCESSES

<i>Designed Conflicts and misconceptions</i>	Competing is the main goal
<i>Learning processes emphasized:</i>	All students in the team work together and construct the robot. They are confident and know that building a simple robot is not difficult .
<i>Expected relevance of alternative knowledge</i>	Alternative knowledge will be encouraged to be demonstrated during the creativity session in which the students will have to associate the robot with other domains

STUDENT PRODUCTIONS

PRODUCTION	DESCRIPTION
<i>Artifacts - robots</i>	Defined engineering and programming tasks; open exercises and creative tasks
<i>Programs - code</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Structure of code-commands: visual programming following patterns that are typical for C and C++ programming

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Elements (e.g. iteration, selection, variables): variables, constants, simple cycles and logical functions such as if, and, or.- ▪ Conditionals (e.g. event handling): -using the ultrasonic sensor to detect and avoid obstacles or to direct the robot to objects.
<p><i>Discussions – arguments</i> (Describe the emphasis of the activity plan in one or more types of discussion provided in the next cell)</p>	<p>Discussions and reflections were left to the teachers in the classroom.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Descriptive - explanatory: description of base robotics elements such as sensors, processors, drivers, actuators; description of the general tasks and purpose. ▪ Alternative: provision of alternatives if a dead end is reached; ▪ Critical - objection: critical thinking about problems and possible solutions; ▪ Contributory - extending: discussions about alternative design or additions to the construction; software and purpose

Sequence and description of activities

Total duration of the activities will be in the range of 6-12 hours. The session in which the student will develop code and will animate the robots will be used as a buffer to compensate the time.

Orchestration: team of 3-4 students per table; enough free space in the center of the room for demonstrations; demo robots such as NAO; omnidirectional models or mobile telepresence robot + full set per a team.

Description:

MODULE 1: INTRODUCTION AND PRE-EVALUATION

(1/2 hour)

The researchers introduce themselves as robot enthusiasts and explain that in this workshop they will play and work together with the student teams in order to build together a real robot. The rules and safety instructions are explained:

Rules

- Everybody listens to the others and respect their ideas
- No direct competition, lets cooperate and have fun
- Questions and strange ideas are highly encouraged
- The researchers are facilitators and friends - everybody can argue with them regarding the content but not regarding the discipline

Safety instructions:

- Do not put small parts in the mouth - can have serious injury
- Do not connect batteries before the instructors check the model for short circuits - the robot can cause fire.
- Be careful when using jump wires and pins - you can feel pain.

Kids fill out pre-workshop evaluation form.

MODULE 2: WHAT IS A ROBOT

(1/2 – 1 hour)

The researchers discuss with student the key elements of the robots such as processors, drivers actuators and sensors. The researcher is using the available demo robots to show the elements. Children guess different types of robots such as industrial robots; home robots; humanoids; drones; toys and others.

MODULE 3 CONSTRUCTION

(1-2 hours)

Students build a robot using visual guides on printed cards or slideshow on computers. The instructor does not directly contribute during the building but help them to discover the right approach.

MODULE 4: ROBOT'S TOUCH

(1-2hours)

Once the models are built the researchers demonstrate in action different type of robots such as Nao, vGo, omnidirectional robots or other and facilitate Q&A session. During that time technical assistant or another researcher verifies the models to be sure that they are operational and no significant mistakes e.g. short circuits are present.

Student play with their models using predefined control program and PC keyboards. They pass through different obstacles and experiment with the physical characteristics of the models.

MODULE 5 LET'S IMAGINE...

(2 hours)

Researchers facilitate creativity session trough brainstorming and mind mapping on how the robots can support people in their life and what is the importance of robot for our civilization.

MODULE 6 PROGRAMMING

(2-3 hours)

Students learn how to control the robots with Scratch or Snap and they try to fulfill missions that were included in the brain storming by developing simplified code. The students are using proportions, arithmetic operations, geometry and other math domains in order to achieve their missions. The students could use paper, glue and other materials to decorate the robots

MODULE 7 EVALUATION

(1 hour)

Evaluation session is held for students to present their achievements and evaluate their experience.

Group and/or individual interviews are conducted and students fill out post-workshops questionnaires.

Assessment Procedures

FOCUS	ASSESSMENT METHOD OR TOOL
<i>Are popular gender stereotypes about STEM held?</i>	Draw a scientist
<i>Past experience and existing attitudes to STEM subjects and careers</i>	Pre-questionnaire
<i>Past experience and existing attitudes to STEM subjects and careers</i> <i>Includes questions about the activities to help understand learner's experiences of the workshop as a whole, what participants feel they have learned and what their future intentions are</i>	Post-questionnaire
<i>Understand the experience of participants and their reasons for particular actions</i>	Interview with focus group
	Peer assessment
	Essays- Tests-Student productions (code-robots-textual communication – presentations,)
	Observation notes
	Reflection Sheet

4.3 LEARNING THE BASICS OF PROGRAMMING WITH THYMIO II

AUTHORS

Julian Angel-Fernandez, Felix Hembach, and Johanness Pagitsch (Researchers)

Partner: TU Wien, Austria

Focus, Set up and Requirements of the activity

CURRICULUM

Select NO if the scenario is not aligned with the curriculum of your country and YES if it is. Please mention the relevant subject matter.

NO YES

CONTENT

Choose categories and give a rating of the level of emphasis on concepts from each of the following domains

<input type="checkbox"/> Science	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Technology	<input type="checkbox"/> Business	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Engineering	<input type="checkbox"/> Arts	<input type="checkbox"/> Mathematics
(0-10)	(0-10)	(0-10)	(0-10)	(0-10)	(0-10)
0	10	0	6	0	0

OBJECTIVES

<i>Subject related</i>	Introduction to basic programming
<i>Technology use related</i>	Programming
<i>Social and action related</i>	
<i>Argumentation and fostering of maker culture:</i>	

TIME

Duration: 1 session

Schedule: 4 hours

MATERIALS AND ARTIFACTS

<i>Digital artifact</i>	Thymio Programming Interfaces: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Visual Interface • Blockly • Text
<i>Robotic artifact</i>	Thymio II
<i>Student's workbook and manual</i>	Activity Sheets
<i>Teacher's instruction book and manual:</i>	None

Students and space

STUDENTS (TARGET AUDIENCE)

<i>Sex and Age:</i>	Boys & girls, 11-17 years old
<i>Prior knowledge:</i>	None
<i>Nationality and cultural background</i>	Austrian
<i>Social status and social environment</i>	In the workshop participate students from different cultural backgrounds
<i>Special needs and abilities</i>	None

SPACE INFO

Organizational and cultural context: In school computer lab

Physical characteristics: Indoors

Social Orchestration

POPULATION**Students:** 25**Tutors:** 2**GROUPING:**

Grouping criteria	Left upon the students to formulate groups
Setting:	

INTERACTION DURING THE ACTIVITY (EMPHASIS)

Actions	Exchange ideas, dialogue, negotiation, debate
Relationships	Collaborative
Roles in the group	Emergent roles
Support by the tutor(s)	Support and facilitate

Teaching and Learning Procedures**TEACHER'S ROLE**

Consultant

TEACHING METHODS

Facilitate the construction process, provide guidance when asked.

EXPECTED STUDENT ACTIVITY

Students during the activity are expected to engage in the following actions: Writing, observing, constructing, discussing, negotiating.

STUDENT LEARNING PROCESSES

<i>Designed Conflicts and misconceptions</i>	N.A.
<i>Learning processes emphasized:</i>	Basic programming concepts
<i>Expected relevance of alternative knowledge</i>	N.A.

STUDENT PRODUCTIONS

PRODUCTION	DESCRIPTION
<i>Artifacts - robots</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Assignment: Robot as a tool for the students to learn programming. ▪ Interaction: Thymio App (Aseba Studio). ▪ Morphology: The robot looks like a disk. ▪ Behavior: Tool ▪ Material: None
<i>Programs - code</i>	Elements: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Variables

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Conditionals
<p><i>Discussions – arguments</i> (Describe the emphasis of the activity plan in one or more types of discussion provided in the next cell)</p>	<p>Contributory - extending: sharing of resources, provision of ideas towards improving an existing construct or initial idea.</p>

Sequence and description of activities

PHASE 1: INTRODUCTION AND EXPERIMENTATION

Duration: 20 minutes

Orchestration: group work

Description: Participants are asked to form groups of 2 or 3. Once the groups have been created, each group should pick one person who will be blindfolded. The person selected is asked to leave the room, thus the other participants could arrange a “maze”, which has diverse obstacles. When the mazes are ready, the blindfolded participants are asked to re-enter and go at the beginning of their respective maze. Then each group should give instructions to the blindfolded participant in how to go to the end of the maze following two rules. First, all the instructions should be given at the beginning, once the person starts to walk no further commands could be given. Second, the person cannot bump into the “walls”. As soon as all the groups have finished, they are officially a team. The tutors discuss with the teams about the problems they encountered during the activity and they use this discussion as trigger to introduce the functioning of robots and the importance of sensors in performing tasks like the one performed earlier.

PHASE 2: STUDYING THYMIO’S SENSORS

Duration: 20-30 minutes

Orchestration: group work

Description: Participants study Thymio’s sensors. Therefore, they are asked to connect the robot to the computer and observe the variables that are available in the interface. Groups are asked to focus on the distance sensors and take some measurements. Then, participants should answer the question: what kind of relationship do you see between the real world and Thymio’s sensor values?

Once participants have finished with the distance sensors, they are asked to focus their attention to the microphone, experiment with it and document what happen.

PHASE 3: FIRST ASEBA PROGRAM

Duration: 10-20 minutes

Orchestration: group work

Description: Participants program for first time in aseba and the tutors explain the basics of sequential programming. First one of the tutors demonstrates by example on how participants can program the robot and then they are asked to:

- Generate a precise sequence of colors.
- Search in aseba library, for the commands that make the robot to move. Once they have found the commands, they have to make the robot move forward and then turn.
- Guide thymio through a maze.

PHASE 4: EVENT PROGRAMMING – FOLLOWING COMMANDS

Duration: 10-20minutes

Orchestration: group work

Description: Introduce the participants on the event-programming paradigm, which is the one used to program Thymio. To achieve this, first the participants are asked to copy and paste an example code and watch what does. Once they have understood what the code does, they are asked to program the robot to move towards a specific direction when a button is pressed.

PHASE 5: DON'T FALL OFF THE TABLE!

Duration: 20 minutes

Orchestration: group work

Description: The participants will learn to make the robot to autonomously react when the ground sensors detect that there the robot has reached the “end” of the table. The tutors at this point should advice the participants to set a low value in the velocity of the robot, so if the robot does not detect the border, the participants could catch it.

PHASE 6: GOING STRAIGHT!

Duration: 15 minutes

Orchestration: group work

Description: The participants will learn to use Thymio’s timers. During this phase, participants are asked to do the following: they should program the robot so it starts moving when a button is pushed or when clapping is heard. The second step is to make the robot to stop autonomously. To do this they must use robot’s timer to stop the robot after specific time.

PHASE 7: AVOID A CRASH!

Duration: 15 minutes

Orchestration: group work

Description: The participants program the robot to autonomously avoid obstacles by using the proximity sensors.

PHASE 8: TRIP IN A CORRIDOR!

Duration: 20 minutes

Orchestration: group work

Description: The participants will use a template with specific markings depicting a corridor (S-shape corridor). Their goal is to make the robot drive through the corridor without moving in zig-zag. Participants must use ground sensors and timers.

PHASE 9: FRIENDLY PET!

Duration: 20 minutes

Orchestration: group work

Description: The participants learn how to use sensors, values and conditionals (IF and ELSE). The final goal is to program the robot to follow a participant's hand. If the robot gets too close to the hand, it must stop.

PHASE 10: BRIGHT COLORS!

Duration: 15 minutes

Orchestration: group work

Description: During this task participants will use variables to change the robot's color. The participants should program the robot to change colors each time a button is pressed.

PHASE 11: LINE FOLLOWER

Duration: 15 minutes

Orchestration: group work

Description: The participants will program the robot to follow a line. To make things interesting, each group should make their line road.

Assessment Procedures

FOCUS	ASSESSMENT METHOD OR TOOL
<i>Are popular gender stereotypes about STEM held?</i>	Draw a scientist
<i>Past experience and existing attitudes to STEM subjects and careers</i>	Pre-questionnaire
<i>Past experience and existing attitudes to STEM subjects and careers Includes questions about the activities to help understand learner's experiences of the workshop as a whole, what participants feel they have learned and what their future intentions are</i>	Post-questionnaire
<i>Understand the experience of</i>	Interview with focus group

<i>participants and their reasons for particular actions</i>	
	Peer assessment
	Essays- Tests-Student productions (code-robots-textual communication – presentations,)
	Observation notes
	Reflection Sheet

4.4 CRAZY ROBOTS – ROBOTIC PRODUCT DEVELOPMENT

AUTHOR

Lara Lammer (Researcher)

Partner: TU Wien, Austria

Focus, Set up and Requirements of the activity

CURRICULUM

Select NO if the scenario is not aligned with the curriculum of your country and YES if it is. Please mention the relevant subject matter.

NO YES

CONTENT

Choose categories and give a rating of the level of emphasis on concepts from each of the following domains

<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Science	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Technology	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Business	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Engineering	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Arts	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Mathematics
(0-10)	(0-10)	(0-10)	(0-10)	(0-10)	(0-10)
8	10	8	8	8	1

OBJECTIVES

<i>Subject related</i>	Design a robotic product from scratch (technology design); design, execute and present a user study (science); develop a marketing and sales strategy (business); basic understanding of circuits and sensors (engineering); design the robot's morphology and interaction (art, science); basic mathematics during testing ($s=v*t$ or Pythagoras)
<i>Technology use related</i>	Mattie robot, programming of Arduino
<i>Social and action related</i>	Whole class decides on one robot concept, sales and marketing group often takes the role of coordinator, children learn about different areas in robotics (e.g. also psychology), different

	personality types (introvert, feeling type, etc.). Students should be acquainted with the idea that in real-life you may collaborate with persons that you don't like but recognize that they can contribute valuable ideas and work to the team.
<i>Argumentation and fostering of maker culture:</i>	Testing of the prototype from two perspectives: engineering and user perspective.

TIME

Duration: One semester

Schedule: 3 workshops: each lasting two school hours, +1/2 hour visit to the lab and Romeo robot demo after the second workshop

MATERIALS AND ARTIFACTS

<i>Digital artifact</i>	Robot sound files
<i>Robotic artifact</i>	Mattie robot (TU Wien construct) in different shapes, e.g. bee, fish, trash bin, toilet, Wall-E etc.
<i>Student's workbook and manual</i>	5-step plan for the design process, different instructions and circuit plans
<i>Teacher's instruction book and manual:</i>	N.A.

Students and space

STUDENTS (TARGET AUDIENCE)

<i>Sex and Age:</i>	Boys & girls, 10-14 years (mainly 10-12)
<i>Prior knowledge:</i>	No prior knowledge required
<i>Nationality and cultural background</i>	Mostly Austrian, cultural background diverse, capital city and surroundings.
<i>Social status and social environment</i>	Mainstream public school
<i>Special needs and abilities</i>	N.A.

SPACE INFO

Organizational and cultural context: Two workshops in school, either in classroom or handicraft room, and one workshop at the university; during regular school time.

Physical characteristics: Indoors.

Social Orchestration

POPULATION

Students: 10-27 (big groups require more tutors, are more chaotic and demanding, but it works)

Tutors: 2 (+teacher and more tutors when necessary)

GROUPING:

Grouping criteria	Preference of subject (engineering, science, human-robot interaction, design or sales & marketing)
Setting:	Can be adapted to different indoor settings. Students need to watch a beamer presentation but also work in groups afterwards.

INTERACTION DURING THE ACTIVITY (EMPHASIS)

Actions	Result-oriented, solution-oriented
Relationships	Collaborative
Roles in the group	Emergent roles
Support by the tutor(s)	Support where needed, the students solve the problem and present their solution.

Teaching and Learning Procedures

TEACHER'S ROLE

Frontal presentation with discussion; during group work mentoring or watching

TEACHING METHODS

Partly instructionist, mostly constructionist

EXPECTED STUDENT ACTIVITY

Students during the activity are expected to engage in the following actions: action, writing, observing, creating, presenting.

STUDENT LEARNING PROCESSES

<i>Designed Conflicts and misconceptions</i>	All five different teams work on the same robot. If they do not communicate, the things they do will not come together, they need to communicate and align through the whole process, but the activity is designed that they learn this by experience.
<i>Learning processes emphasized:</i>	Holistic concept to show students that different talents and interests can all work in robotics
<i>Expected relevance of alternative knowledge</i>	Depending on what robot they design, e.g. one group did a robot for children with down-syndrome and one student from the class (with a sibling having down-syndrome) was their expert and they learned about this.

STUDENT PRODUCTIONS

PRODUCTION	DESCRIPTION
<i>Artifacts - robots</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Assignment: Mostly needs from the students and their families, like cooking and serving food, helping with homework, protecting, being a friend, entertaining, transporting from A to B, etc. ▪ Interaction: Mostly via speech ▪ Morphology: Mostly anthropomorphic, then zoomorphic or cartoon-like. ▪ Behavior: Mostly friendly; either butler or friend or both. ▪ Material: This is the most difficult part where kids perform

	better if the five steps are iterated: “do you think the robot can help you cooking, when it does not have an arm?”
<i>Programs - code</i>	N.A.
<i>Discussions – arguments</i> (Describe the emphasis of the activity plan in one or more types of discussion provided in the next cell)	Discussions and reflections were left to the teachers in the classroom <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Descriptive - explanatory: description of a situation, a construct or an idea for others to understand and /or to implement. ▪ Alternative: provision of solutions to problems, provision of alternatives if a dead end is reached. ▪ Critical - objection: revision of other’s constructs and ideas, identification of problems, challenge of ideas. ▪ Contributory - extending: sharing of resources, provision of ideas towards improving an existing construct or initial idea.

Sequence and description of activities

WORKSHOP 1: IDEATION

Duration: 100 min (= two school hours)

Orchestration: presentation, assembly discussion, each student works on clay model

Description: The researchers introduce themselves as robot experts and explain that in this workshop, the children will learn how to design robots while the researchers will learn from their ideas how to build better robots in the future. We expect that children broaden their view of technology as “something that we build to make our lives easier” and that they will consider that “true robots act autonomously”. From then on, children start thinking critically about it. Children are also introduced to the idea that “Real robots are highly complex and designed by a team of experts from different disciplines (designers, human-robot-interaction experts, programmers, engineers, etc.)”. They are also encouraged to think as product designers during “ideation” phase and offered a simple structure to conceptualize a robot from scratch, using materials like clay, stones, feathers, plush wire, etc. Furthermore, children are not constrained by the limits of technology: there are no limits for their robots’ capabilities when they start brainstorming. The teacher on the other hand, records students’ ideas in a power point or in the blog of the class or in a template.

When all the aforementioned are actualized and children are guided step-by-step through five important topics, eventually they design a robot like a product designer.

STEP 1 – ROBOT TASK (“ASSIGNMENT”).

The children are asked to imagine a robot for themselves that does anything they want. Every idea is valuable in this phase and not discarded as useless or undoable. Children are rather encouraged to think about a helper and adapt their ideas to this concept.

STEP 2 – ROBOT INTERACTION.

Known and not yet invented applications are both encouraged equally. Children learn that some of their ideas need scientists who invent new things that are then built into the robots by engineers. How would you tell your robot what to do? Would you talk to it in a secret language or with signs? Would the robot understand your thoughts? Or would you use an app to control it?

STEP 3 – ROBOT MORPHOLOGY (“LOOKS AND MATERIALS”).

We divide the third step, robot morphology, into “looks” and “materials”. First, we introduce four different categories of robot morphology “Robots can look like machines, like cartoon characters, like animals (zoomorphic) or similar to humans with a head and body (anthropomorphic)”. Second, we talk about different materials robots can be made of, and describe some properties: They can feel smooth, hard, furry, etc. How would your robot feel like?

STEP 4 – ROBOT BEHAVIOR.

In the fourth step, the abstract concept of autonomous behavior needs to be explained in a manner that children understand. We use two paths: In order to make the abstract word “behavior” more concrete, we describe roles (or personas) with which children identify. Would you like your robot to be rather like a butler, a teacher, a protector, a pet or a friend? We also explain that robots have rules to obey and introduce the Three Laws of Robotics.

STEP 5 – ROBOT PARTS.

This last step brings the previous steps together. The researchers show pictures of mechanic and electronic parts: some are used in every robot; others depend on what the robot does, how it looks like or how it should behave. In the beginning of the design process (ideation), the focus is on the holistic view of a product developer who needs to know what parts are needed but is not concerned with the details.

After this introduction children immediately start building a prototype with modeling clay that they can take home to show family and peers. In an expanded 5-step plan concept with follow-up workshops that move from ideation to prototyping, Step 5 is a starting point to go into more detail by using simple technology (e.g. maker electronics) to work out technically feasible solutions.

WORKSHOP 2: PROTOTYPING

Duration: 100 minutes + approx. 30 min lab visit

Orchestration: presentation, assembly discussion, group work

Description: Before we start the second workshop, the class visits the Vision for Robotics Lab at the Vienna University of Technology and are shown a demonstration of the Romeo robot from the company Aldebaran (<http://projetromeo.com/>) where we introduce them to the robot’s different capabilities and sensors including 3D cameras and computer vision. In the workshop after the demonstration, we start the theory session by repeating definitions from the first workshop: what is technology; what is a robot; how do robot experts translate their ideas into a product (i.e. the three incisive stages “ideation”, “prototyping”, and evaluation). We also repeat the five steps and underlin our next focus on prototyping and getting deeper into different robot parts.

It is also an important topic of this workshop to introduce children to robot experts: “What kind of people are they? What do they know?” We explain children important areas in robotics such as mechatronics and coding but also sociology, psychology, design, or ethics. We tell them about three different personality traits to consider when collaborating: thinking and feeling types, generalist and specialist thinkers, and extrovert and introvert types. We also introduce them to multiple intelligences (Howard Gardner) underlining that each of them is unique with their interests and

talents, and can contribute different aspects to a team. We also talk about what robotics experts all have in common: curiosity, creativity, persistence and the ability to collaborate.

Finally, the “CEO of Crazy Robots Company” (one researcher) assigns the “Mattie robot project manager” (the other researcher) with the project to build a robot for children with a budget of 300 Euros. The project manager explains the concept of the Mattie robot, and then divides the students in groups. Each group has different tasks that are described next:

Sales & Marketing: In this task, students define a target customer group (e.g., children at a specific age or with special needs as users and their parents, grandparents or other relatives as buyers) and the tasks of the robot along with its design and behavior. They have to coordinate their ideas with all other groups. They discuss with the design group which materials are available, with the engineering and research groups the capabilities of the existing technology and with the human-robot interaction groups the best way of interaction with the target group. They learn about the 4 Ps of marketing (product, price, place, promotion) and think of a strategy for their product.

Engineering: This is a typical task for children interested in STEM and robotics. The students connect the electronic parts using jumper wires, a breadboard and step-by-step instructions. They need to figure out how the motors need to turn for the robot to drive straight or turn left or right. We programmed the microcontroller beforehand because of time constraints; in an expanded workshop, students can also code. This is a classic technical assignment with a predetermined goal that has to be achieved.

Human-Robot Interaction (HRI): The children in this group need to define the types of sound files the robot will play and design an interface for the interaction. They need to coordinate with the sales & marketing and design groups so that their sound files and buttons match the overall concept and design of the robot. When all agree, this group records the sound files and assists the design team that creates the buttons.

Research & Development: This group is like the research & development department of a company or researchers at a research institution who develop new sensors. For this task we let students get acquainted with real sensors and teach them what to do with sensor readings – a number which represents a voltage. In a wooden box six sensors are connected to a display that shows the current sensor readings. First, students have to identify the different sensors by stressing them. Then, they help the engineering team choose the right sensors for the Mattie robot to follow light. They discuss how to use the other sensors on the robot and what additional sensors can be developed. For groups who finish quickly there is an optional task: the students connect a tilt sensor with an LED and test it as a possible anti-theft solution.

Design: The task of this group is the design of the robot, especially the body or hull – the transparent bucket, cut on top and bottom – with decoration materials. Before the group can start crafting, they need to decide with the other groups what the robot is for and for whom. The design needs to fit the robot concept and the customer (user) group. The designers also help the HRI group to finalize their buttons on the robot with conductive paint or tin foil.

PHASE 3: EVALUATION

Duration: 100 minutes (in some cases + 50 minutes when teacher could organize next class hour)

Orchestration: group work

Description: In the third workshop, groups can complete tasks from the second workshop, especially the design team needs the time for e.g. finishing buttons or other parts of the robot. The theory part is kept very short, again repeating definitions and shortly explaining what evaluation is. Then, some students are given the unfinished tasks from the second workshop. The rest of the class is divided into two teams: technical evaluation and product (or user) evaluation.

The technical group evaluates the chassis, e.g. average speed of robot, maximum distance of infrared receiver, reliability of the ultrasound sensor for detecting objects, or average deviation on a straight line. The user group is again divided into user study experts and marketing experts. While the user study experts design the study and prepare questionnaires and interview guidelines, the marketing experts design a product poster. When design and buttons are finished, the whole robot is put together and the user study is conducted either with classmates or students recruited from other classes. Then, the presentations follow: Product presentation, robot demonstration and presentation of evaluation results.

Assessment Procedures

FOCUS	ASSESSMENT METHOD OR TOOL
<i>Are popular gender stereotypes about STEM held?</i>	Draw a scientist
<i>Past experience and existing attitudes to STEM subjects and careers</i>	Pre-questionnaire
<i>Past experience and existing attitudes to STEM subjects and careers</i> <i>Includes questions about the activities to help understand learner's experiences of the workshop as a whole, what participants feel they have learned and what their future intentions are</i>	Post-questionnaire
<i>Understand the experience of participants and their reasons for particular actions</i>	Interview with focus group
	Peer assessment
	Essays- Tests- Student productions (code-robots-textual communication – presentations): 5 step plan template filled, in one version of the concept a storyboard “one day with my robot”, robot clay model, Mattie robot concept, exterior design and human-robot interaction buttons and sound
	Observation notes
	Reflection Sheet

4.5 ECER-BOTBALL-PREPARATION-WORKSHOP

AUTHOR

Lisa Vittori

Partner: PRIA, Austria

Focus, Set up and Requirements of the activity

CURRICULUM

Select NO if the scenario is not aligned with the curriculum of your country and YES if it is. Please mention the relevant subject matter.

NO YES

CONTENT

Choose categories and give a rating of the level of emphasis on concepts from each of the following domains

Science Technology Business Engineering Arts Mathematics
 (0-10) (0-10) (0-10) (0-10) (0-10) (0-10)
 7 10 4 10 0 2

OBJECTIVES

<i>Subject related</i>	Identify and study key elements of a robot as well as the essential programming concepts to build and program a robot, which is capable of competing in the ECER tournament
<i>Technology use related</i>	Programming of the Botball controller in C
<i>Social and action related</i>	Working in a team, assuming different roles, overcoming of difficulties
<i>Argumentation and fostering of maker culture:</i>	Expression of ideas, exchange of solutions to mutual problems.

TIME

Duration: 16 h**Schedule:** 2 consecutive days with 8 hours each

MATERIALS AND ARTIFACTS

<i>Digital artifact</i>	Programming language C
<i>Robotic artifact</i>	Botball robotic kit, the form must be developed by the students, usually it is a kind of vehicle
<i>Student's workbook and manual</i>	Manual for the controller, the sensors and the motors, step-by-step instructions for building a first drivable robot as a basis for the workshop, workshop slides
<i>Teacher's instruction book and manual:</i>	Workshop slides

Students and space

STUDENTS (TARGET AUDIENCE)

<i>Sex and Age:</i>	Boys & girls, 15 - 18 years old
<i>Prior knowledge:</i>	No prior knowledge required
<i>Nationality and cultural background</i>	Mainly Austrian students with some participants from other countries which don't do a separate Botball workshop (e.g. Poland, Belgium, Egypt, etc.)
<i>Social status and social environment</i>	Mixed environment, a large part from public technical high schools
<i>Special needs and abilities</i>	N.A.

SPACE INFO

Organizational and cultural context: A large room for the workshop event, which is a special event occupying school and free time, participation is voluntary.

Physical characteristics: indoors with table-space for placing laptops and building the first robot and space for letting the robot move.

Social Orchestration

POPULATION

Students: up to 100

Tutors: 1 lecturer, 3 assistant tutors.

GROUPING:

<i>Grouping criteria</i>	Students formulate their own groups using their own criteria.
<i>Setting:</i>	Students around tables, looking at the projection screen, in small groups

INTERACTION DURING THE ACTIVITY (EMPHASIS)

<i>Actions</i>	Exchange ideas, dialogue, negotiation, debate
<i>Relationships</i>	Collaborative
<i>Roles in the group</i>	Emergent roles
<i>Support by the tutor(s)</i>	Support, intervene, self-regulatory.

Teaching and Learning Procedures

TEACHER'S ROLE

Lecturer, trouble shooter.

TEACHING METHODS

Constructionism combined with instruction-element

EXPECTED STUDENT ACTIVITY

Students during the activity are expected to engage in the following actions: observing, creating, discussing

STUDENT LEARNING PROCESSES

<i>Designed Conflicts and misconceptions</i>	N.A.
<i>Learning processes emphasized:</i>	Emphasis is placed on empowering students to control their robot as a result of the program they create.
<i>Expected relevance of alternative knowledge</i>	N.A.

STUDENT PRODUCTIONS

PRODUCTION	DESCRIPTION
<i>Artifacts - robots</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Assignment: Act like a vehicle ▪ Interaction: speech, gesture, mind control, buttons, app. ▪ Morphology: vehicle like. ▪ Behavior: butler, friend. ▪ Material: parts of the Botball robotic set
<i>Programs - code</i>	Structure of code-commands: function calls Elements: iteration, selection, variables, function definition Conditionals: waiting for sensor-events
<i>Discussions – arguments</i> (Describe the emphasis of the activity plan in one or more types of discussion provided in the next cell)	Discussions and reflections were left to the teachers in the classroom <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Descriptive - explanatory: description of a situation, a construct or an idea for others to understand and /or to implement ▪ Alternative: provision of solutions to problems, provision of alternatives if a dead end is reached ▪ Critical - objection: revision of other’s constructs and ideas, identification of problems, challenge of ideas ▪ Contributory - extending: sharing of resources, provision of ideas towards improving an existing construct or initial idea

Sequence and description of activities

WORKSHOP DAY 1

PRE-PHASE: INTRODUCTION

Duration: 30 min

Orchestration: assembly discussion

Description: The tutors and lecturers introduce themselves as robot experts and explain that in this workshop, the children will learn how to design and program a robot that is capable of competing in the tournament. The tournament basic set up is explained.

PHASE 1: FIRST PROTOTYPE

Duration: 90 min

Orchestration: group work

Description: All groups are encouraged to build a first robot, which can drive using two motors and carry the controller. Students who use the set for the first time are encouraged to build their robot according to a step-by-step guide to make them familiar with the basic parts for this simple robot like motors, wheels and the basic metal parts

PHASE 2: PROGRAMMING PRINCIPLES - SIMPLE MOVEMENTS

Duration: 120 minutes

Orchestration: group work with short lecture parts

Description: The students are briefly introduced to basic programming principles, like structure of a program, statements. Afterwards basic movement functions are discussed by means of simple tasks, like driving a specific path or pattern.

PHASE 3: COMPLEX PROGRAMMING STRUCTURES - USING SENSORS

Duration: 220 minutes

Orchestration: group work with short lecture parts

Description: The students experience the usage of sensors, loops, selections through small examples and simple tasks.

PHASE 4: DISCUSSION AND OUTLOOK FOR THE NEXT DAY

Duration: 30 min

Orchestration: assembly discussion

Description: The tutors discuss the main parts of the workshop day and present an outlook for the next day

WORKSHOP DAY 2

PHASE 5: COMPETITION SETUP DISCUSSION AND SHORT PLANNING PHASE

Duration: 90 min

Orchestration: assembly discussion

Description: The tutors and lecturers explain the competition task for the actual year and discuss points which are unclear for the students. The students are encouraged to think about a strategy for the winning the competition and the needed parts of the robot.

PHASE 6: GATHER EXPERIENCE WITH DIFFERENT ROBOTIC PARTS

Duration: 360 min

Orchestration: group work with short lecture parts

Description: The students experience the usage of different parts of the Botball robotic set and their possible relevance for the competition through small examples and simple tasks.

PHASE 7: WORKSHOP EVALUATION

Duration: 30 min

Orchestration: individual work

Description: The students have the possibility to express their feedback for the workshop through questionnaires and personal discussion

Assessment Procedures

FOCUS	ASSESSMENT METHOD OR TOOL
<i>Are popular gender stereotypes about STEM held?</i>	Draw a scientist
<i>Past experience and existing attitudes to STEM subjects and careers</i>	Pre-questionnaire
<i>Past experience and existing attitudes to STEM subjects and careers</i> <i>Includes questions about the activities to help understand learner's experiences of the workshop as a whole, what participants feel they have learned and what their future intentions are</i>	Post-questionnaire
<i>Understand the experience of participants and their reasons for particular actions</i>	Interview with focus group
	Peer assessment
	Essays- Tests-Student productions (code-robots-textual communication – presentations,)
	Observation notes
	Reflection Sheet

4.6 EUROPEAN CONFERENCE ON EDUCATIONAL ROBOTICS (ECER)

AUTHOR:

Lisa Vittori

Partner: PRIA, Austria

Focus, Set up and Requirements of the activity

CURRICULUM

Select NO if the scenario is not aligned with the curriculum of your country and YES if it is. Please mention the relevant subject matter.

NO YES

CONTENT

Choose categories and give a rating of the level of emphasis on concepts from each of the following domains

Science Technology Business Engineering Arts Mathematics

(0-10) (0-10) (0-10) (0-10) (0-10) (0-10)
7 10 0 10 3 5

OBJECTIVES

<i>Subject related</i>	Construct robots, develop algorithms and programs
<i>Technology use related</i>	Programming of Botball controller
<i>Social and action related</i>	Improve collaborative skills, take roles within group, present own work
<i>Argumentation and fostering of maker culture:</i>	Exchange of ideas, ask and provide help.

TIME

Duration: 1 week

Schedule: 10 hours per day

MATERIALS AND ARTIFACTS

<i>Digital artifact</i>	Programming language(s)
<i>Robotic artifact</i>	Each teams creates their own robot
<i>Student's workbook and manual</i>	N.A.
<i>Teacher's instruction book and manual:</i>	N.A.

Students and space

STUDENTS (TARGET AUDIENCE)

<i>Sex and Age:</i>	Boys & girls, 15-18 years old (also younger allowed but rare)
<i>Prior knowledge:</i>	General programming skills
<i>Nationality and cultural background</i>	Austrian and international teams as well (UK, Germany, Poland, USA, Egypt, Kuwait)
<i>Social status and social environment</i>	
<i>Special needs and abilities</i>	English is the conference language.

SPACE INFO

Organizational and cultural context: a few months before the conference, the game – competition setting is provided by the KISS Institute of Practical Robotics (USA)

Physical characteristics: indoors – in Game tables

Social Orchestration

POPULATION

Students: 150 approx.

Tutors:

GROUPING:

Grouping criteria	No specific criteria, apply, often teams composed of students of one class
Team size	4-6 students (plus mostly a teacher as supervisor)

INTERACTION DURING THE ACTIVITY (EMPHASIS)

Actions	Robotic competitions (Botball tournament, open tournament), presentation of papers by students, robotic showcases, talks by researchers
Relationships	Collaborative (in groups) – competitive (among groups)
Roles in the group	Team leader, programmer, robot developer, documentation, presenter.
Support by the tutor(s)	e.g. Intervene, monitor, facilitate

Teaching and Learning Procedures

TEACHER'S ROLE

Mentor, consultant.

TEACHING METHODS

Constructionist

EXPECTED STUDENT ACTIVITY

Students during the activity are expected to engage in the following actions: analyzing, creating, discussing, writing, observing.

STUDENT LEARNING PROCESSES

<i>Designed Conflicts and misconceptions</i>	A usual misconception of the participants is that winning is the single aim
<i>Learning processes</i>	Acknowledge and value the developed solutions of other teams

<i>emphasized:</i>	despite the fact that they might succeed over the own team
<i>Expected relevance of alternative knowledge</i>	N.A

STUDENT PRODUCTIONS

PRODUCTION	DESCRIPTION
<i>Artifacts - robots</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Assignment: The robot should perform the tasks defined in the competition. ▪ Interaction: speech, gesture, mind control, buttons, app etc. ▪ Morphology: Each team will construct their own robot in order to win the competition. ▪ Behavior: Defined by the competition ▪ Material: Various types of robotic kits are used
<i>Programs - code</i>	Structure of code-commands: function calls Elements: iteration, selection, variables, function definition Conditionals: waiting for sensor-events
<i>Discussions – arguments</i> (Describe the emphasis of the activity plan in one or more types of discussion provided in the next cell)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Descriptive - explanatory: description of a situation, a construct or an idea for others to understand and /or to implement ▪ Alternative: provision of solutions to problems, provision of alternatives if a dead end is reached ▪ Critical - objection: revision of other’s constructs and ideas, identification of problems, challenge of ideas ▪ Contributory - extending: sharing of resources, provision of ideas towards improving an existing construct or initial idea

Sequence and description of activities

PRECONFERENCE

Each student team writes a scientific paper before the conference which they submit. They receive feedback to their paper and can submit an improved version. At the conference, the teams give a presentation of their paper.

Actual researchers give talks so that the students can grasp ongoing research and understand what research actually does and achieves

PREPARING FOR THE COMPETITION

The student teams develop robots with an iRobot (normally used for vacuum cleaning), metal parts as well as Lego parts that can tackle the tasks to be achieved according to the competition on the game table.

The student teams develop programs and algorithms for their robots. They use various programming languages. For the development of their programs students should take into account the given measurements of the game table. Often teams use basic mathematics integrating time constraints in their solutions.

Often the developed robots can be regarded pieces of art. This is especially true regarding specific modules of the developed robots. Besides, some teams indeed add pure non-functional parts to their robot just for fun.

TYPES OF COMPETITIONS

During the whole period of the conference two types of team competitions take place with preliminary rounds at the beginning and the finals at the last day. ECER hosts the European regional tournament of Botball, at which only official Botball teams are allowed to participate. For teams using other controller technology and material, an open competition exists called PRIA Open. Furthermore, an aerial competition exists using drones.

SEEDING (ALL)

Seeding rounds are used for all technologies (Botball, PRIA Open and Aerial). In this part of the competition, the table is used by one student team that has 2 minutes for scoring points according to the game rules.

DOUBLE ELIMINATION (BOTBALL AND OPEN)

Double Eliminations takes place for Botball and PRIA Open teams and is regarded from most teams as the part where the actual competition begins. In this part of the tournament teams compete directly against each other until they are eliminated twice.

ALLIANCE (BOTBALL)

Alliance Matches are matches for teams who have been eliminated twice early in the Botball competition. Two teams are paired up together and they compete for points. It works like the seeding rounds but there is 1 individual team on each side and they try and score points as an alliance.

Assessment Procedures

The content of the competition defines the rules and the goals for the winning teams (see organizational and cultural content). A number of awards exists, that are given either based on results of the competitions or based on a jury voting. Generally, the aim is to spread awards to as many teams as possible. The following awards existed in 2015:

- Best Paper
- Best Programming
- Best Rookie Team
- Best Subsystem
- KISS Award
- Man in Technology
- Outstanding Engineering
- Overall Documentation
- Overall Judges' Choice
- PRIA Judges' Choice
- Spirit of Botball
- Woman in Technology

4.7 MAKING A ROBOT “SMART” (INTRODUCING PROGRAMMING STRUCTURES)

AUTHOR:

Marios Xenos - Researcher

Partner: UoA - ETL

Focus, Set up and Requirements of the activity

CURRICULUM

Select NO if the scenario is not aligned with the curriculum of your country and YES if it is. Please mention the relevant subject matter.

NO YES Subject: Programming

CONTENT

Choose categories and give a rating of the level of emphasis on concepts from each of the following domains

<input type="checkbox"/> Science	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Technology	<input type="checkbox"/> Business	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Engineering	<input type="checkbox"/> Arts	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Mathematics
(0-10)	(0-10)	(0-10)	(0-10)	(0-10)	(0-10)
0	10	0	6	0	5

OBJECTIVES

<i>Subject related</i>	Introducing basic programming structures in the context of robotics in order for students to give a vehicle autonomous behavior.
<i>Technology use related</i>	Programming in LEGO programming environment
<i>Social and action related</i>	Taking and exchanging roles in a group. Communicate with other groups to find solutions
<i>Argumentation and fostering of maker culture:</i>	Identifying an authentic problem, make assumptions, test possible solutions, choose the best solution, communicate with other “makers

TIME

Duration: 6 weeks

Schedule: 1 hour per week

MATERIALS AND ARTIFACTS

<i>Digital artifact</i>	Lego programming environment.
<i>Robotic artifact</i>	A simple vehicle.
<i>Student's workbook and manual</i>	Activity sheet, Lego electronic manual, evaluation sheet.
<i>Teacher's instruction book and manual:</i>	Teacher's notes on each of 4 stages

Students and space**STUDENTS (TARGET AUDIENCE)**

<i>Sex and Age:</i>	Boys & girls, 14-15 years old
<i>Prior knowledge:</i>	Little knowledge of programming concepts
<i>Nationality and cultural background</i>	Greek students
<i>Social status and social environment</i>	Mainstream public school.
<i>Special needs and abilities</i>	Lego programming environment is in English. English is not native language for participants

SPACE INFO

Organizational and cultural context: In Computer Lab, in the context of school schedule.

Physical characteristics: indoors

Social Orchestration**POPULATION**

Students: 59 (6 classes, 3-4 groups in each class)

Tutors: 1

GROUPING:

<i>Grouping criteria</i>	Mixed ability, mixed gender
<i>Setting:</i>	Students in front of computers with one lego NXT kit available for each group.

INTERACTION DURING THE ACTIVITY (EMPHASIS)

<i>Actions</i>	Exchange ideas, dialogue, negotiation, debate
<i>Relationships</i>	Collaborative, competitive
<i>Roles in the group</i>	Emergent roles;
<i>Support by the tutor(s)</i>	Facilitate, support, intervene

Teaching and Learning Procedures**TEACHER'S ROLE**

Facilitator, mentor, co-researcher,

TEACHING METHODS

introducing simple examples, setting initial program status

EXPECTED STUDENT ACTIVITY

Students during the activity are expected to engage in the following actions: **writing, observing, creating**

STUDENT LEARNING PROCESSES

<i>Designed Conflicts and misconceptions</i>	Misconceptions about programming structures conditions, misconceptions about what a robot can “understand”
<i>Learning processes emphasized:</i>	Emphasis on: a) how different programming structures and conditions affect the robot behaviour and b) how a robot acts in real world.
<i>Expected relevance of alternative knowledge</i>	Physics laws can affect the result of robot behaviour

STUDENT PRODUCTIONS

PRODUCTION	DESCRIPTION
<i>Artifacts - robots</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Assignment: Robot will perform programmable movements for educational purposes. ▪ Interaction: Gesture. ▪ Morphology: Machine-like ▪ Behavior: Autonomous vehicle. ▪ Material: Lego Mindstorms NXT parts
<i>Programs - code</i>	
<i>Discussions – arguments</i> (Describe the emphasis of the activity plan in one or more types of discussion provided in the next cell)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Descriptive - explanatory: Discussion and hypothesis testing ▪ Alternative: provision of alternative solutions to the same programming or robot movement problem. ▪ Critical - objection: Identification of problems ▪ Contributory - extending: Extending a successful problem solution to enrich the robot’s behavior.

Sequence and description of activities

PHASE 1: INTRODUCTION AND EXPERIMENTATION

Duration: 1 hour

Orchestration: group work

Description: Children are engaged in discussion about science and robotics and how the creator-programmer can give the desired functionalities and characteristics to a robotic device. Students are introduced to available parts, sensors, motors. They are practicing with assembling a specific robot following printed instructions.

PHASE 2: SEQUENTIAL PROGRAMMING

Duration: 1 hour

Orchestration: group work

Description: Students implement their first program which consists of programming blocks placed in a row. No loops or selection structures are needed. The first program should move the robot on a predefined path (a rectangular path) on the floor. The robotic vehicle is pre-assembled so students have to focus on programming and debugging their own programs. They are facing two real issues: a) How the real distance on the floor is related to distance parameter on the program b) How a robot can turn 90 degrees as it cannot understand “degrees” by default. After a successful first program, they are asked to enhance the program by repeating the movements on the floor and ensuring that the robot returns to the initial position.

PHASE 3: USING LOOPS – GIVING “SENSES” TO A ROBOT

Duration: 2 hours (in 2 sessions)

Orchestration: group work

Description: Students are asked to assemble and connect an ultrasonic sensor on the robot in a way it can detect objects in front of it. The teacher gives them a predefined program with a simple loop. The program includes one “move” block that results in the following behavior: the robot moves until it detects an object at 20 cm away. Firstly, students have to test the program and find out the role of loop and its parameters. Secondly, they have to modify the program in such a way that, after the obstacle detection, the robot will perform a U turn and will move for 4 floor plates. In this phase, students are facing two new issues: a) The robot detects the obstacle in different distances each time it runs the program. It is needed to find the reason for this “malfunction” b) How can they measure or calculate the distance that robot covers and set the proper parameters on the program?

PHASE 4: GETTING FEEDBACK AND ENHANCING THE “SMARTNESS” OF THE ROBOT

Duration: 2 hours (in 2 sessions)

Orchestration: group work

Description: At the beginning of this phase, students are discussing in the classroom the solutions they found to the issues which were raised in previous phases. In this final phase they are asked to make their robots really “smart”; not just avoid an obstacle and stop. Now they have to use their experience to program the robot to avoid any obstacle and continue its way.

Assessment Procedures

FOCUS	ASSESSMENT METHOD OR TOOL
<i>Are popular gender stereotypes about STEM held?</i>	Draw a scientist
<i>Past experience and existing attitudes to STEM subjects and careers</i>	Pre-questionnaire
<i>Past experience and existing attitudes to STEM subjects and</i>	Post-questionnaire

<i>careers</i> <i>Includes questions about the activities to help understand learner's experiences of the workshop as a whole, what participants feel they have learned and what their future intentions are</i>	
<i>Understand the experience of participants and their reasons for particular actions</i>	Interview with focus group
	Peer assessment
	Essays- Tests-Student productions (code-robots-textual communication – presentations,)
	Observation notes
	Reflection Sheet

4.8 ROBOTIC “SAFE SWING” AND A SEESAW

AUTHOR:

Christos Bitas (Teacher)⁵

Partner: UoA - ETL

Focus, Set up and Requirements of the activity

CURRICULUM

Select NO if the scenario is not aligned with the curriculum of your country and YES if it is. Please mention the relevant subject matter.

NO YES

CONTENT

Choose categories and give a rating of the level of emphasis on concepts from each of the following domains

Science (0-10)
 Technology (0-10)
 Business (0-10)
 Engineering (0-10)
 Arts (0-10)
 Mathematics (0-10)

⁵ The idea of the swing and seesaw is not original as it is also addressed and described for LEGO WEDO in the [TUFTS curriculum](#) unit for programming with robotics. However for ER4STEM the implementation and description of the activity has followed the template created for the project.

0 4 0 9 3 8

OBJECTIVES

<i>Subject related</i>	Study the angle and position of all materials (servo motors, circuits, sensors), as well as the construction of the swing in order for the swing to be autonomous and move (swinging) correctly.
<i>Technology use related</i>	Programming of LEGO WEDO 2
<i>Social and action related</i>	Improve collaborative skills, take roles within groups
<i>Argumentation and fostering of maker culture:</i>	Practice making conjectures about how the robot will react to external stimuli based on the program given

TIME**Duration:** 2 weeks**Schedule:** 6 hours per week**MATERIALS AND ARTIFACTS**

<i>Digital artifact</i>	Programming language
<i>Robotic artifact</i>	“Safe swing” and “seesaw”
<i>Student’s workbook and manual</i>	Manual with instructions for the electronic part (related photos) and programming (instructions, directions) part too
<i>Teacher’s instruction book and manual:</i>	Teacher’s notes with photos and instructions.

Students and space**STUDENTS (TARGET AUDIENCE)**

<i>Sex and Age:</i>	Boys & girls, 12 years old
<i>Prior knowledge:</i>	Little if any knowledge of LEGO WEDO 2 but 5 pupils out of 25 are experts on the electronic part of the construction.
<i>Nationality and cultural background</i>	23 pupils are from Greece, 1 from Armenia and 1 from Palestine
<i>Social status and social environment</i>	Mainstream public school
<i>Special needs and abilities</i>	None

SPACE INFO**Organizational and cultural context:** In school at the technology Lab**Physical characteristics:** indoors**Social Orchestration****POPULATION**

Students: 25**Tutors:** 2**GROUPING:**

Grouping criteria	Mixed ability, mixed gender.
Setting:	Students in a normal classroom, around light mobile tables in small groups of 3.

INTERACTION DURING THE ACTIVITY (EMPHASIS)

Actions	Exchange ideas, dialogue, negotiation
Relationships	Collaborative
Roles in the group	Emergent roles
Support by the tutor(s)	Support, intervene

Teaching and Learning Procedures**TEACHER'S ROLE**

Mentor, co-researcher, lecturer.

TEACHING METHODS

Demonstrate,

EXPECTED STUDENT ACTIVITY

Students during the activity are expected to engage in the following actions: observing, constructing, discussing.

STUDENT LEARNING PROCESSES

<i>Designed Conflicts and misconceptions</i>	N.A.
<i>Learning processes emphasized:</i>	Emphasis on studying robot behavior as a result of the usage of motion sensor and the program the students created.
<i>Expected relevance of alternative knowledge</i>	Emphasis on mathematical thinking (i.e. the angle of the swing and the motor power that the swing moves correctly, the same for the seesaw)

STUDENT PRODUCTIONS

PRODUCTION	DESCRIPTION
<i>Artifacts - robots</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Assignment: Entertainment, co-operation ▪ Interaction: Gesture ▪ Morphology: Machine-like, cartoon-like ▪ Behavior: Toy ▪ Material: Electronics, software, mechanics
<i>Programs - code</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Structure of code-commands: LEGO WEDO 2. ▪ Elements (e.g. iteration, selection, variables): Iteration: for loop, while loop, selection : wait statements, recursion.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Conditionals (e.g. event handling): Event handling of motion sensor.
<p><i>Discussions – arguments</i> (Describe the emphasis of the activity plan in one or more types of discussion provided in the next cell)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Descriptive - explanatory: description of a situation, a construct or an idea for others to understand and /or to implement Alternative: provision of solutions to problems, provision of alternatives if a dead end is reached Critical - objection: revision of other’s constructs and ideas, identification of problems, challenge of ideas Contributory - extending: sharing of resources, provision of ideas towards improving an existing construct or initial idea

Sequence and description of activities

PRE-PHASE: INTRODUCTION

Duration: 20 min

Orchestration: assembly discussion

Description: The teachers what will happen in this workshop and the children will learn how to design robots while the teacher will learn from their ideas how to build better robots in the future. We expect that children broaden their view of technology as “something that we build to make our lives easier” and as “true robots act autonomously”. From then on, children start thinking critically about it.

PHASE 1: GROUP FORMULATION – “WHAT ARE WE GOING TO CONSTRUCT?”

Duration: 3 hours

Orchestration: group work

Description: Students are introduced to the idea that “Real robots are highly complex and designed by a team of experts from different disciplines (designers, human-robot-interaction experts, programmers, engineers, etc.)”. The students are guided step by step through five important topics, eventually they design specific robots (“safe swing” and a seesaw).

STEP 1 – ROBOT TASK (“ASSIGNMENT”).

The children are asked to imagine a robot for themselves that does anything they want. Every idea is valuable in this phase and not discarded as useless or undoable.

STEP 2 – ROBOT INTERACTION.

Known and not yet invented applications are both encouraged equally. Children learn that some of their ideas need scientists who invent new things that are then built into the robots by engineers. How would you tell your robot what to do? Would you talk to it in a secret language or with signs? Would the robot understand your thoughts? Or would you use an app to control it?

STEP 3 – ROBOT MORPHOLOGY (“LOOKS AND MATERIALS”).

We divide the third step, robot morphology, into “looks” and “materials”. First, we introduce two different categories of robot morphology “Robots can look like machines, like cartoon characters”. Second, we talk about different materials robots can be made of, and describe some properties: They can feel smooth, hard, furry, etc. How would your robot feel like?

STEP 4 – ROBOT BEHAVIOR.

In the fourth step, the abstract concept of autonomous behavior needs to be explained in a manner that children understand. We use two paths: In order to make the abstract word “behavior” more concrete, we describe roles (or personas) with which children identify. Would you like your robot to be rather like a butler, a teacher, a protector, a pet or a friend? We also explain that robots have rules to obey.

STEP 5 – ROBOT PARTS.

This last step brings the previous steps together. The researchers show pictures of mechanic and electronic parts: some are used in every robot; others depend on what the robot does, how it looks like or how it should behave. In the beginning of the design process (ideation), the focus is on the holistic view of a product developer who needs to know what parts are needed but is not concerned with the details.

PHASE 2: PROGRAMMING

Duration: 2 hours

Orchestration: group work

Description: The groups of children will deal with the programming part of the robot.

PHASE 3: EVALUATION

Duration: 40 minutes

Orchestration: group work

Description: We collect all the data (questionnaires, interviews, etc)

Assessment Procedures

FOCUS	ASSESSMENT METHOD OR TOOL
<i>Are popular gender stereotypes about STEM held?</i>	Draw a scientist
<i>Past experience and existing attitudes to STEM subjects and careers</i>	Pre-questionnaire
<i>Past experience and existing attitudes to STEM subjects and careers</i> <i>Includes questions about the activities to help understand learner’s experiences of the</i>	Post-questionnaire

<i>workshop as a whole, what participants feel they have learned and what their future intentions are</i>	
<i>Understand the experience of participants and their reasons for particular actions</i>	Interview with focus group
	Peer assessment
	Essays- Tests-Student productions (code-robots-textual communication – presentations,)
	Observation notes
	Reflection Sheet

4.9 CONSTRUCTING & CONTROLLING A ROBOT-PAINTER

AUTHOR:

Agni Pahouli

Partner: UoA- ETL

Focus, Set up and Requirements of the activity

CURRICULUM

Select NO if the scenario is not aligned with the curriculum of your country and YES if it is. Please mention the relevant subject matter.

NO YES Subject: Programming

CONTENT

Choose categories and give a rating of the level of emphasis on concepts from each of the following domains

<input type="checkbox"/> Science	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Technology	<input type="checkbox"/> Business	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Engineering	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Arts	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Mathematics
(0-10)	(0-10)	(0-10)	(0-10)	(0-10)	(0-10)
0	10	0	10	5	10

OBJECTIVES

<i>Subject related</i>	Observe/Study the movement of the robot/vehicle and program it in order to achieve specific rotation angle and make it move autonomously following desired routes
<i>Technology use related</i>	Programming in the graphical programming environment NXT-G

<i>Social and action related</i>	Improve collaborative skills, exchange ideas, take roles within groups
<i>Argumentation and fostering of maker culture:</i>	Identifying an authentic problem, make assumptions, test possible solutions, choose the best solution

TIME

Duration: 2 weeks

Schedule: 3 hours per week

MATERIALS AND ARTIFACTS

<i>Digital artifact</i>	Lego NXT-G programming environment
<i>Robotic artifact</i>	A vehicle (the default construction in Lego Mindstorms manual)
<i>Student's workbook and manual</i>	Manual with step-by-step instructions for the electronic part, worksheets with activities for the programming part, evaluation sheets.
<i>Teacher's instruction book and manual:</i>	Teacher's notes

Students and space

STUDENTS (TARGET AUDIENCE)

<i>Sex and Age:</i>	Boys & girls, 12-13 years old
<i>Prior knowledge:</i>	No previous knowledge of Lego technology is required. Good knowledge of programming concepts (the students piloting this activity plan have been using Scratch)
<i>Nationality and cultural background</i>	12 students from Greece, Athens
<i>Social status and social environment</i>	Experimental high school.
<i>Special needs and abilities</i>	N.A.

SPACE INFO

Organizational and cultural context: In school, during computer science lesson.

Physical characteristics: indoors

Social Orchestration

POPULATION

Students: 12

Tutors: 1

GROUPING:

Grouping criteria	Mixed ability, mixed gender.
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<i>Setting:</i>	Students in robotics classroom, one Lego NXT kit and laptop available for each group, each group is seated in their own workbench.
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INTERACTION DURING THE ACTIVITY (EMPHASIS)

<i>Actions</i>	Exchange ideas, dialogue, negotiation, debate
<i>Relationships</i>	Collaborative
<i>Roles in the group</i>	Emergent roles
<i>Support by the tutor(s)</i>	Intervene, monitor, facilitate

Teaching and Learning Procedures

TEACHER'S ROLE

Facilitator, consultant.

TEACHING METHODS

The teacher support student active exploration and investigation through properly designed activity sheets.

EXPECTED STUDENT ACTIVITY

Students during the activity are expected to engage in the following actions: writing, observing, creating

STUDENT LEARNING PROCESSES

<i>Designed Conflicts and misconceptions</i>	Students often think that when they assign to a motor a 90 degrees movement, the whole robot will turn 90 degrees. It takes time for the students to realize that the degrees refer to the wheel's rotation and not the robot's as a whole
<i>Learning processes emphasized:</i>	Emphasis on studying robot behavior as a result of the program the students created (use behavior as feedback on programming)
<i>Expected relevance of alternative knowledge</i>	Physics laws can affect the result of robot behavior, mathematic formula for calculating the wheel's perimeter ($2*\pi*R$).

STUDENT PRODUCTIONS

PRODUCTION	DESCRIPTION
<i>Artifacts - robots</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Assignment: robot-painter, drawing shapes ▪ Interaction: the robot is autonomous, no sensors are being used ▪ Morphology: machine-like (vehicle). ▪ Behavior: autonomous vehicle. ▪ Material: Lego Mindostorm NXT parts
<i>Programs - code</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Structure of code-commands: commands in sequence, commands in repeat structure ▪ Elements: commands for motor movement and repeat programming structure
<i>Discussions – arguments</i> (Describe the emphasis of the activity plan in one or	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Descriptive - explanatory: description of a situation, a construct or an idea for others to understand and /or to implement

more types of discussion provided in the next cell)	<ul style="list-style-type: none">▪ Alternative: provision of solutions to problems, provision of alternatives if a dead end is reached▪ Critical - objection: N.A.▪ Contributory - extending: sharing of resources, provision of ideas towards improving an existing construct or initial idea
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Sequence and description of activities

PRE-PHASE: INTRODUCTION

Duration: 10 min

Orchestration: discussion

Description: In order to break the ice and generate interest in the topic of the workshop, students are engaged in discussion about their previous involvement to robotics (if they have any), robotic behaviors and how the programmer can give the desired functionalities and characteristics to a robotic device. In detail, students are prompted to answer questions such as: “What is a robot?”; “Why do humans use robots?”; “Can they be helpful?”. Brainstormed-words describing characteristics of a robot are written on the whiteboard. Afterwards, the teacher presents the overall aim, the objectives of the workshop, the training methodology and the expected training results. Finally, the teacher demonstrates shortly the NXT brick, motors, connection ports and materials included in the Lego Mindstorms Education NXT kit. Before they start acting, groups are asked to choose a name for their team.

PHASE 1: A FIRST APPROACH TO CONSTRUCTION

Duration: 50 min

Orchestration: group work

Description: Students get involved in constructing a robot car with two motors. To this end, they use instructions included in the official guide. In order to save time and proceed to the programming part, students don't start the robot construction from scratch; a small part of the robot is already assembled.

PHASE 2: A FIRST APPROACH TO PROGRAMMING: MOVING AROUND

Duration: 60 min

Orchestration: group work

Description: This phase is focused on the Lego NXT programming environment and the development of programs that guide robots with varying configurations, i.e. motors' activation using basic programming blocks within the NXT software. Students undertake specific introductory activities to the programming environment of Lego Mindstorms Education NXT. An appropriate worksheet is given to all groups with specific guidelines (worksheet 1).

STEP 1 – LET'S EXPERIMENT WITH “MOVE” BLOCK

The initial activity is to investigate the “move” block and describe the results of this command.

STEP 2 – ROBOT’S FIRST MOVEMENTS

Students investigate the relation between power of motor and speed of the car-robot they have already constructed. Students are prompted to conduct additional experimentations are conducted regarding the parameters of “duration” and “direction”, by testing the results of various different values in these two parameters of the “move” block.

STEP 3 – HELP THE ROBOT TURN

In the last activity of worksheet 1, students are asked to investigate left and right turns with both “move” and “motor” blocks. Finally, they develop their own programs for a 180-degree pivot turn and a 180-degree spin turn.

PHASE 3: TRANSFORM YOUR ROBOT INTO A PAINTER

Duration: 120 minutes

Orchestration: group work

Description: During the activities of worksheet 2, all groups will create programs with blocks such as “move”, “motor”, “loop”. The activities gradually introduce students to programming concepts of varying difficulty and complexity, as they have to recall mathematical knowledge. An appropriate worksheet is given to all groups with specific guidelines (worksheet 2).

STEP 1 – STUDY CLOSELY THE ROBOT’S MOVEMENTS

Empirically, students have to determine/calculate the distance the robot will cover when the duration of movement equals 1 wheel rotation. Mathematical knowledge must be applied, taking into consideration the wheel’s perimeter or radius (formula: $2*\pi*R$). All groups are supplied with a ruler, a protractor and a scoop. After that, students have to run the program and compare the results of the experimental trial to the empirical conclusion.

STEP 2 – TESTING TURNS

Starting from the same spot, the robot must be programmed to perform a spin rotation. The value of wheel’s rotations varies every time and students have to measure the angle the robot has turned each time. After many measurements, they will be able to calculate the rotation angle of the robot for different values of wheel’s rotation.

STEP 3 – MOVE ON A SQUARE PATH

Groups are asked to program their robot properly in order to move on a square path. Based on their previous empirical and experimental outcomes, they will define the number of rotations the wheels must perform in order to make the robot rotate 90-degrees. In this activity, the repeat block “loop” is used for the first time.

STEP 4 – DRAW A SQUARE

A pencil must be provided to the robot in order to leave its trace on a paper sheet while moving. Students must find out which is the most appropriate point to embed the pencil on the robot.

STEP 5 – DRAW A COLORFUL PAINTING!

Students are asked to provide their robot with colorful pencils and program it in order to make an abstract painting.

PHASE 4: EVALUATION

Duration: 20 minutes

Orchestration: group work

Description: While groups are trying to solve the requested problems, test their code and fill in their activity sheets, they discuss the difficulties, the different solutions, the limitations that may have come up with in every step. After each workshop, students also fill in an evaluation questionnaire and teacher gets short informal open interviews from students that want to share their experience.

Assessment Procedures

FOCUS	ASSESSMENT METHOD OR TOOL
<i>Are popular gender stereotypes about STEM held?</i>	Draw a scientist
<i>Past experience and existing attitudes to STEM subjects and careers</i>	Pre-questionnaire
<i>Past experience and existing attitudes to STEM subjects and careers</i> <i>Includes questions about the activities to help understand learner's experiences of the workshop as a whole, what participants feel they have learned and what their future intentions are</i>	Post-questionnaire
<i>Understand the experience of participants and their reasons for particular actions</i>	Interview with focus group
	Peer assessment
	Essays- Tests-Student productions (code-robots-textual communication – presentations,)
	Observation notes
	Reflection Sheet

4.10 SOLVING THE MAZE PROBLEM WITH LEGO EV3

AUTHOR:

Vasilios Spachos

Partner: UoA- ETL

Focus, Set up and Requirements of the activity

CURRICULUM

Select NO if the scenario is not aligned with the curriculum of your country and YES if it is. Please mention the relevant subject matter.

NO YES

CONTENT

Choose categories and give a rating of the level of emphasis on concepts from each of the following domains

Science Technology Business Engineering Arts Mathematics

(0-10) (0-10) (0-10) (0-10) (0-10) (0-10)

4 10 0 10 0 10

OBJECTIVES

<i>Subject related</i>	Constructing an EV3 robot to solve the maze problem
<i>Technology use related</i>	Programming in Lego EV3 environment
<i>Social and action related</i>	Improve collaborative skills, take roles within groups, improve active learning
<i>Argumentation and fostering of maker culture:</i>	Practice making conjectures about how the robot will react to external stimuli based on the program given.

TIME

Duration: 3 weeks**Schedule:** 2 hours per week

MATERIALS AND ARTIFACTS

<i>Digital artifact</i>	Lego EV3 programming environment
<i>Robotic artifact</i>	A simple robotic construction
<i>Student's workbook and manual</i>	Activity sheet, Evaluation sheet
<i>Teacher's instruction book and manual:</i>	Lesson Plan and teacher's notes

Students and space

STUDENTS (TARGET AUDIENCE)

<i>Sex and Age:</i>	Boys & girls, 16 years old
<i>Prior knowledge:</i>	basic knowledge of Lego EV3 Programming
<i>Nationality and cultural background</i>	24 Greek students
<i>Social status and social environment</i>	Mainstream public school
<i>Special needs and abilities</i>	Lego Programming Environment is in English and English is not the native language of participants

SPACE INFO

Organizational and cultural context: Extracurricular activity in school at the Educational Robotics Laboratory.

Physical characteristics: indoors

Social Orchestration**POPULATION**

Students: 25

Tutors: 1

GROUPING:

<i>Grouping criteria</i>	Mixed ability, mixed gender
<i>Setting:</i>	Students in a normal classroom, around light mobile tables with PC, looking at the interactive whiteboard, in 6 groups of 4 students each.

INTERACTION DURING THE ACTIVITY (EMPHASIS)

<i>Actions</i>	Exchange ideas, dialogue, negotiation, debate
<i>Relationships</i>	Collaborative
<i>Roles in the group</i>	Emergent roles
<i>Support by the tutor(s)</i>	Intervene, monitor, facilitate

Teaching and Learning Procedures**TEACHER'S ROLE**

Mentor, consultant, co- researcher, lecturer.

TEACHING METHODS

demonstrate, engage by example, guide (e.g. setting initial program status).

EXPECTED STUDENT ACTIVITY

Students during the activity are expected to engage in the following actions: writing, observing, creating, collaborating.

STUDENT LEARNING PROCESSES

<i>Designed Conflicts and misconceptions</i>	The way that the maze problem can be solved and the interaction between Programming and Mathematics
<i>Learning processes emphasized:</i>	Emphasis on studying robot behavior as a result of the program the students gave (i.e. use behavior as feedback on programming) and emphasis on computational thinking
<i>Expected relevance of alternative knowledge</i>	Physic laws can affect the result of robot behavior.

STUDENT PRODUCTIONS

PRODUCTION	DESCRIPTION
<i>Artifacts - robots</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Assignment: Robot will move in the maze and will have to get out of it ▪ Interaction: through programming the robot. ▪ Morphology: Machine-like ▪ Behavior: autonomous vehicle ▪ Material: Lego EV3 parts and 2 Ultrasonic sensors
<i>Programs - code</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Structure of code-commands: Nested structures ▪ Elements: Nested structures, Loops, Variables ▪ Conditionals: Conditions are embedded into structures
<i>Discussions – arguments</i> (Describe the emphasis of the activity plan in one or more types of discussion provided in the next cell)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Descriptive - explanatory: description of possible solutions ▪ Alternative: provision of alternative solutions to the same problem. ▪ Critical - objection: N.A. ▪ Contributory - extending: Constructing a successful program in order to for the robot to solve the maze problem

Sequence and description of activities

PRE-PHASE: INTRODUCTION AND PRESENTATION OF THE PROBLEM

Duration: 20 min

Orchestration: assembly discussion

Description: The teacher introduces the challenge, presents the 3 rules of Robotics and discusses with the students about which behaviors can result in successful navigation through the maze. We expect that the students will start thinking critically about their construction and the elements needed. Group formulation will take place.

PHASE 1: CONSTRUCTION PHASE AND EXPERIMENTATION

Duration: 2 1/2 hours

Orchestration: group work

Description:

STEP 1 – ROBOT TASK (“ASSIGNMENT”):

The groups start constructing their robot vehicles, taking into account all the parameters and parts that they have to include. They have to add the sensors, like the 2 Ultrasonic

STEP 2 – ROBOT MORPHOLOGY (“LOOKS AND MATERIALS”):

We show to students some robot constructions in order to give them ideas about the "morphology" of their robot .

STEP 3 – ROBOT PARTS:

Step 3 is a starting point to go into more detail by using simple technology (e.g. maker electronics) to work out technically feasible solutions.

STEP 4 – EXPERIMENTATION:

The groups experiment with their construction and communicate with other groups for exchanging ideas.

At the end of Phase1, the students complete the respective activity sheet.

PHASE 2: PROGRAMMING THE ROBOT

Duration: 2 1/2 hours

Orchestration: group work

Description: The groups are assigned to program their robots and their behavior. They use the Programming environment of Lego EV3, using sequential programming, loops, selection. At the same time, they test their robot and its behavior , trying to solve possible problems they face.

At the end of Phase2, the students complete the respective activity sheet.

PHASE 3: PERFORMANCE

Duration: 30 minutes

Orchestration: group work

Description: Each group demonstrates their robot and their solution for the maze problem. The demonstration happens on the appropriate desk in the Educational Robotics Laboratory. Each try is filmed.

At the end of Phase3, the students complete the activity sheet.

PHASE 4: EVALUATION

Duration: 10 minutes

Orchestration: group work

Description: The students complete a questionnaire and the teacher collects all the activity sheets and the questionnaires. The teacher gets short informal interviews from students who want to share their experience.

Assessment Procedures

FOCUS	ASSESSMENT METHOD OR TOOL
<i>Are popular gender stereotypes about STEM held?</i>	Draw a scientist
<i>Past experience and existing attitudes to STEM subjects and careers</i>	Pre-questionnaire
<i>Past experience and existing attitudes to STEM subjects and careers</i> <i>Includes questions about the activities to help understand learner's experiences of the workshop as a whole, what participants feel they have learned and what their future intentions are</i>	Post-questionnaire
<i>Understand the experience of participants and their reasons for particular actions</i>	Interview with focus group
	Peer assessment
	Essays- Tests-Student productions (code-robots-textual communication – presentations)
	Observation notes
	Reflection Sheet

4.11 MY FIRST ROBOT

AUTHOR:

Mavrantzas Nikolaos

Partner: UoA-ETL

Focus, Set up and Requirements of the activity

CURRICULUM

Select NO if the scenario is not aligned with the curriculum of your country and YES if it is. Please mention the relevant subject matter.

NO YES Subject: Robotics

CONTENT

Choose categories and give a rating of the level of emphasis on concepts from each of the following domains

<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Science	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Technology	<input type="checkbox"/> Business	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Engineering	<input type="checkbox"/> Arts	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Mathematics
(0-10)	(0-10)	(0-10)	(0-10)	(0-10)	(0-10)
2	5	0	10	0	1

OBJECTIVES

<i>Subject related</i>	Making a LEGO robot and use small programs to make it move. Understand how motors and distance sensor works.
<i>Technology use related</i>	Program with Lego WeDo 2.0
<i>Social and action related</i>	Learn how to collaborate, take roles within groups and solve practical problems as a team.
<i>Argumentation and fostering of maker culture:</i>	Programming a robot is something that a student can do and do it well. Trial and error methodology

TIME

Duration: 3 weeks

Schedule: 2 hours per week

MATERIALS AND ARTIFACTS

<i>Digital artifact</i>	LEGO programming environment (LEGO WeDo 2.0 software, free edition)
<i>Robotic artifact</i>	LEGO WeDo robo-vehicle with one motor and one proximity (distance) sensor.
<i>Student's workbook and manual</i>	Lego instructions for building a robot with 2 wheels. Step by step instructions - Examples with small programs.
<i>Teacher's instruction book and manual:</i>	-

Students and space

STUDENTS (TARGET AUDIENCE)

<i>Sex and Age:</i>	Boys & girls, 10-12 years old
<i>Prior knowledge:</i>	Basic computer skills, basic programming
<i>Nationality and cultural background</i>	30 pupils are from Greece and 4 are from Albania
<i>Social status and social environment</i>	Mainstream primary school – small town in Greek province
<i>Special needs and abilities</i>	N.A.

SPACE INFO

Organizational and cultural context: In School Computer Lab

Physical characteristics: indoors

Social Orchestration

POPULATION

Students: 34 (two classes, 17 pupils each)

Tutors: 1

GROUPING:

Grouping criteria	Mixed ability, mixed gender
Setting:	3 or 4 students per group, looking at the wall projector, in 5 small groups. Each group has a LEGO WeDo 2.0 kit and a laptop.

INTERACTION DURING THE ACTIVITY (EMPHASIS)

Actions	Exchange ideas, dialogue, negotiation, debate
Relationships	Collaborative and some times competitive
Roles in the group	Emergent roles – loose. If needed a student take the role of the team leader
Support by the tutor(s)	Intervene, monitor, facilitate – Scaffolding methodology

Teaching and Learning Procedures

TEACHER'S ROLE

Mentor, facilitator, animating spirit, encourage problem solving and encourage group working.

TEACHING METHODS

Demonstrate, engage by example, scaffolding methodology

EXPECTED STUDENT ACTIVITY

Students during the activity are expected to engage in the following actions: learning by doing, use trial and error to solve smaller problems, combine ideas and solutions towards resolving the initial big problem

STUDENT LEARNING PROCESSES

<i>Designed Conflicts and misconceptions</i>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. At the beginning of the robotics class when students see the target robotic construction and its behavior, they (the students) think that it is impossible for them to construct something similar. The main point of working with robotics is to show the students how to make possible the impossible (collaboration, hard and methodic work) 2. Robot's moving towards a specific destination is only dependent on the starting point and the speed or on the starting point and the duration of movement.
<i>Learning processes emphasized:</i>	Robots can do a lot of things, from building a car to explore the surface of Mars. In any case it is important to give them very specific

	instructions for what to do. Most of the time we must solve small problems and connect the proper solutions to achieve our target.
<i>Expected relevance of alternative knowledge</i>	Physics and especially the result of speed and moving time to the distance traveled.

STUDENT PRODUCTIONS

PRODUCTION	DESCRIPTION
<i>Artifacts - robots</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Assignment: help scientists to transfer equipment to not friendly environments. 1st task: the robot must transfer equipment to specific destinations and return back. 2nd task: the robot, that is carrying heavy equipment, must follow our astronaut when he is moving and stop when he stops. ▪ Interaction: with proximity sensor, bluetooth ▪ Morphology: Machine - like ▪ Behavior: Transportation machine and following assistant ▪ Material: LEGO, WeDo 2.0 kit, hard paper, PC
<i>Programs - code</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Structure of code-commands: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ 1st task: Linear execution of setting motor power, setting a timer, stop, and change motors rotation. Do all the above multiple times to solve the final problem. ○ 2nd task: Iteration of a) reading measurements of proximity sensor, b) assigning values to the power of the motor c) setting parameters for color ▪ Elements: Iteration, assigning values, motor power, led color, timers ▪ Conditionals (e.g. event handling): In logo environment there aren't conditional statements if..then...else but we have event handlers e.g. if there is something in front of you wait.
<i>Discussions – arguments</i> (Describe the emphasis of the activity plan in one or more types of discussion provided in the next cell)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Descriptive - explanatory: Situation: we must transfer heavy scientific equipment to the surface of an unfriendly planet. So, we must make a robot that can move forth and back in order to deliver equipment to space stations on the planet's surface. Then we must program the robot to follow the astronaut as he is moving and build an extra trailer for carrying more equipment. ▪ Alternative: provision of solutions to problems by breaking down the big problem to smaller ones. Control the distance traveled by choosing different a set of parameters for speed and duration of movement. ▪ Critical - objection: N.A. ▪ Contributory - extending: sharing of resources, provision of ideas towards improving an existing construct or initial idea

Sequence and description of activities

PRE-PHASE : INTRODUCTION

Duration: 1 hour

Orchestration: Assembly discussion

Materials and processes: Lego programming environment and Lego hub connected via bluetooth with the computer (Demonstration of the connection to the students)

Description: The teacher presents the task to the students and says that each team must build a robot with Lego. It must move to the surface of an unfriendly planet. The students must be familiar with Lego wedo 2.0 kit and must use the Lego programming environment in order to follow the instructions about how to build the robot and how to connect it to the pc via bluetooth.

PHASE 1: “IDEATION”- GROUP FORMULATION AND BRAINSTORMING FOR THE 1ST ACTIVITY

Duration: 2 hours

Orchestration: group work

Description: Children are introduced to the idea that “Real robots are highly complex and designed by a team of experts from different disciplines (designers, human-robot-interaction experts, programmers, engineers, etc.)”.

“The robots are so clever as is their program that controls them”

STEP 1 – ROBOT MORPHOLOGY.

Let’s learn our robot main parts: one hub with 2 ports, color led, motor, proximity sensor, wheels, gears and belt

STEP 2 – CONNECT IT AND PROGRAM IT.

Learn how to set ON pc bluetooth, how to add a bluetooth device (LEGO hub) and how to activate a LEGO hub (that is already connected to pc) to LEGO programming environment. Explain how to use the graphical programming environment and how to control a motor.

STEP 3 – “JUST MOVE IT”.

Program the robot to move forward for 3 sec and then return back. Explain timers, motor power, motor rotation, stop.

STEP 4 – TIME TO TRANSFER SOME EQUIPMENT TO PLANET STATIONS

A hard paper strip is given to each team (see picture below). The strip has 2 linear paths. The robot starts always from Αρχή=start. The robot must stop exactly to the planet stations (black 1, red 1, red 2 and red 3) to transfer some equipment.

1st path: from “Αρχή” to “black 1” and back.

2nd path: from “Αρχή” to “red 1”, to “red2”, then to “red 3” and back to “Αρχή”.

1st mission: Program the robot move to 1st path. The robot must stop for 2sec to station 1 in order to deliver the equipment and the return back to start.

2nd mission: Program the robot move to 2nd path. The robot must stop for 2" to each station (1, 2 and 3) in order to deliver the equipment and the return back to start.

PHASE 2: "FOLLOW THE LEADER" - USING PROXIMITY SENSOR

Duration: 2 hours

Orchestration: group work

Description: The teams during this phase should work into evolving their robot to react on its own initiative using proximity sensor. The scenario is that an astronaut must walk to the surface of the planet in order to repair some machines near the main station. The astronaut can't carry equipment and his vehicle is damaged. So the task for the teams is to reconstruct their robots so that they are able to follow the astronaut in order to carry his tools-equipment.

STEP 1 – LETS LOOP

Give some examples how to program our robot to do repetitive tasks (loops or iteration). We are using the repeat graphical command to change the led color of hub.

STEP2 – LETS LOOP II

We connect our proximity sensor and we are using loop command to change continuously the color of the led in accordance to the distance of our hand from the proximity sensor

STEP 3 – LET'S MAKE SOME FOLLOWERS

Now we know everything that is needed to make our robot to follow our paper astronaut to his mission.

EXTRA MISSIONS (IF THERE IS TIME)

Extra mission I: Use LEGO to make a unique trailer for the robot in order to carry more equipment.

Extra mission II: Try to reform your robot in order to follow the one that is in front of it. The target is to make a convoy of robots. When the first stops to an obstacle the followers are stopping also.

PHASE 3: EVALUATION

Duration: 1 hour

Orchestration: group and individual work

Description: Final discussion in the class. Each team should complete the team reflection sheet and each student the post questionnaire. The focus group – team will give an interview.

Assessment Procedures

FOCUS	ASSESSMENT METHOD OR TOOL
<i>Are popular gender stereotypes about STEM held?</i>	Draw a scientist
<i>Past experience and existing attitudes to STEM subjects and careers</i>	Pre-questionnaire
<i>Past experience and existing attitudes to STEM subjects and careers</i> <i>Includes questions about the activities to help understand learner's experiences of the workshop as a whole, what participants feel they have learned and what their future intentions are</i>	Post-questionnaire
<i>Understand the experience of participants and their reasons for particular actions</i>	Interview with focus group
	Peer assessment
	Essays- Tests-Student productions (code-robots-textual communication – presentations)
	Observation notes
	Reflection Sheet

4.12 ROBOTS AND WALKING MECHANISMS

AUTHOR:

Giannis Baras, Kitsakis Konstantinos

Partner: UoA, ETL

Focus, Set up and Requirements of the activity

CURRICULUM

Select NO if the scenario is not aligned with the curriculum of your country and YES if it is. Please mention the relevant subject matter.

NO YES Subject:

CONTENT

Choose categories and give a rating of the level of emphasis on concepts from each of the following domains

Science Technology Business Engineering Arts Mathematics
 (0-10) (0-10) (0-10) (0-10) (0-10) (0-10)
 5 9 0 10 3 3

OBJECTIVES

<i>Subject related</i>	Study and construction of walking mechanisms for robot, based on Theo Jansen mechanism and Klann linkage.
<i>Technology use related</i>	Programming, engineering
<i>Social and action related</i>	Improve collaborative skills, take roles within groups, brainstorming, solving problems.
<i>Argumentation and fostering of maker culture:</i>	Discovering and understanding, constructing and improving, finding new ways to solve the investigated problems.

TIME

Duration: 2 weeks

Schedule: 3 hours per week

MATERIALS AND ARTIFACTS

<i>Digital artifact</i>	Programming language (LEGO Mindstorm)
<i>Robotic artifact</i>	Walking machines
<i>Student's workbook and manual</i>	Manual with instructions for the basic construction, electronic and programming parts
<i>Teacher's instruction book and manual:</i>	4 demonstration videos and 2 video presentations

Students and space

STUDENTS (TARGET AUDIENCE)

<i>Sex and Age:</i>	Boys & girls (one), 12-15 years old
<i>Prior knowledge:</i>	Average experience and knowledge on robotics using LEGO robotic kits.
<i>Nationality and cultural background</i>	Greek students

<i>Social status and social environment</i>	Underprivileged area
<i>Special needs and abilities</i>	N.A.

SPACE INFO

Organizational and cultural context: in school at the technology laborat

Physical characteristics: indoors

Social Orchestration

POPULATION

Students: 15

Tutors: 2

GROUPING:

Grouping criteria	Mixed ability, mixed gender
<i>Setting:</i>	Students in a normal classroom, around light mobile tables, looking at the blackboard, in small groups of 3

INTERACTION DURING THE ACTIVITY (EMPHASIS)

Actions	Exchange ideas, dialogue, negotiation, debate
<i>Relationships</i>	Collaborative
<i>Roles in the group</i>	Emergent roles
<i>Support by the tutor(s)</i>	Intervene, monitor, facilitate

Teaching and Learning Procedures

TEACHER'S ROLE

Mentor, co-researcher, lecturer

TEACHING METHODS

demonstrate, engage by example, guide (e.g. setting initial program status), trigger investigation, orchestrate discussion.

EXPECTED STUDENT ACTIVITY

Students during the activity are expected to engage in the following actions: writing, observing, constructing

STUDENT LEARNING PROCESSES

<i>Designed Conflicts and misconceptions</i>	Misconceptions about the way of Robot walking - locomotion
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<i>Learning processes emphasized:</i>	Emphasis on studying the walking mechanisms of man and animals, and how students can construct a walking mechanism for robots.
<i>Expected relevance of alternative knowledge</i>	Emphasis on mathematical and analytical thinking. Also in designing, constructing and improving mechanisms.

STUDENT PRODUCTIONS

PRODUCTION	DESCRIPTION
<i>Artifacts - robots</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Assignment: To construct walking mechanisms for robots ▪ Interaction: Gesture ▪ Morphology: Theo Jansen mechanism, Klann linkage ▪ Behavior: Walking robot. ▪ Material: Electronics, software, mechanics etc.
<i>Programs - code</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Structure of code-commands: Sequential programming, commands for simple movement ▪ Elements: commands for activating motors ▪ Conditionals: time depending commands
<i>Discussions – arguments</i> (Describe the emphasis of the activity plan in one or more types of discussion provided in the next cell)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Descriptive - explanatory: description of a situation, a construct or an idea for others to understand and /or to implement ▪ Alternative: provision of solutions to problems, provision of alternatives if a dead end is reached ▪ Critical - objection: N.A. ▪ Contributory - extending: sharing of resources, provision of ideas towards improving an existing construct or initial idea

Sequence and description of activities

PRE-PHASE: INTRODUCTION

Duration: 15 min

Orchestration: assembly discussion - brainstorming

Description: The teachers explain what will happen in this workshop and the children will learn how to design walking mechanisms for robots. All of the team is going to have a brainstorming session regarding the investigated theme.

PHASE 1: GROUP FORMULATION – CONSTRUCTION

Duration: 30 minutes

Orchestration: group work

Description: Children are introduced to the Klann linkage for walking mechanism. The students are going to study the linkage. They will try to find the basic ideas behind the mechanism, and then the teams are going to construct a walking robot-based on Klann linkage.

The children are guided step by step through five important topics, eventually they design a specific robot a zoomorphic insect.

STEP 1 – BRAINSTORMING: WALKING.

The children are asked to consider how humans and animals move. What is the mechanism that supports movement of humans and animals?

STEP 2 – BASIC THEORY OF WALKING MECHANISMS: KLANN LINKAGE AND THEO JANSEN MECHANISM.

There is going a short explanation of basic walking mechanisms. Videos and presentations will help the students to understand the mechanisms.

PHASE 2: “CONSTRUCTING”

Duration: 4 hours

Orchestration: group work

Description: The groups of children will construct the mechanisms

Step 1: Klann linkage

Step 2: Theo Jansen mechanism

PHASE 3: INTERACTING - CONTEST

Duration: 30 minutes

Orchestration: group work

Description: The students are going to test the robots of the other groups. Also there will be an dancing (or speed) contest with robots. The teams are going to program depending the theme of the contest.

PHASE 4: EVALUATION

Duration: 15 minutes

Orchestration: group work

Description: We collect all the data (questionnaires, interviews, etc)

Assessment Procedures

FOCUS	ASSESSMENT METHOD OR TOOL
<i>Are popular gender stereotypes about STEM held?</i>	Draw a scientist
<i>Past experience and existing attitudes to STEM subjects and careers</i>	Pre-questionnaire
<i>Past experience and existing attitudes to STEM subjects and careers Includes questions about the activities to help understand</i>	Post-questionnaire

<i>learner's experiences of the workshop as a whole, what participants feel they have learned and what their future intentions are</i>	
<i>Understand the experience of participants and their reasons for particular actions</i>	Interview with focus group
	Peer assessment
	Essays- Tests-Student productions (code-robots-textual communication – presentations)
	Observation notes
	Reflection Sheet

4.13 A ROBOTIC INSECT

AUTHOR:

Nikitopoulou Sofia (researcher – teacher)

Partner: UoA - ETL

Focus, Set up and Requirements of the activity

CURRICULUM

Select NO if the scenario is not aligned with the curriculum of your country and YES if it is. Please mention the relevant subject matter.

NO YES Subject: Electrical Engineering

CONTENT

Choose categories and give a rating of the level of emphasis on concepts from each of the following domains

<input type="checkbox"/> Science	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Technology	<input type="checkbox"/> Business	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Engineering	<input type="checkbox"/> Arts	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Mathematics
(0-10)	(0-10)	(0-10)	(0-10)	(0-10)	(0-10)
0	4	0	10	0	10

OBJECTIVES

<i>Subject related</i>	Study the angle and position of all materials (servo motors, circuits, sensors), as well as the construction of the legs in order for the insect to be autonomous and move correctly.
<i>Technology use related</i>	Programming of Arduino.

<i>Social and action related</i>	Improve collaborative skills, take roles within groups
<i>Argumentation and fostering of maker culture:</i>	Practice making conjectures about how the robot will react to external stimuli based on the program given

TIME

Duration: 2 weeks

Schedule: 6 hours per week

MATERIALS AND ARTIFACTS

<i>Digital artifact</i>	Programming Language
<i>Robotic artifact</i>	An insect
<i>Student's workbook and manual</i>	Manual with step-by-step instructions for the construction, electronic and programming parts
<i>Teacher's instruction book and manual:</i>	Three incisive stages and five steps for the first two stages using workshop's slides.

Students and space

STUDENTS (TARGET AUDIENCE)

<i>Sex and Age:</i>	Boys & girls, 15-17 years old
<i>Prior knowledge:</i>	Little if any knowledge of Arduino but 10 pupils out of 20 are experts on electronics
<i>Nationality and cultural background</i>	5 pupils are from Albania, 2 from Bulgaria, 1 from Poland and 12 from Greece.
<i>Social status and social environment</i>	Underprivileged area.
<i>Special needs and abilities</i>	2 pupils suffer from ADD (Attention Deficit Disorder)

SPACE INFO

Organizational and cultural context: In school at the engineering laboratory

Physical characteristics: indoors

Social Orchestration

POPULATION

Students: 20

Tutors: 2

GROUPING:

<i>Grouping criteria</i>	Mixed ability, mixed gender - mixed specialties for 3 groups
<i>Setting:</i>	students in a normal classroom, around light mobile tables, looking at the blackboard, in small groups of 3

INTERACTION DURING THE ACTIVITY (EMPHASIS)

Actions	Exchange ideas, dialogue, negotiation, debate
Relationships	Collaborative, competitive
Roles in the group	Emergent roles
Support by the tutor(s)	Intervene, monitor, facilitate

Teaching and Learning Procedures**TEACHER'S ROLE**

Mentor, co-researcher, lecturer.

TEACHING METHODS

Demonstrate, engage by example, guide (e.g. setting initial program status), trigger investigation, orchestrate discussion.

EXPECTED STUDENT ACTIVITY

Students during the activity are expected to engage in the following actions:

STUDENT LEARNING PROCESSES

<i>Designed Conflicts and misconceptions</i>	Biology is irrelevant to mathematics
<i>Learning processes emphasized:</i>	Emphasis on studying robot behavior as a result of the usage of sensors and the program that defined the robot's behavior (i.e. use robot behavior as feedback on programming)
<i>Expected relevance of alternative knowledge</i>	Emphasis on mathematical thinking (i.e. the construction of the insect's legs depends on a specific geometry pattern in order for the zoomorphic robot to move).

STUDENT PRODUCTIONS

PRODUCTION	DESCRIPTION
<i>Artifacts - robots</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Assignment: Entertain, keep company. ▪ Interaction: Gesture ▪ Morphology: Zoomorphic ▪ Behavior: Pet ▪ Material: electronics, software, mechanics, materials like wood and paper clips
<i>Programs - code</i>	Structure of code-commands: The program was divided in a number of different procedures. Sub-procedures were used. 5.2.2 Elements: Iteration: for loop, while loop etc., selection: if, ifelse, if not etc., arithmetic variables, recursion etc. 5.2.3 Conditionals: Event handling of the sensors.
<i>Discussions – arguments</i> (Describe the emphasis of the activity plan in one or more types of discussion provided in the next cell)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Descriptive - explanatory: description of a situation, a construct or an idea for others to understand and /or to implement ▪ Alternative: provision of solutions to problems, provision of alternatives if a dead end is reached

	<ul style="list-style-type: none">▪ Critical - objection: N.A.▪ Contributory - extending: sharing of resources, provision of ideas towards improving an existing construct or initial idea
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Sequence and description of activities

PRE-PHASE: INTRODUCTION

Duration: 20 min

Orchestration: assembly discussion

Description: The teachers explain that will happen in this workshop and the students will learn how to design robots. We expect that students will broaden their view of technology as “something that we build to make our lives easier-happier” and they will be encountered with the idea that “true robots act autonomously”. From then on, students are expected to start thinking critically about it.

PHASE 1: GROUP FORMULATION – CONSTRUCTION

Duration: 3 hours

Orchestration: group work

Description: Students are introduced to the idea that “Real robots are highly complex and designed by a team of experts from different disciplines (designers, human-robot-interaction experts, programmers, engineers, etc.)”. The students are guided step by step through five important topics, eventually they design a specific robot a zoomorphic insect.

STEP 1 – ROBOT TASK: “ASSIGNMENT”.

The children are asked to imagine a robot for themselves that does anything they want. Every idea is valuable in this phase and not discarded as useless or undoable.

STEP 2 – ROBOT INTERACTION.

Known and not yet invented applications are both encouraged equally. Students learn that some of their ideas need scientists who invent new things that are then built into robots by engineers. How would you tell your robot what to do? Would you talk to it in a secret language or with signs? Would the robot understand your thoughts? Or would you use an app to control it?

STEP 3 – ROBOT MORPHOLOGY: “LOOKS AND MATERIALS”.

We divide the third step, robot morphology, into “looks” and “materials”. First, we introduce the robot morphology “Robots have to look like animal (zoomorphic)”. Second, we talk about different materials robots can be made of, and describe some properties: They can feel smooth, hard, furry, etc. How would your robot feel like?

STEP 4 – ROBOT BEHAVIOR.

In the fourth step, the abstract concept of autonomous behavior needs to be explained in a manner that children understand. We use two paths: In order to make the abstract word “behavior” more concrete, we describe roles (or personas) with which children identify. Would you like your robot to be rather like a protector, a pet or a friend? We also explain that robots have rules to obey.

STEP 5 – ROBOT PARTS.

This last step brings the previous steps together. The teachers-researchers show pictures of mechanic and electronic parts: some are used in every robot; others depend on what the robot does, how it looks like or how it should behave. In the beginning of the design process, the focus is on the holistic view of a product developer who needs to know what parts are needed but is not concerned with the details.

PHASE 2: PROGRAMMING

Duration: 2 hours

Orchestration: group work

Description: The groups of students will deal with the programming part of the robot.

PHASE 3: EVALUATION

Duration: 40 minutes

Orchestration: group work

Description: We collect all the data (questionnaires, interviews, etc)

Assessment Procedures

FOCUS	ASSESSMENT METHOD OR TOOL
<i>Are popular gender stereotypes about STEM held?</i>	Draw a scientist
<i>Past experience and existing attitudes to STEM subjects and careers</i>	Pre-questionnaire
<i>Past experience and existing attitudes to STEM subjects and careers Includes questions about the activities to help understand learner’s experiences of the workshop as a whole, what participants feel they have learned and what their future intentions are</i>	Post-questionnaire
<i>Understand the experience of participants and their reasons for particular actions</i>	Interview with focus group
	Peer assessment

	Essays- Tests-Student productions (code-robots-textual communication – presentations)
	Observation notes
	Reflection Sheet

5 EVALUATION OF ACTIVITY PLANS BY SCIENTIX AMBASSADORS

The first draft of the activity plans was created with use of the activity template in January. At this time of the project 8 activity plans were developed out of the 13 we are presented here. The 5 activity plans created by the teachers who collaborate with the UoA were delivered later, in March. ER4STEM made contact with the Scientix network⁶ and arranged an evaluation of the first draft of activity plans by five Scientix ambassadors. Scientix is a community for promoting innovative approaches in science education in Europe, thus an evaluation of ER4STEM activity plans from Scientix ambassadors was expected to provide useful criticism and interesting ideas on how to further develop and refine our activity plans so that they are appealing and useful for STEM teachers. The activity plans were reviewed by 5 Scientix Ambassadors coming from different areas of Europe (Bosnia-Herzegovina, Poland, Denmark, Sweden and Slovakia).

Evaluators⁷ were asked to comment in three questions, which involved a) their interest to implement the activity plans in their classroom as they are described b) their interest to adapt the activity plans in order to implement them in their classroom and c) the clarity of the structure and the presentation of the activity plans. The actual questions⁸ were formulated as follows:

- Would you implement this activity in your class or school as it is described? Why? Why not? Any cultural aspects?
- Would you implement this activity by adapting it to your class or school's needs? Why? Why not?
- If you have adapted the activity, would you use the activity plan to describe your version? Or would you use the activity plan to describe a new activity that you have created? Could you please elaborate if the activity plan is clearly structured and described? How should it be so that you use it?

Next we present an overview of the comments and we attempt an analysis of how these comments can be used for the refinement of the activity template and the activity plans in general. A summary of these comments is also provided in this section. The actual review of the Scientix Ambassadors is provided in Appendix 1 of this deliverable.

5.1 OVERVIEW AND REFLECTION ON THE EVALUATORS' COMMENTS

⁶ <http://www.scientix.eu/web/guest/about>

⁷ We use the term "Evaluators" and "Reviewers" interchangeably in this section to refer to the scientix ambassadors who reviewed the draft versions of activity plans.

⁸ The activity plan review document ER4STEM gave to the Scientix ambassadors is presented in Appendix 1 section 9.1.

Before presenting each review per activity plan, we attempt a critical reflection on the review of the activity plans as a whole. Specifically, in this section we investigate what are the factors determining the replicability (1st question of the review) and the adaptability of the activity plans (2nd question) as well as the general structure and clarity of the activity plans (3rd question). Next we focus on other issues raised from the reviews which need to be considered in the second version, we identify appealing characteristics of the activity plans so as to reinforce them in the second version and suggestions made by the reviewers.

Replicability

In this section we present aspects that seemed to influence reviewers' decisions on the replicability of an activity plan in their country – school – or classroom. Some of the parameters identified are related to cultural differences among European countries, while others involve aspects related to the topic of the activities and the technology used. Before analyzing each parameter separately we need to point out here that replicability largely depends on the level of detail used to describe the implementation of activities (the “how to” in the classroom – section “sequence and description of activities” in the activity plans”) in the classroom. This aspect is further elaborated in subsection “Form and structure of activity plans” which relates to the 3rd question of the evaluation.

LANGUAGE OF ACTIVITY PLANS

The 4th review stressed the issue of the language of activity plans as a parameter affecting its replicability and adaptability by the Danish teachers. This was an issue raised in only one review and it mainly involved cases where activity plans were considered “main stream” STEM activities similar to many other activities available also in the native language of the reviewer (in Danish). Even though only one reviewer brought up the issue of Language, we acknowledge that in Europe has a special importance. Thus, in the second year of the project we will attempt to tackle this issue, by taking into account the travel well criteria of the European school net (<http://www.eqnet.eun.org/web/guest/travel-well-learning-resources>) for the production of learning resources, crowd-sourcing techniques and the use of multimedia instead of exclusively textual information.

ALIGNMENT WITH CURRICULA

Alignment of activity plans with the National curriculum or with a set of standardised competences emerged in most of the reviews. Specifically, if the subject matter of the activity plan (e.g. like programming) was not part of the National curriculum of the reviewer's country of origin then the activity plan wasn't considered replicable as is. Furthermore, the reviewer from Denmark stressed the need for alignment of the activities with “visible learning targets” or competences within the subject defined by the Danish ministry of Education. ER4STEM is going to consider who to address this issue in the second year of the project a) taking into account existing practices (like the travel well criteria for the development of learning resources of the European School Net) b) developing in the framework a skills- tree and mapping the activity plans to this tree c) examining other options like crowdsourcing techniques (i.e. making available the activity plans to teacher communities like Scientix and asking from the participants to align activity plans of their choice to their national curriculum).

MAINSTREAM AND INNOVATIVE ACTIVITIES

Mainstream activities (especially when it comes to programming) with which reviewers seem to be more familiar appears to be considered more easily replicable. This is more an inference rather than a clear statement made by the reviewers. Our observation lies on comments like “the activity is easy to implement”, it is similar to other existing activities etc. However, this advantage can turn at the same time to disadvantage when it comes to replication because then we need to answer to the question why would a teacher choose this activity plan over many similar others? Furthermore, it appears that mainstream activities might not be able to “travel well” if they are not fully aligned with the national curriculum of other European countries or being described in an appealing and informative way or being translated in various other languages.

On the other hand, innovative activities also attracted the reviewers’ interest to replicate them. Thus, reviewers stated that they would be interested to implement activities that are inherently multidisciplinary and address very well new subjects like business (See section 5.4 Crazy Robots); activities that seamlessly integrate skills like creativity and collaboration (in the sense that these skills are exploited and become necessary for the completion of the task); activities that refer to topics not usually addressed in STEM with Robotics (like biology – see section 5.13). However, in one case (see 5th review section 6.2) “crazy robots” which is one of the activities we consider innovative, was considered difficult to implement because the reviewer considered that additional training was necessary.

The above observations show that the question is not innovative or mainstream activities. Under certain circumstances both types of activities might have advantages and disadvantages and replicability seems to depend to a set of different parameters. Our approach in ER4STEM is to produce both types of activities and / or integrate elements of both approaches in our activity plans (i.e structure an innovative activity plan with some mainstream activities in the lesson plan so that teachers can find familiar aspects in them or enrich mainstream activity plans with some optional innovative activities).

TECHNOLOGIES: ROBOTIC KIT AND PROGRAMMING LANGUAGE(S)

An activity that uses a familiar, wide spread technology like Lego mindstorm for example or Lego NXT seems to be more easily replicable in comparison to technologies that are more demanding in their use (like Arduino). Interestingly enough, custom made robotic technologies (like the case of “Crazy Robots” and the case of technologies produced by ESI-CEE – “introduction to robotics with Arduino, Scratch and Mindmaps”), were not considered difficult to use and did not seem to be an obstacle in replicating the activity plan as such. Considering that adaptability does not depend only on one characteristic of the activity plan but on a set of parameters, our assumption regarding the role of technology in the replicability of an activity plan, is that the robotic kit is not seen in isolation but in relation to the following parameters: a) the use of multiple programming languages like in the Scratch, Mindmaps and Arduino; b) the support of the construction process with a visual guide; c) the detailed documentation of the lesson plan (how to process); d) the interesting topic of the activity plan (involving business and seamless collaboration between teams – Crazy robots).

ROBOTIC KIT AVAILABILITY AND COST.

The availability of the suggested robotic kit in the school seems to be a factor influencing replicability of the activity plan. This became apparent in reviewers’ justifications, which stated “we have this robotic kit in our school” thus this activity plan would be easily implemented. Furthermore, reviewers identified that some activity plans (see 4th review) could be implemented

with many other robotic kits – especially activities which are introductory to robotics – and this characteristic made them appealing for implementation.

Lack of robotic kits in a school and the problem of their cost was a barrier for implementation for the 1st evaluator (See 1st Review section 6.2). ER4STEM in the second year will look for solutions to the issue of robotic cost and provide low cost or no cost alternatives for teachers and schools how have difficulties in buying robotic kits.

PREVIOUS KNOWLEDGE REQUIRED

Activity plans without the requirement for specific previous knowledge appeared to be easier to replicate (1st reviewer in one activity plan). However this is not to say that this is a decisive parameter for the replication of an activity plan.

Adaptability

In this section we present the dimensions of adaptability we identified in the comments of the evaluators. In the second version of the activity plans and in the framework we plan to design for adaptability of the activity plans so as to make them useful to a wide range of teachers by making suggestions for alternatives. Before analyzing each dimension separately we need to mention that an activity wasn't opted for adaptation because the reviewer considered that a lot of work was needed in order to produce the accompanying material (help with the technology, provision of solutions, illustrative lesson plan) that would facilitate the implementation in the classroom (4th review – Reference to the draft of "A robotic insect")

HARDWARE AND SOFTWARE

One of the parameters that seem to influence the adaptability is a) the use, in activity plans, of Kits that can communicate with multiple programming languages (when the emphasis is both on construction and programming) b) the design of activity plans that can be implemented with more than one robotic kits. With respect to the second dimension ER4STEM will work towards identifying a) the special characteristics of specific robotic technologies and design learning activities that exploit exactly these characteristics of the kit and b) learning activities that can be supported by various robotic kits.

SETTING

Adaptability of the first draft of activity plans involved their transfer from normal classroom to the context of extra-curricular activities. This seemed a solution when alignment with national curricula was not possible or when the focus of the activity was not covered by a specific curriculum. However, the innovative character of the activity seemed to influence its selection for extra-curricular activities. Another interesting context for adapting mainly the preparation workshop for ECER conference and the actual conference is the context of summer schools organized for students which was suggested by the 5th reviewer.

TEACHING ASSISTANTS

The presence of assistants in the classroom for the implementation of the activity plan does not seem to be a common practice in schools across Europe. Thus adaptation of activity plans included suggestions for collaboration among teachers and / or alterations in the tasks. These suggestions will be included in the second version of activity plans and others will be explored in order to support a wider range of teachers and learning settings.

AGE OF PARTICIPANTS

Adaptation of activity plans also focused on suggesting implementation for different age groups according to the background of the country in exploiting digital technologies in the classroom. Thus, the reviewer for Denmark for example suggested for several activities to address younger students while reviewers from the south like Bosnia Herzegovina and Slovakia suggested the opposite.

DURATION OF ACTIVITY PLANS AND TIME MANAGEMENT

Duration of the most activity plans did not emerge as a parameter that needed adaptation to different settings. We interpreted this as an indication that Schools across Europe can easily integrate these activities in their science or technology classrooms within the time frame suggested. However, adaptation seemed necessary when it came to intensive courses like the conference and the workshop for competition preparation, where student engagement was expected to last between 8 and 10 hours a day. As mentioned earlier this adaptation was accompanied by suggestions to include this type of activity plans in extra-curricular activities and/or summer schools. This indicates a special characteristic of robotics as a learning environment because it appears that students can engage with the subject for long. Furthermore, evaluators in some cases suggested the prolongation of the timing of some activities included in the activity plans changing slightly the overall timing of the activity or compromising the overall duration by shortening other activities.

VISITS TO UNIVERSITIES OR RESEARCH CENTERS

Visits to universities or Research centers with expertise in Robotics seemed appealing to some evaluators who suggested that they could transfer this visit to a local University (e.g. Aarhus, Zilinia). For the design of the next version of activity plans we consider integrating other alternatives for teachers who may not have access to such centers like video-conferencing.

SOCIAL ORCHESTRATION AND COLLABORATION

Learning with educational robotics seems to have a very strong social dimension; rarely someone can see students working with their robots exclusively in isolation as it might happen with other tasks. More than one reviewer stressed the importance of group work in their comments and found “Crazy Robots”, an activity with a strong social dimension, very appealing. Adaptations with respect to this part of activity plans involved: a) teachers determining the criteria for group formulation b) using more skillful students as group supervisors and teacher assistants and c) dividing groups of students between advanced and beginners as opposed to the mixed abilities groups suggested by most activities. This last adaptation was accompanied by comments questioning the effectiveness of mixed ability groups in Robotics as more skillful students seem to work faster and prevail over other students. There seems to be a differentiation in Robotics when compared with other domains

as groups seem to be performance oriented (they want to make the robot to work) and they do whatever is effective in terms of final product and not in terms of collaboration.

EVALUATION ACTIVITIES

Most of the reviewers stressed the importance of evaluating the learning outcome of the activity plans. When activity plans like the one describing the ECER conference did not have explicit evaluation activities, some reviewers marked this as a missing and important part of the activity. Adaptations included suggestions for quantitative evaluation and the inclusion of evaluation activities addressing the parents (so that they know what their children learn when engaged with such activities).

Taking into account that robotics as a learning object and as a context for learning subject matters related to STE(A)M has some special characteristics when compared to other subject matters (see Yiannoutsou et al., 2016), it is easy to understand that the evaluation of learning in this context is something that needs careful consideration. Evaluation of learning will be further investigated in the second version of activity plans attempting to identify all the different types of learning competences and skills that are involved in such an activity. Evaluation will address not only the results of learning but also the process and it will identify all the different aspects of the learning activity taking place (construction, programming, design, creativity, social skills, artistic skills, stem knowledge, critical thinking, project management, design thinking, time management, argumentation, social skills etc).

Form and structure of activity plans

A strong and useful criticism on the structure and the form of activity plans was made in the 4th Review (see section 6.2). Specifically, the activity plans were considered that were written in a very academic form and as such there were not appealing to the Danish teachers. The reviewer suggested to use digital design for the activity plan including multimedia: i.e. videos, designs, photographs and the creation of a u-tube channel. This approach is wide spread in Danish educational platforms according to the reviewer and the project following these suggestions will investigate alternatives to presenting activity plans during the second year of the project and it will inform the design of the project repository (WP1). In the same line, the 5th reviewer suggested the creation of an e-library with solutions to the tasks and with examples to be used in the classroom.

Furthermore when it comes to the structure of the activity plans the reviewer suggested to focus mainly on the “how to” part (Section: “Sequence and description of activities” in the activity plan template) omitting the grid about teacher methodologies and student activities. Detailed presentations of this section of the activity plan were positively received and they appeared to be one of the factors that seemed to facilitate replicability and adaptability of the activity plan (see review 4 of the “Crazy Robots”). This criticism about the level of detail of the “how to” section of the activity plans offers valuable feedback for refinement in the second year. In line with our observations that the section describing the sequence of activities did not include aspects of the teaching methodology of the objectives stated, we consider modifying the activity plan template so that it will be populated with suggested constructionist (see section 4.3) and social activities to be included in the activity plans created by teachers.

The 4th reviewer stressed the need to provide notes for the teachers regarding the use of the suggested technology especially if it is not wide spread like Arduino. The same comment did not

come up when more wide spread technologies like Lego or more simple technologies like Dash and Dot were included in the activity plan. This comment is very helpful for the development of the refined version of activity plans because it can help to make them useful for STEM teachers not acquainted with robotics technologies (or not acquainted with all robotics technologies available). The plan for the refined version is to include something like a “walkthrough” on the technologies addressing other teachers who are not familiar – i.e. how the specific teacher created the robot, “tips and tricks” for the construction and programming of the robot.

Appealing elements of activity plans

In this section we summarize those characteristics of activity plans that were found appealing to reviewers in order to strengthen them in the second version of the activity plans:

- Providing a visual guide for robot construction especially when students are beginners
- Promotion of critical thinking by the activity plan
- Promotion of maker culture and creative thinking
- Dash and Dot was addressed as a good option for introduction to coding and robotics and for work with young students (Primary schools)
- Promotion of social and action related goals of an activity that can be related to the different personalities of the children and their diverse contributions (Reference to Crazy Robots)
- Interaction between teams as a necessary prerequisite for the completion of the task
- Teamwork expertise and exchange of ideas
- Botball was addressed as a good option for middle and high school students
- Include robotic kits that can communicate with multiple programming languages
- Addressing students with special needs (like ADD)

Controversial elements of activity plans

Reviewers from Northern European countries regarded the awards mentioned in the conference (workshop 8) differently from the other Europeans. Specifically, the reviewer from Sweden (3rd Review) said that awards would be removed from the workshop plan if it was to be adapted for a school setting because students would be stressed if an award was at stake and this was expected to block their creativity. Similarly the Reviewer from Denmark (4th reviewer) made a remark of removing the awards in order to adapt the conference in the school setting. Interestingly other reviewers considered the awards a motivation for the students and they pointed out that the existence of many awards so that most of the students would be covered was a very good idea.

Several Greek teachers, in their reflections, mentioned that organizing a competition between teams, at the end of the task, was a strong motivation for their students, even if there was no award involved. It appears that competition and awards are a cultural issue, which needs to be addressed in the framework of ER4STEM and in the second version of the activity plans.

Suggestions

Reviewers in their comments made several suggestions addressing various aspects of the activity plans. In this section we summarise these comments and we will take them into account in the second version of the activity plans:

- Online collaboration between schools from different countries for competition preparations
- Introduce social orchestration with mixed expertise: identify different activities and tasks per expertise (electronics students, computer science etc.)
- In conference settings: students skilful in programming to act as supervisors
- To overcome problems related to financial issues (i.e. obtaining toolkits) it is suggested collaboration between industries and education.
- Use Plickers and Kahoot.it good for formative assessment and critical thinking engagement

5.2 SUMMARY OF SCIENTIX AMBASSADORS' COMMENTS

In this section we present in the form of a table, a summary of the comments made by the Scientix ambassadors in the first version of the activity plans. This section consists of 5 tables. Each table corresponds to the comments of each evaluator per review question and per activity plan.

1st Review – Bosnia Herzegovina

1. EVALUATOR: Ivan Derek Primary School Teacher - Bosnia Herzegovina				
Partner	Workshop	Implementation of activity as it is described	Adaptation of the activity in order to implement it	Usefulness of the template to adapt the plan - is the plan clearly structured and described?
TU-Wien	Bee Programming (7 -10 years old) 1a,1b,1c	Conduct the activity as described- (the class has no robots): Good points: use robots to learn programming (demonstrate programming) b) sequential programming (breaking a problem to smaller parts) c) Development of social skills	Adaptation of the activity for other topics such as controlling robots with the use of sensors	Clearly described scenario - recognized the validity of the structure of the template
ESI-CEE	2. Introducing robotics with Arduino, Scratch and Mindmaps	Conduct the activity as described-however there is the problem of financial support by the school. Good points highlighted: a)Role of teacher as facilitator & consultant b)Use of the visual guide for robot construction c)Use of multiple programming languages d) Work in teams	Problems in adapting the activity for financial reasons (school cannot buy the specific robotic set)	Good structure of the activity- Estimation that more time is required for the programming part of the activity. Good point the combination of constructionist and instructionist approach on behalf of the teacher.
PRIA	ECER-Botball- Preparation-Workshop	Use of BotBall- great idea, however a) not appropriate for primary schools b) C programming language not part of the country's curricula	Adaptation not possible for public schools which need to follow the National Curricula. Private schools however would have more freedom. In public schools there is a process a) getting approval by the ministry of education and b) funding for obtaining Botball. IDEA-	Good structure of the activity- Good point the groups with pre-defined goals available for selection (programmer, builder etc). Comment on social orchestration-suggestion that 6 instructors would better facilitate the process with 100 students.

D4.1 FIRST VERSION OF THE ACTIVITY PLANS

			collaboration between industry and education	
UoA-ETL	4: A robotic Insect	Not possible the implementation due to lack of robots in the school (ref to response for workshop 1c)	Adapt the activity plan to emphasise the different steps for the creation of a robot. Strong point of the activity the cross-curricular nature	Not clear description of the activity plan - not clear if the focus is on construction of the legs or students will also get involved in learning how to program in Arduino. Suggestion: state clearly the objective - then divide it to smaller steps. Collaboration: problem with the different nationalities- not stated how the students communicate and what are the National curricula for these countries - Mixed abilities groups - not stated what abilities are the criterion - suggestion for introductory test. Good idea the sequential phases (three phases- five steps)
UoA-ETL	5: Introducing programming structures using LEGO NXT	Not possible the implementation due to lack of robots in the school (ref to response for workshop 1c)	Adaptation if the kit was available in school. MS Logo is taught in the school - After school activity. Good point that no prior knowledge of Logo NXT is required. Adaptation would involve connection of MS Logo to NXT Logo environment	Very good structure of the activity plan. NOTE material in english - suggestion that one of the students would be the translator- Experiment with loops before being introduced in the main activity
AL	6: Introduction to Dash and Dot	More clear description is required to determine if the plan should be implemented as is.	Adaptation would involve getting to know fundamental concepts of robots like movements or other functionalities of the specific kit - integration in a game like activity.	Problems with the structure: Not clearly defined objectives. Suggested objective: control the robot through coding and then introduce blocks for movement, loops etc. At the end organize a competition: i.e. drive the robot through a maze

TU-Wien	7: Crazy robots – Robotic Product Development	Problem of equipment - The activity would be implemented as described. Good points: students gain much more than the knowledge of robotics: planning, building the robot in relation to demands of customers, different areas of robotics, behaving with different target groups	Small adaptation for implementation: More time in the second phase to familiarize students with the robot parts and arduino language (not part of curriculum)	Perfect structuring of the activity plan. Excellent the idea of making a robot from scratch as it makes necessary collaboration and introduces other aspects of robotics such as sales and marketing. Good mapping between objectives and activities - First phase enhances creativity. Second phase: leaving open the choice of students to select the group they will join (Sales & Marketing, Engineering, HRI, Research & Development, Design) is great because all ideas are considered. Estimation that more time is needed for each of these phases. Reflection at the end: great idea
PRIA	European Conference on Educational Robotics	No. Problem of equipment and student programming knowledge.	Yes. Appealing aspects: use of multiple programming languages, teamwork and collaboration - competition, practice English as working language	Yes

2nd Review - Poland

2. Małgorzata Zajackowska Poland			
Partner	Workshop	Implementation of activity as it is described	Adaptation of the activity in order to implement it
TU-Wien	Bee Sequential Programming (7 -10 years old) 1a,1b,1c		No evaluation provided
		Usefulness of the template to adapt the plan - is the plan clearly structured and described?	

ESL-CEE	2. Introducing robotics with Arduino, Scratch and Mindmaps	Highlighted critical thinking and the encouragement of students to express their individual ideas and then enable the thinking in groups	Implementation in the classroom: Positive response under the condition that the evaluator is not a primary school teacher. Stresses the importance of the visual guide. Points out that students at this age do not work at a steady pace	Identifies consistency between goals and activities - stresses the evaluation for learning- clear and well written
PRIA	3.ECER-Botball-Preparation-Workshop	Not previous experience, however it seems feasible in cooperation with schools from the neighborhood. The 16 hour workshop seems short. Suggestion to work online with Austrian peers and then participate in the tournament	Stresses the issue of skills with different abilities, more skillful working faster	Sufficient details for replication and evaluation
UoA-ETL	4: A robotic Insect	Not direct response to the implementation. Various questions regarding social orchestration- group creation, group handling- identified that 15-17 difficult group age	Relating different levels of work to the different expertise of the students	More details are needed regarding the evaluation
UoA-ETL	5: Introducing programming structures using LEGO NXT	The evaluator says that she would implement the activity- no previous knowledge needed- interaction between teams	Very well described teaching and learning activities- easily adapted by teachers and designers	Clear, replicable, can be evaluated.
AL	6: Introduction to Dash and Dot	Not enough information provided by the activity plan so the evaluator can not determine an answer to this question	Not enough information provided by the activity plan so the evaluator can not determine an answer to this question	Dash and Dot good for introduction to coding and robotics with young children. Longer than 4 hours. Pickers and Kahoot:it good for wrapping up a workshop with the students. Evaluation could be enriched with more activities (like parent - student feedback)
TU-Wien	7: Crazy robots – Robotic Product Development	YES the evaluator would implement the activity. Stresses the social and action related goals takes into account the different personalities and diverse	Suggestions: Robot in more advanced shape/ asking students to design their own heroes=> compare between countries. When large groups are	Suggestion so that assessment addresses also parents. Self-assessment of students. Excellent style and content.

		contribution for a common project	involved meetings of smaller groups to reach the social actions.	
PRIA	European Conference on Educational Robotics	One-week conference seems long. Good choice of kit	Stresses the learning by doing and the gathering of teamwork experience. Suggestion for introducing skilful students in programming as group supervisors	Very good description- evaluation is missing

3rd Review - Sweden

3. EVALUATOR: Jennie Malmberg Sweden				
Partner	Workshop	Implementation of activity as it is described	Adaptation of the activity in order to implement it	Usefulness of the template to adapt the plan - is the plan clearly structured and described?
TU-Wien	Bee Sequential Programming (7-10 years old) 1a,1b,1c	Yes because of the explorative nature of activities - Points out that the teacher should have a good knowledge on Robotics and programming	Yes, if there was a teacher's guide or movie. Programming not part of the curriculum. Good way of introducing programming to Swedish schools – Need for a good manual for teachers	Comments about the importance of knowledge around robotics and programming (Arduino, Scratch). Group work appealing but groups should be formulated by the teacher-
ESI-CEE	2. Introducing robotics with Arduino, Scratch and Mindmaps	Good approach - appealing the focus on creativity and collaboration - the different options also are appealing for implementation	Barrier to implementation the number of students and the existence of assistants	Suggestion to formulate groups with less students
PRIA	ECER-Bothall-Preparation-Workshop	YES: appealing: timing, creativity, collaboration, step-by-step guide for inexperienced students, gradual difficulty.	Adaptation for the school removing the dimension of competition - not a part of the Swedish culture: - blocking creativity, stress	Good structure
UoA-ETL	4: A robotic Insect	Appealing elements: groups with different expertise, gradual difficulty	Difficult to adapt if you need expertise that is not available to younger students: collaboration among students of	Good structure

			different ages	
UoA-ETL	5: Introducing programming structures using LEGO NXT	YES: appealing: timing, creativity, collaboration, gradual difficulty, activity-sheets.	Yes, no adapting needed	Good structure
AL	6: Introduction to Dash and Dot	Yes: Appealing elements: The robotic kit (Dash and Dot) and the lesson plans that come with it, introduction video	Yes, introduction to programming with play.	More details in the activity sequence are needed
TU-Wien	7: Crazy robots – Robotic Product Development	collaboration of different expert groups (marketing, desing, research and development), Long project: one semester, seamless integration of communication in the activity.	More details required on the timing and the laws of robotics	
PRIA	European Conference on Educational Robotics	Appealing elements: the preparatory activity and the feedback provided to the students	Clarify the expectations from teachers and students before the conference	More info about the preparation of the students

4th Review - Denmark

4. EVALUATOR: Thorbjørn Harrelius_Denmark				
Partner	Workshop	Implementation of activity as it is described	Adaptation of the activity in order to implement it	Usefulness of the template to adapt the plan - is the plan clearly structured and described?
TU-Wien	Bee Sequential Programming (7-10 years old) 1a,1b,1c	1a) Activity would not be implemented as is- lacks step by step info for teachers not familiar with robotics (short video or pictures). Teaching and learning sequence useful- Grid on interaction with students unnecessary- teachers are acquainted with this. 1b) yes- science class- more clear than 1a) implementation in afterschool context or with science classes - similar activities exist - academic form of paper.1c) use it	Yes: Adaptation from a technological perspective (lego and/or Fab/Lab) not necessarily one technology - time scale would need adaptation and the existence of two tutors (collaboration with other classes so that two teachers can collaborate). 1b) translation to Danish visual guide necessary 1c) Too academic form - you tube channel - visual guide- website. Emphasis on the	yes but more emphasis is needed on the actual how to (teaching sequence -) - alignment with "visible learning targets or competences" (National Curriculum)- Superficial reference to multidisciplinary. TRANSLATION is important

ESL-CEE	2. Introducing robotics with Arduino, Scratch and Mindmaps	with younger students	teaching sequence	Only the lesson plan is necessary!
		Video and audio material is necessary - many platforms exist with similar Danish activities- clear description about how students will gain new competences in coding.	Yes: maps well with the skills and concepts already taught, would use the activity for deepening understanding and checking acquired knowledge - existence of technology helps adaptation	
PRIA	ECER-Botball-Preparation-Workshop	Yes! Suits well the Danish teachers. Implement the activity with younger students 13-16	Yes! But it is too academic- should be enriched with pictures and video - translation to Danish	Collaborative work and teamwork appealing to teachers
UoA-ETL	4: A robotic Insect	YES- very good and would be adapted by Danish teachers- too academic. Needs to provide help to those not familiar with Arduino. Appealing that includes a student that suffers from ADD needs more info about what went well, if special attention is needed, what such students gain from this activity	No. Needs more details on the "how to" part - needs a lot of helpful notes and guides- too academic.	Needs further details on the how to part, needs helpful notes with respect to Arduino,. Interesting if the focus would be on students with ADD.
UoA-ETL	5: Introducing programming structures using LEGO NXT	Yes. Functional and easy to implement - appealing the maker culture element - too academic- should be more thorough on the presentation of the lesson plan (how to) designs, video, audio.	Yes - fits well without adaptation. Appealing the collaboration and working together	More in depth description of the lesson plan- more digital design and guides
AL	6: Introduction to Dash and Dot	Good intro to robotics- not sufficiently described - lesson plan easy to follow.	Prerequisite the possession of Dash and Dot. Easy adaptation for schools who have this technology. This plan could be followed for other similar technologies (Sphero, Lego Mindstorm, Sparki, MakeyMakey, Little Bits). Not clear what is the Unique Selling Point of the activity	Needs to provide guidance to teachers not familiar with Dash and Dot. Good for introduction to robotics- should be enriched with more digital skills.
TU-Wien	7: Crazy robots – Robotic Product Development	YES. However the visit to the university lab should be replaced. Appealing aspects: involvement of whole class, business element (collaboration in companies). Very	Adaptation so that one teacher can perform the activity - instead of the university visit the fab lab - experiment with other robotic kits. Include a group	Excellent lesson plan. The previous parts are not necessary for Danish teachers.

		helpful the lesson plan and the notes. The introduction of material like clay for the design of the robot.	of students to work on video production.	
PIA	European Conference on Educational Robotics	Too academic- should be formed as a competition poster - Timing is a bit problematic (10 hours per day)	Adapt it to a full day workshop with students from different schools working on their robot. (2 lessons for 4 weeks) the competitions could work	For school adaptation more focus is needed on collaboration and teamwork, awards wouldn't be included.

5th Review - Slovakia

5. EVALUATOR: Zuzana Christozova_Slovakia				
Partner	Workshop	Implementation of activity as it is described	Adaptation of the activity in order to implement it	Usefulness of the template to adapt the plan - is the plan clearly structured and described?
TU-Wien	Bee Sequential Programming (7 -10 years old) 1a,1b,1c	Yes: Appealing aspects: Understanding, Exploration, conceptualization and conclusion - analogies with the human body - story and story presentations of design solutions Yes: Appealing are the rules of work with robot, the aim of the workshop (building competitiveness) existence of complementary material: visual guide, teacher workbook and manual	Yes, easily adopted to classes on Informatics and/or extra-curricular activities Yes. Appealing is the modular structure of the workshop	Add a teacher's manual - motivational and creative approach, multimedia database of solved tasks Include quantitative assessment
ESI-CEE	2. Introducing robotics with Arduino, Scratch and Mindmaps	Yes: Relationship with the real world (animals, humans, insects). Interesting discussion with students. Necessary student workbook and manual. Manual and	Yes. Adapt to a summer school: Good structure, C programming language is appealing, Devote time on reflection and discussion of student solutions Yes: the idea of insects is appealing-	Well described activity
PIA	ECER-Bothall-Preparation-Workshop	Yes: instructions for the students to build the first drivable robot, the teacher should have instructions and manual	Yes. Adapt to a summer school: Good structure, C programming language is appealing, Devote time on reflection and discussion of student solutions	Create a multimedia database of solved tasks, ask students to prepare videos of solved tasks
UoA-ETL	4: A robotic Insect			

		instructions for the teachers		
UoA-ETL	5: Introducing programming structures using LEGO NXT	Yes: sequence and description of activities are convincing	Yes - because of acquaintance with technology (I Use Lego Mindstorm EV3)- provide elementary examples and solved tasks (e-library)	Yes- relevant to activities with Lego EV3 in the specific countries
AL	6: Introduction to Dash and Dot	Appealing activity for 7-8 year olds	Suggestion to use the website https://www.makewonder.com/ with examples and tasks of varied difficulty	Yes- the technology used (Dash and Dot) is appealing
TU-Wien	7: Crazy robots – Robotic Product Development	Appealing elements: visit to a robot lab, take and give between students and researchers, emphasis on design	Difficult to implement - training required	Collaboration with a university (Zilina) adaptation for students 15-18
PRIA	8. European Conference on Educational Robotics	Appealing elements: discussions between students and researchers, different types of awards	Adaptation for extra-curricular activity	Open participation to more countries

6 CONSIDERATIONS FOR THE SECOND VERSION OF ACTIVITY PLANS

Based on the analysis of the previous sections (especially section 3 and 5), we will outline here some considerations that will guide our work in the second year of the project. Specifically, our reflection in the first version of activity plans (section 3) revealed that two aspects of the teaching and learning process need special attention. One is related to the aspect of multidisciplinary and the other involves the social dimension of teaching and learning with ER.

Our observations about the multidisciplinary in the first version of the activity plans can be resumed to the following points:

- One activity plan (“Crazy robots”) demonstrated very good integration of subject like business, design, Human Robot Interaction and product evaluation and
- Mathematics and Physics are the best-integrated disciplines as some concepts from these domains are connected to the operation of robotics (e.g. physics laws influencing the motion of a robot, using the diameter of the robots wheel in order to determine the turning angle of the robot).
- Other subjects like arts and biology do not seem integrated in a deep and organic way in the activity plan mainly because the task does not require exploration and does not support student learning about the domain of arts or biology.

For the second year of work on activity plans we will work on refining the activity plan template and the first version of activity plans, so as to better support teachers and practitioners to design multidisciplinary learning activities with ER. To this end we will draw from two theoretical constructs: one is the concept of “powerful ideas” (Papert, 1980) and the other is the idea of “conceptual fields” (Vergnaud, 2009).

Powerful ideas are a concept developed around the theory of constructionism. Before getting into the concept of powerful ideas it is important to outline the context in which it developed which is constructionism. Constructionism shares with constructivism the idea that knowledge is actively constructed through the child’s interaction with the world and emphasize teaching not just as a process of directing learning towards a strict known end but as a process of offering opportunities to kids to engage in hands on explorations that fuel the constructive process (Ackermann, 2001). In constructionism, the constructive process of learning evolves around constructions with personal meaning for the learner (Papert, 1980), and is mediated by digital tools that empower learners to shape, express and share their inner ideas in and through their constructions (Ackermann, 2001). Constructions – being sand castles or theories about the universe (ibid) – as public entities to be shared and discussed, integrate elements of art that relate not only to the end product (i.e., the construction) but also to the process: the art of learning how to learn (ibid).

In this context, powerful ideas “involve new ways of thinking, new ways of putting knowledge into use and new ways of making personal and epistemological connections with other domains” (Papert, 2000, cited in Bers, 2008 p. 27). Bers (ibid) further analyzing powerful ideas, identifies 5 major connections one of which addressed directly their relationship to multidisciplinary:

“Powerful ideas serve as organizing principles for rethinking a whole domain of knowledge and connecting it with others. A domain defines specialty areas of knowledge where many diverse topics or subjects come together” (ibid pp. 28)

To elaborate how powerful ideas facilitate connections with other domains, she refers to the example of children being interested in animals. Animals can be a powerful idea because it can be connected with the domains of biology and geography. Children's personal interest (in this case to animals) is of central importance in constructionism related to the idea of ownership and agency (emergent curriculum). Personal interest is a second connection of powerful ideas, which is also relevant to the approach of designing activity plans for learning with ER.

Conceptual fields on the other hand offer another interesting viewpoint in multidisciplinary. Vergnaud investigating learning in mathematics, argued that mathematical concepts do not exist and are not learned in isolation *ibid* (2009): "a concept is altogether: a set of situations, a set of operational invariants⁹ (contained in schemes), and a set of linguistic and symbolic representations" (pp. 94). Thus understanding involves the situations and the examples in which a concept manifests its properties and also the symbolic representations by which this concept is mediated. Healy and Kynigos (2010) used the idea of conceptual fields to discuss the design of digital learning environments for mathematics (mathematical microworlds). In ER4STEM we plan to investigate how concepts related to robotics are manifested in different domains (subject matters) and how they are connected to form a power idea.

In the second year of the project we will combine the above theoretical constructs (powerful ideas and conceptual fields) to reconceptualize multidisciplinary working towards the following directions:

- a) Making explicit the implicit connections of activity plans to other domains. The designers of the activity plans (be it teachers, researchers, practitioners etc), often design focusing on their own domain of expertise. However, a teacher or an expert from another domain by going through the same activity plan, might identify connections with this new domain which were not clearly identified and elaborated in the activity plan. In this case some small alterations might be necessary and/ or a reconceptualization of the task.
- b) Suggesting adaptations of the activity plans so as to support learning in other domains that were not initially conceived or implied in the activity plan. This might mean that a teacher or a designer from another discipline adapts the activity plan so as to integrate seamlessly another STE(A)M domain.

The other aspect that seems to need special attention is the social dimension of learning in the context of the maker culture and argumentation as an instrument that forms not only collaboration but also learning and understanding (Wegerif, 2007). The maker culture is closely connected to the current trend where user activity incrementally shifts from consumption to participation and in which the distinction between users and designers is blurred (Fischer, 2009). This shift takes place through a technologically mediated transformation of the user from a passive consumer of finished goods designed by some to be consumed by many to an empowered individual equipped with the means to participate actively in the produced culture. Such constructionist tools, along with innovations such as 3D printing, democratize production by lending users the power to produce high-quality goods (physical or digital).

An important point to note here is that the use of tools oriented towards construction (from now on "constructionist tools") is situated in the powerful social space of virtual communities. Virtual

⁹ Operational invariants are concepts and theorems in actions from which the learner picks up relevant information and infer from it goals and rules.

communities are not just the space where members share and discuss their products. Instead, they constitute a learning environment that offers the support and the collective intelligence necessary for individuals (as opposed to companies or experts) to deal with the demanding process of constructing high-quality end products. Characteristic examples are, to name a few, the “Do It With Others Communities” (an evolution of the “Do It Yourself ” communities), the communities that develop and live around popular sandbox games (such as Minecraft) or around tools such as Scratch, the communities that organize events around technology and culture such as museomix (<http://museomixuk.tumblr.com>), etc.

The characteristics of constructionist tools designed to empower end users, new materials and innovations (3D printing and automation), by democratizing production, have empowered communities to such a degree that a new direction in the design and production process is identified. This new direction involves shifting the orientation of design as a top-down process of producing rigid closed products to a process that entails the... “ activation of open systems, tools that shape society by enabling self-organization platforms of collaboration independent of the capitalist model of competition, and empowering networks of production”^{10,11}

Our reference to the broader technological and societal landscape aims to show that what we called “social dimension” of learning with ER is an important skill for the citizens of today. Thus our work for the refinement of the activity plans will aim at strengthening the support of the social dimension of learning with robotics by structuring the social activity and suggesting relevant activities for the lesson plan. To this end we will identify best practices and examples where social interaction between the groups is necessary for the completion of the task (like in the case of “Crazy robots”). Furthermore, we will introduce simple tasks like creating a promotion video or a teaching video or a video with advice for other students enhancing also the maker culture among students.

The second version of activity plans will also take into account a set of considerations derived from the evaluation of the scientix ambassadors (see section 6):

- Emphasize the “how to” of activity plans (more detailed descriptions of the “sequence and description of activities”). To this end one solution to be explored might include suggesting a set of different activities described at a general level and requiring adaptation by the teachers (like the construction activities and programming activities described in section 4)
- Employ digital design solutions in the presentation of the activity plans like websites, YouTube channels, e-library with examples and solutions, use of pictures and videos, and refine language so as to be less academic and more appealing to teachers.
- Strengthen the maker culture among teachers by producing videos and walkthroughs with the technology that maybe useful for other teachers. This material will function as a teacher guide to the use of the robotic kit, will provide “tips and tricks” for other teachers on how to experiment with the specific technology, how they can construct the robot – which programming languages they can use, advice on how to program the robot behavior.

¹⁰ “Adhocracy” by Joseph Grima, M. Matters, December 2012, http://www.mplumatters.hk/asiandesign/paper_topic3.php

¹¹ The three paragraphs referring to the maker culture are taken from ETL’s recent work which is described in the following publication “Yiannoutsou N. (2015) Elements of Surprise in Teaching and Learning (Open Peer Commentary). In Special Issue on Constructionism and Creativity – Constructivist Foundations 10 (3) pp 383-384”

- Investigate solutions to language issues. We already mentioned the “travel well” criteria in the production of learning resources created by the European Schoolnet, the investigation of crowdsourcing techniques and of automatic translation.
- Investigate how we can address issues of alignment with national curricula across Europe. We already mentioned that the second version of the activity plans will be aligned with the skills tree developed in the framework (W.P.1) and we will also investigate crowdsourcing practices (introducing the activity plans to communities of STEM teachers and asking them to align selected activity plans to their national curriculum)
- Record observations, tips and ideas on how to support students with special needs (like ADD) when engaged with Robotics activity. This is an important parameter as it was stressed very much as an appealing element of the “Robotic Insect” by the 4th Reviewer.
- Investigate alternatives to address financial issues (i.e. cost of robotic kits), limited number of robotic kits in a classroom and / or absence of a robotic kit coupled with financial difficulties of the school to cover the expense of buying a new one. Our work here will also include SLurtres a potential low cost alternative (See D.5.2) to be tested in year 2 of the project.

The above list will be examined in relation to other project activities (i.e. Framework, evaluation, technologies) and will be prioritized and refined during the second year of the project. Furthermore, this list is not exhaustive, as the considerations included, will be informed by the first year evaluation of the project and will be taken into account in the second version of activity plans (D.4.2 Operational Release of activity plans Due in m 23)

7 GLOSSARY / ABBREVIATIONS

EC	European Commission
ER	Educational Robotics
ER4STEM	Educational Robotics for Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics
ERW	Educational Robotics Workshop
Implementation Team	All members of the team that implements the workshop including but not limited to facilitators, teachers, researchers, evaluators and others.
REA	Research Executive Agency
STE(A)M	Science, Technology, Engineering, Art, and Mathematics
STEM	Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics

8 BIBLIOGRAPHY

Ackermann, E. (2001). Piaget’s constructivism, Papert’s constructionism: What’s the difference. In *Constructivism: Uses and Perspectives in Education* (pp. 85–94). Geneva: Geneva Research Centre in Education. Retrieved from http://learning.media.mit.edu/content/publications/EA.Piaget%20_%20Papert.pdf

- Bers, M. U. (2008). *Blocks to robots: learning with technology in the early childhood classroom*. New York: Teachers College Press.
- Fischer, G. (2009). End-user development and meta-design: Foundations for cultures of participation. In V. Pipek, M. B. Rossen, B. deRuyter, & V. Wulf (Eds.), *End-User Development* (pp. 3–14). Heidelberg: Springer-Verlag.
- Healy, L., & Kynigos, C. (2010). Charting the microworld territory over time: design and construction in mathematics education. *ZDM Mathematics Education*, *42*, 63–76.
- Kynigos, C. (2004). A “black-and-white box” approach to user empowerment with component computing. *Interactive Learning Environments*, *12*(1-2), 27–71.
- Kynigos, C. (2007). Half-baked Logo microworlds as boundary objects in integrated design. *Informatics in Education*, *6*(2), 335–358.
- Papert, S. (1980). *Mindstorms: Children, computers, and powerful ideas*. Basic Books, Inc.
- Papert, S. (2000). What’s the big idea? Towards a pedagogy of idea power. *IBM Systems Journal*, *39*(3-4), 720–729.
- Vergnaud, G. (2009). The Theory of Conceptual Fields. *Human Development*, *52*(2), 83–94.
<http://doi.org/10.1159/000202727>
- Wegerif, R. (2007). *Dialogic education and technology expanding the space of learning*. New York: Springer. Retrieved from <http://site.ebrary.com/id/10197371>
- Yiannoutsou, N., & Mavrikis, M. (2012). Learning how to learn with microworlds: feedback evaluation and help seeking. In C. Kynigos, J. Clayson, & N. Yiannoutsou (Eds.), *Proceedings of Constructionism 2012: Theory Practice and Impact*. (pp. 490–499). Athens, Greece.
- Yiannoutsou, N., Nikitopoulou, S., Kynigos, C., Gueorguiev, I., & Fernandez, J. A. (2016). Activity Plan Template: a mediating tool for supporting learning design with robotics. In *Robotics in Education*. Vienna-Austria: Springer.

9 APPENDIX 1: EVALUATION DOCUMENTS BY SCIENTIX AMBASSADORS

9.1 SCIENTIX AMBASSADOR PROJECT SUPPORT – REVIEW TEMPLATE

Imagine that you would like to implement an educational robotics activity in your class or school and you have searched the ER4STEM repository and have found these ten activities. Please review the ten activities from this perspective. For each activity, please answer three questions:

- Would you implement this activity in your class or school as it is described? Why? Why not? Any cultural aspects?
- Would you implement this activity by adapting it to your class' or school's needs? Why? Why not?
- If you have adapted the activity, would you use the activity plan to describe your version? Or would you use the activity plan to describe a new activity that you have created? Could you please elaborate if the activity plan is clearly structured and described? How should it be so that you use it?

The more detailed the review is on each aspect mentioned (one A4 page per activity plan or even more), the more accessible and usable will future versions of the activity plans be. Please use the template to answer the three questions. You can download this document onto your computer and answer the questions directly. Or you print it and fill in your answers by hand, then scan it. In either case, please send the electronic document with your completed review to lammer@acin.tuwien.ac.at. If you have any questions, you can contact Lara Lammer at the same email address.

Workshop 1a-c:

1. Would you implement this activity in your class or school as it is described? Why? Why not? Any cultural aspects?
2. Would you implement this activity by adapting it to your class' or school's needs? Why? Why not?
3. If you have adapted the activity, would you use the activity plan to describe your version? Could you please elaborate if the activity plan is clearly structured and described?

Workshop 2:

1. Would you implement this activity in your class or school as it is described? Why? Why not? Any cultural aspects?
2. Would you implement this activity by adapting it to your class' or school's needs? Why? Why not?
3. If you have adapted the activity, would you use the activity plan to describe your version? Could you please elaborate if the activity plan is clearly structured and described?

Workshop 3:

1. Would you implement this activity in your class or school as it is described? Why? Why not? Any cultural aspects?
2. Would you implement this activity by adapting it to your class' or school's needs? Why? Why not?
3. If you have adapted the activity, would you use the activity plan to describe your version? Could you please elaborate if the activity plan is clearly structured and described?

Workshop 4:

1. Would you implement this activity in your class or school as it is described? Why? Why not? Any cultural aspects?
2. Would you implement this activity by adapting it to your class' or school's needs? Why? Why not?
3. If you have adapted the activity, would you use the activity plan to describe your version? Could you please elaborate if the activity plan is clearly structured and described?

Workshop 5:

1. Would you implement this activity in your class or school as it is described? Why? Why not? Any cultural aspects?

2. Would you implement this activity by adapting it to your class' or school's needs? Why? Why not?

3. If you have adapted the activity, would you use the activity plan to describe your version? Could you please elaborate if the activity plan is clearly structured and described?

Workshop 6:

1. Would you implement this activity in your class or school as it is described? Why? Why not? Any cultural aspects?

2. Would you implement this activity by adapting it to your class' or school's needs? Why? Why not?

3. If you have adapted the activity, would you use the activity plan to describe your version? Could you please elaborate if the activity plan is clearly structured and described?

Workshop 7:

1. Would you implement this activity in your class or school as it is described? Why? Why not? Any cultural aspects?

2. Would you implement this activity by adapting it to your class' or school's needs? Why? Why not?

3. If you have adapted the activity, would you use the activity plan to describe your version? Could you please elaborate if the activity plan is clearly structured and described?

8. Conference:

1. Would you implement this activity in your class or school as it is described? Why? Why not? Any cultural aspects?
2. Would you implement this activity by adapting it to your class' or school's needs? Why? Why not?
3. If you have adapted the activity, would you use the activity plan to describe your version? Could you please elaborate if the activity plan is clearly structured and described?

9.2 SCIENTIX AMBASSADOR REVIEWS

1st Review: Ivan Derek Primary School Teacher - Bosnia Herzegovina

WORKSHOP 1A-C:

1. Would you implement this activity in your class or school as it is described? Why? Why not? Any cultural aspects?

If I would have an opportunity to implement this kind of activity (my school does not have robots) I would conduct this activity as described. I think that the usage of robots can lead towards better understanding of programming in the schools, pupils have an opportunity to actually see what the program does in real time (I think on movement of robots) so it would demystify programming in classes. In that sense, connection of programming, building the robots and the usage of robots in real life can lead towards emphasizing the importance of STEM among young pupils. Sequential thinking is another thing which I like in this scenario, through this kind of thinking, dividing the problem into smaller parts and through collaboration of students on solving the problem they work on communication, respect each other ideas, develop social skills which are needed in the future.

2. Would you implement this activity by adapting it to your class' or school's needs? Why? Why not?

Yes I would. The basic idea can be used for different pupils, it can be built upon and used as a template for writing the scenarios for different topics, not only for the introduction of robotics in class. It can be adapted for controlling the robots with the usage of sensors and so on.

3. If you have adapted the activity, would you use the activity plan to describe your version? Could you please elaborate if the activity plan is clearly structured and described?

The description of the scenario (domain, objectives, time, materials and artefacts) is clearly described, space and students info is well described. Social orchestration through dividing the students into groups are good idea because collaboration of students will lead towards interaction during the solution – oriented activity. Teacher's role as a mentor not as a lecturer which is oriented towards

developing student's cognitive skills, confidence of students is a great idea. Sequence and description of activities are well structured and explained. Assessment through tests, essays can further develop student's knowledge

WORKSHOP 2:

1. Would you implement this activity in your class or school as it is described? Why? Why not? Any cultural aspects?

I would like to implement this kind of activity in my school, but unfortunately my school does not have financial possibility for implementing this kind of activity.

Teacher's role as a facilitator and consultant for robot construction can lead towards creation of creative thinking skills among students which are needed to fulfill the main goal in this activity. Usage of a Visual Guide for assembling the functional robot will evoke interest in students for creating first robot and contribute to development of self – confidence among students. This activity includes multiple programming environment (Scratch or Snap, Arduino IDE, python and pymata) in order to control the robot which in turn have a result that the students will learn to use this languages what leads towards development of cognitive skills among students. Working in teams, students develop communication and collaboration skills which is needed in their future lives as a future engineers, researchers and responsible citizens.

2. Would you implement this activity by adapting it to your class' or school's needs? Why? Why not?

Unfortunately, I cannot implement this kind of activity in my school because financial reasons – school does not have a possibility to buy ESI CEE set.

3. If you have adapted the activity, would you use the activity plan to describe your version? Could you please elaborate if the activity plan is clearly structured and described?

Activity plan is clearly structured and well described. Objectives are clearly stated but time is, by my opinion a little bit short for this activity. Students need to get to know with different programming environments and I think for this part of activity they need more time (since they do not need any prior knowledge as is stated in activity plan). Social orchestration by dividing the students into groups encourages collaboration between students and not predefined roles of students in group offers possibility for students to shift between roles to find best suited position in group. Teaching and learning procedures for this activity are good elected because the usage of teacher's approaches as a constructionist with elements of instructionism will contribute to the development of discussion, observation and analysis of steps needed to construct robot in each group. Students will be cooperative in order to achieve the main goal.

Sequence and description of activities in each Module is well described and organized and this idea is great for this kind of activity.

WORKSHOP 3:

1. Would you implement this activity in your class or school as it is described? Why? Why not? Any cultural aspects?

This kind of activity couldn't be implemented as it is described in my school. I teach in a primary school and this kind of activity is intended for students who are going into technical schools. Another thing, for completing this activity students need to know C programming environment on higher level (function calls, iteration, selection, variables). Unfortunately, how the Curricula for informatics which is not mandatory subject in schools in my country (Bosnia and Herzegovina) is different from other countries and C is left out in from Curricula.

Students are learning basics from ICT, that's the problem (curricula).

Botball robotic kit is another thing which schools in my country do not possessing.

But, the idea for Botball is great, it could lead towards better understanding of ICT and its application in real life through creation and programming a robot.

2. Would you implement this activity by adapting it to your class' or school's needs? Why? Why not?

I couldn't implement adapted this kind of activity in school where I teach because it is a public school which needs to follow the Curricula for the ICT as it is described in National Curricula. In private primary schools it is different situation because the Curricula for the ICT is a little bit flexible in that case. In public primary schools, for doing this activity, teacher needs to write down and send an official letter to the Ministry of Education and Centre for National Curricula in order to get approval for doing this kind of activity. Also, for doing this activity teacher needs to get funds for the Botball robotic kit from Ministry of Education which is very difficult. Perhaps, if the cooperation between schools and representatives of industry was better, schools could get necessary kits for doing this kind of activity with children.

3. If you have adapted the activity, would you use the activity plan to describe your version? Could you please elaborate if the activity plan is clearly structured and described?

Activity plan for Botball Preparation Workshop is very good structured and described. Building and programming the robot for the competition in Botball by using a step – by – step manual in the group of students which have different roles and choice to select them can create cohesive force between members of the group where everyone is responsible for one part of completing the objective which in turn motivates them to do the task selected best they can. Roles in the group can be programmer, builder and so on. Group created in this manner will induce dialogue and interaction between students. Time provided for this activity for the students of technical school is sufficient because programming the controller in C for them will be challenging but achievable task. Social orchestration predicts 4 teachers for 100 students but I think that one or two more teachers could be better because small number of teachers in that big group could lead to chaos and more teachers which are trouble shooters will lead towards less stress among students when they encounter with the problem. Sequence and description of activities in two – days workshop are clearly and good structured.

WORKSHOP 4:

1. Would you implement this activity in your class or school as it is described? Why? Why not? Any cultural aspects?

Unfortunately, I cannot use this activity plan see answer 1 in Workshop 1a-c,

2. Would you implement this activity by adapting it to your class' or school's needs? Why? Why not?

If I could have a chance to get necessary kit I would adapt this kind of activity for the students in my school. Adopted version of this activity in my case could for a main goal have a creation of autonomous zoomorphic robot. It would be divided into smaller steps needed for the construction of a robot (learning the functionalities of each part, how they will communicate with each other...).

This workshop offers a possibility for connecting the knowledge from different subjects into one whole and that is the part which I like the most. I think that this is a turn towards creation of cross curricular subject which, in my opinion, is the future of education.

3. If you have adapted the activity, would you use the activity plan to describe your version? Could you please elaborate if the activity plan is clearly structured and described?

In this case activity plan is not clearly described. Objective is not fully described, they do not state is the goal of the workshop creation and programming in Arduino autonomous robot or just construction of the legs of zoomorphic robot. My suggestion in this manner is to state clearly main objective of the workshop then divide it to smaller steps. Workshop is intended for the students of different nationalities (plus two pupils suffer from ADD) so I think that the collaborative part (language, knowledge of Arduino) could be a problem (it is not stated which level of common language students possess nor the correspondence of National Curricula for ICT for this countries) so I suggest more time for the workshop. Another thing is the grouping criteria (mixed abilities), it is not stated in which way the abilities of the students will be made – I suggest introductory exam of the students before the workshop in order to get full picture about abilities of the students to create equally “strong” groups. Sequential (three phases five steps) activity plan for designing and programming the robot is a great idea.

WORKSHOP 5:

1. Would you implement this activity in your class or school as it is described? Why? Why not? Any cultural aspects?

See answer 1 in Workshop 1a-c

2. Would you implement this activity by adapting it to your class' or school's needs? Why? Why not?

If I someday get a kit for doing this kind of activity in my school I would use adapted version of this workshop in my school. In my school children learn MS Logo so this kind of activity would be a good after school activity for the deepening the knowledge from subject Informatics and possibility for students to see that the knowledge from classes could be used in the real world. Plan suggests that the students do not need any prior knowledge about the programming in the LEGO NXT and I agree

about this manner. Another thing, students in my school do not use programming environments which are block based like LEGO NXT so this would be a great opportunity for them to see that they can build programs via usage of the blocks instead of writing the code. Adopted version in this manner would implement the knowledge from MS Logo in first day of the workshop (movement of turtle on computer screen) in order to show students that this kind of movement could be done in real world by programming the robot in LEGO NXT.

3. If you have adapted the activity, would you use the activity plan to describe your version? Could you please elaborate if the activity plan is clearly structured and described?

I would use this kind of activity for describing my adopted version of this workshop because it is very good structured, goal and the steps needed to implement this activity are clearly described, they are not difficult for the students with no prior knowledge of programming in the LEGO NXT. In that case students would be encouraged for further exploration of possibilities offered by this kit.

Plan as it is described follows easy steps towards the main goal which is programming the autonomous robot. Time intended for the conducting of activities is very good planned but the teachers who are implementing this kind of activities must be very good informed about the knowledge of English language of the students because they will use electronic material which is on English language. In this manner could be helpful that one student in the group would be “translator”.

My suggestion is to let to students that before they get to know loops that they “play” with other blocks in order to get familiar with the functions of them.

WORKSHOP 6:

1. Would you implement this activity in your class or school as it is described? Why? Why not? Any cultural aspects?

Unfortunately usage of an activity plan as described for the students in that age in my opinion could not be possible. The main goal of the workshop is not clearly stated nor the intended outcomes of the workshop. In my opinion, the activity plan must be more precise described, goal, steps needed...

2. Would you implement this activity by adapting it to your class’ or school’s needs? Why? Why not?

If I could have a chance to get a kit for doing this kind of an activity, I would use adapted version of this scenario for the pupils in my school. Goal of my activity plan could be for an example getting to know the fundamental concepts of robots such as movement, possibilities which are offered from particular robot and so on.

Maybe it would be a good idea to devise a few games which will involve robots in order that the children learn about the robots through the game.

3. If you have adapted the activity, would you use the activity plan to describe your version? Could you please elaborate if the activity plan is clearly structured and described?

Unfortunately this activity plan is not clearly described nor structured. Main objective, as the steps needed to complete the main objective are not clearly stated so it will be very difficult to implement this kind of activity among eight year olds, I think it would be chaotic in this large group of pupils. Regarding this manner I suggest to teachers to state clearly the main objective (for an example controlling the robot through coding) then steps needed (getting to know blocks for movement, loops etc.) for completing it. Also, I suggest more workshops because the students need to familiar with the coding and they need more time for that. Perhaps it could be a great idea on the ending workshop to organize a competition for an example driving the robot through the maze (it could be fun).

WORKSHOP 7:

1. Would you implement this activity in your class or school as it is described? Why? Why not? Any cultural aspects?

Unfortunately I cannot conduct this kind of activity in my school because I do not have necessary kit for doing this activity nor do I have opportunity to visit University with children in order them to see a real robot.

Plan for this activity is very good structured and described and if I had a chance I would conduct this activity as described. Through this activity the students gain much more than the knowledge of robotics, they learn how to plan, how to build the robot which will do specific tasks and built upon demands of the customers, they learning about different areas of robotics, how to behave with different kinds of humans and so on.

In another words, they learn valuable lessons about collaboration, respect for other and knowledge of need of people with different abilities in robotic industry.

2. Would you implement this activity by adapting it to your class' or school's needs? Why? Why not?

In this case I will do a minor adaptation of the activity plan for my school. Just I think that the students which I teach need more time for the second workshop (see answer 1) because they need more time to get to know the materials and the robot parts since they didn't had a chance to see them in real life. Also, there would be a need for more time for learning Arduino since they do not learn it in regular school classes (Curricula).

3. If you have adapted the activity, would you use the activity plan to describe your version? Could you please elaborate if the activity plan is clearly structured and described?

Activity plan is perfectly structured and described. Idea to make a robot from scratch is excellent! Through this activity students will learn that the very complex problem such as building a robot can be solved only through collaboration within the group and by accepting opinions from all members of the group. Also, the children will learn about different areas of robotics and the ways on which they collaborate in order to meet the demands of customers. That's great because in the class there are students who think that the robotics only needs engineers, program developers and scientists and that the skills which they possess (marketing, sales...) are not necessary for robotic industry.

Sequence of activities which are divided into three workshops (Ideation, Prototyping and Evaluation) plus visit to University are clearly described and well structured. The first workshop offers possibility for students to express their ideas which in turn results in development of creativity among them. This workshop is divided into five steps through which the students develop understanding of basic concepts of robotics (Task, Interaction, Morphology, Behavior and Parts) which is necessary for completing the main objective. In the second workshop the students choose in which group they will go (Sales & Marketing, Engineering, HRI, Research & Development, Design) which is a great idea because every student in that case is important, every idea is taken under consideration and not discarded. My suggestion is only to give more time to students in this workshop according to the needs necessary for this workshop. In the finalizing workshop students have a chance to test their robot and reflect on the results which is great because they will get an experiences which are needed for further development of their skills.

CONFERENCE:

1. Would you implement this activity in your class or school as it is described? Why? Why not? Any cultural aspects?

See answer 1 in Workshop 3

Unfortunately I cannot implement this kind of activity in my school (see answer 1 in workshop.....) because students need to know much more programming (I teach in primary public school) and also my school do not possesses necessary kits for doing this kind of activity.

Maybe, simplified version of the Botball could come into consideration (simplified robots for which isn't necessarily possession of knowledge for programming the controller).

Another obstacle is that in Botball tournament can compete only official teams.

2. Would you implement this activity by adapting it to your class' or school's needs? Why? Why not?

See answer 2 in Workshop 3

If I could have an opportunity (necessary kits) I would probably implement this activity in my school.

Idea of using multiple programming languages in order to win the tournament is great, students in that case are connecting the knowledge from different programming environments into one functional whole. Through the competition students are working in teams and improving the collaborative skills, they are deepening the knowledge of English language and other cultures (teams from other countries).

The goal of winning will be a driving force of reaching the limits of their knowledge from robotics, and the acknowledgment of the results from other teams will result with the development of respect towards others ideas.

3. If you have adapted the activity, would you use the activity plan to describe your version? Could you please elaborate if the activity plan is clearly structured and described?

If I could implement this activity, I would use this activity plan for describing mine. The plan is very good structured and can be used as a template for adopted version of this activity. In my case, adopted version could go in the direction for primary schools (programming the controller could be obstacle because that goes beyond programming skills of students in primary schools in my country) by using the robots which do not need a programming the controller.

Side-effect of adopted version of this activity in my case would result in a changing the Curricula for ICT in my country (which is outdated) which would be excellent. Unfortunately, for doing this it is necessary to put a lot of effort from different entities involved into curricular reforms, but I think that can be done if one teacher begins with the this kind of activities others will follow and at the end it will result with the change of whole educational system.

As I was writing in the answers before, activity plan is very good structured and described. I like the most the fact that the students have the same kits, same possibilities for success like the children from other countries. They have a chance to learn from each other's, learn about different cultures and develop their collaborative and language skills.

Another thing which I like in this activity is the fact that there is a lot of prizes, so the efforts what they do during the competition will not be in vain.

2nd Review: Malgorzata Zajackowska Poland

WORKSHOP 2:

1. Would you implement this activity in your class or school as it is described? Why? Why not? Any cultural aspects?

The scenario has been written by the Team. Great job! The contextual domain involves all STBEAM subjects. There are the detailed objectives. The workshop plan provides the development of critical thinking; takes into account the individual ideas of students and then enables the development of thinking in groups.

2. Would you implement this activity by adapting it to your class' or school's needs? Why? Why not?

Yes, I would if were a primary teacher.

Such meetings are always associated with an increase in the results and preparation of good innovative educational practices.

For example:

When students get Visual Guide, they work faster and it is easier for them to construct robots having a visual background. The target audience, students aged 8-12 are still very young. It is a great offer for them.

No prior knowledge needed. Among them may be students with special needs.

At this age students do not work at a steady pace.

3. If you have adapted the activity, would you use the activity plan to describe your version? Could you please elaborate if the activity plan is clearly structured and described?

The authors use methods very appropriate to the goals, both for the instructional intervention and the evaluation of impact on learning. The paper is clearly and carefully written.

WORKSHOP 3:

1. Would you implement this activity in your class or school as it is described? Why? Why not? Any cultural aspects?

We have no experience in organizing such kind of events in my school, but in the cooperation with some schools from the neighborhood it would be possible.

Suppose that we would be able to prepare our students for the tournament (build and program a robot) but a 16-hour-workshop seems to be quite short for us.

According to the scenario the target audience – students aged 15-18 – don't need any prior knowledge. Why don't we ask them to work online with their Austrian peers who do a separate Botball workshop and take part in the regional tournament.

2. Would you implement this activity by adapting it to your class' or school's needs? Why? Why not?

There is a detailed description of Workshop Day 1. It consists of four phases and one pre-phase. There is nothing about different abilities, more skillful students working fast etc. In this scenario everyone is equal but it is not true.

Students could be divided into less and more advanced groups. The ones who use the robotic set for the first time need much more attention and individual support. They could be cheered by tutors.

Workshop Day 2 consists of four phases. The organizers explain the competition task which is new for participants and let them think about a new strategy. Again, they work in different ways, depending on their personal skills and for this reason need completely different support.

3. If you have adapted the activity, would you use the activity plan to describe your version? Could you please elaborate if the activity plan is clearly structured and described?

The workshop is for up to 100 students. Having more space we could teach more students during this workshop.

The author provides sufficient detail to replicate and evaluate. The paper is clearly and carefully written.

WORKSHOP 4:

1. Would you implement this activity in your class or school as it is described? Why? Why not? Any cultural aspects?

The work appeals to a target audience interested in ARDUINO programming.

The workshop gathers the youth, two groups aged 15-17. This age range is very demanding. Young people ask a lot of questions and try to find new solutions. The group 1 (10 students) involved in Arduino programming will (they know what Arduino is and why they'd want to use it) help the others (group 2 – 10 students).

There are students from different countries in two groups. We have to predict their behavior or even specify how to resolve conflicts. How do we know how to divide our students if we do not work with them on a daily basis? There is no information about it in 2.1.

The international workshop is a new challenge for all involved taking into account all the aspects of such kind of meetings.

There are two special needs students (ADD). Which group do they belong to? How advanced are they in programming? etc. If we assume the participation of mixed ability international students, we need to describe them, their duties in detail in the scenario.

2. Would you implement this activity by adapting it to your class' or school's needs? Why? Why not?

Ad. 6 Sequence and description

The introduction does not provide different levels of work. It would be better to know at the beginning that 10 out of 20 students are experts on the electronic part... and what their duties are.

The phase 1 is well described but the phase 2 only mentioned.

3. If you have adapted the activity, would you use the activity plan to describe your version? Could you please elaborate if the activity plan is clearly structured and described?

The paper is almost clearly and carefully written.

The authors (UoA) use methods appropriate to the goals, for the instructional intervention but do not provide sufficient details to evaluate the workshop, the impact on learning.

The evaluation phase is a very important part of the Arduino workshop. How does it work? We do not know. How is the author going to use the types of formative and summative assessment? Still unknown.

WORKSHOP 5:

1. Would you implement this activity in your class or school as it is described? Why? Why not? Any cultural aspects?

Yes, I would.

The workshop with programming in LEGO NXT gives the equal chance for boys and girls (mixed gender) to work in small groups. No or little knowledge of Lego technology is needed. Group leaders will be able to find new solutions in the cooperation with other groups. The educational process does not limit itself to the members of one team what is really important.

2. Would you implement this activity by adapting it to your class' or school's needs? Why? Why not?

Teaching and learning procedures are clearly introduced. The teachers as co-researchers will be more involved in programming. They have decision-making authority.

All phases of the workshop are well described. There is no problem in adopting the scenario.

The content can be directly applied by classroom instructors or curriculum designers.

3. If you have adapted the activity, would you use the activity plan to describe your version? Could you please elaborate if the activity plan is clearly structured and described?

The work appeals to a target audience interested in LEGO NXT programming.

The author uses methods appropriate to the goals, both for the instructional intervention and the evaluation of impact on learning. The author provides sufficient detail to replicate and evaluate. The paper is clearly and carefully written.

WORKSHOP 6:

1. Would you implement this activity in your class or school as it is described? Why? Why not? Any cultural aspects?

I generally appreciate a draft of the Malta Workshop.

The title is very important. Knowing the title of the workshop, it would be easier to review the design of the project.

There are no research questions and some objectives, materials (etc.) should be defined.

At this stage it is difficult to predict their meanings and the impacts of the workshop.

2. Would you implement this activity by adapting it to your class' or school's needs? Why? Why not?

There are a lot of innovative schools that are bringing coding and STEM to life with Dash and Dot. Dash is a child's first robot. Dot is the best introduction to coding and robotics.

Suppose a new kit Dash and Dot will be very useful.

The issue is that the activity has not been completed yet.

3. If you have adapted the activity, would you use the activity plan to describe your version? Could you please elaborate if the activity plan is clearly structured and described?

The workshop could be a little longer than four hours if we want the young participants to learn (create simple instructions in mini programming)

ad. 2 Space and Students info: Robots could be very useful for special needs students. They help them overcome some difficulties.

It's a good idea to finish the session in a non-traditional way using Plickers or Kahoot.it

Plickers integrate seamlessly into the way we teach, engage all in critical thinking (formative assesment). Are they enough to evaluate the event? What about teacher/parent feedback survey material?

WORKSHOP 7:

1. Would you implement this activity in your class or school as it is described? Why? Why not? Any cultural aspects?

Yes, of course. I would implement this activity in school. The title of this workshop suggests that it brings something to life. The rich conextual domain (STBEAM) and well-formulated learning objectives make the workshop exciting as well as interesting. The social and action related goals take into account different personalities and their diverse contribution to the common project.

The work addresses a significant problem. Mattie robot in different shapes helps children develop creativity.

2. Would you implement this activity by adapting it to your class' or school's needs? Why? Why not?

Taking into account the target audience aged 10-14, we could propose them a robot in a more advance shape, appropriate to their needs/suggestions or just ask learners to design new heroes. It would be interesting to check students' favourites in this field comparing the results between some countries. Maybe one workshop at the university is not enough and the organizers will give a chance for learners to meet professionals in their real workplace, even one more time.

I absolutely agree that big groups of students require more tutors. I would like you to consider some meetings in smaller groups to reach the social and action related goals not only subject ones, for

example. It will be easier to choose the right subject, even change into another one because most students aged 10-14 have no preferences.

3. If you have adapted the activity, would you use the activity plan to describe your version? Could you please elaborate if the activity plan is clearly structured and described?

This plan is full of ideas, very innovative featuring new methodology.

Workshop 1: Ideation and Workshop 2 Prototyping, both professionally planned and described. Congratulations.

The assessment procedures could not be only for teachers and students. Schools have a responsibility to report assessment results to parents in a way that will assist the learning process and parents' understanding. Feedback on student work should be sufficiently timely to allow improvement where necessary. Use of handheld computing devices can help in this field. What about self assessment? Students making judgments about their own learning, both in relation to their process of learning and its outcomes – it also brings a new value to the project. The paper adheres to excellent standards of style, usage, and composition

CONFERENCE:

1. Would you implement this activity in your class or school as it is described? Why? Why not? Any cultural aspects?

I would like to extend my congratulations to the authors and organizers of the conference. 'Today's Botball kids are tomorrow's scientists'. Botball is good for middle and high school students, for team-oriented robotics competitions.

Although one-week conference seems quite long. Five working days would be enough. Very busy working days, ten hours per day.

2. Would you implement this activity by adapting it to your class' or school's needs? Why? Why not?

Students learn-by-doing and gather teamwork experience. Thanks to Botball trusted advisers, teachers know how to use robotics in their classrooms, in curriculum. I suppose that the game will involve a lot of European students and the information about the competition will reach almost every school.

Yes, I would implement this in school.

It's very important to exchange ideas and improve collaborative skills. The conference opens minds for the nearest future.

3. If you have adapted the activity, would you use the activity plan to describe your version? Could you please elaborate if the activity plan is clearly structured and described?

The paper is clearly written.

The target audience of ECER conference should include the youth with a little programming skills to disseminate/promote Robotics among teenagers (future scientists). While grouping, consider to take skillful programming students as supervisors. It will help less advanced overcome some difficulties in programming (a new role of a student in 3.3 Interaction). Sharing knowledge among students by students improves the learning process.

The authors (PRIA) use methods appropriate to the goals, for the instructional intervention but do not provide sufficient details to evaluate the conference, the impact on learning.

3rd Review: Jennie Malmberg - Sweden

WORKSHOP 1A-C:

1. Would you implement this activity in your class or school as it is described? Why? Why not? Any cultural aspects?

Yes:

These activities has a good approach with an introduction and the different phases. There is a gradual increase in the severity and the students learn by exploring. 1a –c are good activities ended with a more creative part of accounting.

It's good that the students are working in pairs, personally I think the teacher should make the pairs. The teacher is a mentor and needs to have a good knowledge of how to assemble a robot and how to program the Arduino.

2. Would you implement this activity by adapting it to your class' or school's needs? Why? Why not?

Yes, if there is a teachers guide or movie that will help the teacher to start.

It says that it requires zero prior knowledge of the students but the teacher needs knowledge of Arduino and Scratch, it should be specified.

I have a wish that 1a - b could be a way to get more teachers to get into programming in Swedish schools, programming is not part of our curriculum. If there were a manual for teachers, and pictures of the various parts that's included, some teachers would probably dare to undertake these activities.

3. If you have adapted the activity, would you use the activity plan to describe your version? Could you please elaborate if the activity plan is clearly structured and described?

I have a wish that 1a - b could be a way to get more teachers to get into programming in Swedish schools and other countries, programming is not part of our curriculum. If there were a manual for

teachers, and pictures of the various parts that's included, some teachers would probably dare to undertake these activities. A good start!

The teacher is a mentor and needs to have a good knowledge of how to assemble a robot and how to program the Arduino.

An introduction to the Arduino:

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=CqrQmQqpHXc>

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=E6KwXYmMiak>

WORKSHOP 2:

1. Would you implement this activity in your class or school as it is described? Why? Why not? Any cultural aspects?

Yes:

Good approach of this activity, the time is sufficient.

Good rules, focus on creativity and collaboration.

Good that there are different options specified.

2. Would you implement this activity by adapting it to your class' or school's needs? Why? Why not?

In Sweden, we have no assistants and classes are approximately 30 students. This could be a problem to implement the activity.

3. If you have adapted the activity, would you use the activity plan to describe your version? Could you please elaborate if the activity plan is clearly structured and described?

Yes, just make the groups with less numbers of students.

Bulgarian students(2.1.3)? Other nationalities may well also implement it?

The structure is good.

WORKSHOP 3:

1. Would you implement this activity in your class or school as it is described? Why? Why not? Any cultural aspects?

Yes:

- Good approach of this activity, the time is sufficient.

- Good rules, focus on creativity and collaboration.
- Good that there are lesson plans for teachers.
- Good that there is “step by step” instructions for the students with zero experience.
- The structure is good, the phases content increases gradually.

Cultural aspects, see the next question.

2. Would you implement this activity by adapting it to your class’ or school’s needs? Why? Why not?

Yes, by not making it as a competition. By changing the element of competition during day two to a “mission” with clear instructions. Swedish students are not used to competitive element and I have experienced that they become stressed and their creativity is blocked.

3. If you have adapted the activity, would you use the activity plan to describe your version? Could you please elaborate if the activity plan is clearly structured and described?

The structure is good.

WORKSHOP 4:

1. Would you implement this activity in your class or school as it is described? Why? Why not? Any cultural aspects?

Yes, the activity is good, the level of difficulty is increased by the various phases. There is a good educational idea that half the group of the students are experts.

I would like to read the slides mentioned in 1.4.4, in order to provide additional feedback.

2. Would you implement this activity by adapting it to your class’ or school’s needs? Why? Why not?

No: Adaption the activity is good, the level of difficulty is increased by the various phases.

Yes: Changes need to be made if you do not have access to students who can act experts. But I think you can find experts among students who are older at your school.

3. If you have adapted the activity, would you use the activity plan to describe your version? Could you please elaborate if the activity plan is clearly structured and described?

The structure is good.

WORKSHOP 5:

1. Would you implement this activity in your class or school as it is described? Why? Why not? Any cultural aspects?

Yes:

- Good approach of this activity, the time is sufficient.
- Good rules, focus on creativity and collaboration.
- Good that there are “active sheets” for the students.
- The structure is good, the phases content increases gradually

(intro. - sequential programming – loops – switch)

2. Would you implement this activity by adapting it to your class’ or school’s needs? Why? Why not?

Yes, no adapting is needed.

3. If you have adapted the activity, would you use the activity plan to describe your version? Could you please elaborate if the activity plan is clearly structured and described?

The structure is good.

WORKSHOP 6:

1. Would you implement this activity in your class or school as it is described? Why? Why not? Any cultural aspects?

Yes:

Dash and Dot is a very good kit to introduce programming on the younger children.

Great introduction with films on various robots.

Good structure on the activity.

Use of some of the finished assignments that come with the kit?

2. Would you implement this activity by adapting it to your class’ or school’s needs? Why? Why not?

Yes

A good activity that introduces programming through play.

3. If you have adapted the activity, would you use the activity plan to describe your version? Could you please elaborate if the activity plan is clearly structured and described?

When the movies from Youtube (activity 1 & 2) and the task in activity 3 are specified it's clearly described.

WORKSHOP 7:

1. Would you implement this activity in your class or school as it is described? Why? Why not? Any cultural aspects?

Good approach with the technical process and marketing. A longer project that will last for one semester.

Good activity that highlight that all intelligences are complementary.

Good that the activity also pressing that communication is important.

Good that it is possible to carry out the activity with Arduino.

2. Would you implement this activity by adapting it to your class' or school's needs? Why? Why not?

Yes, adaptations.

3. If you have adapted the activity, would you use the activity plan to describe your version? Could you please elaborate if the activity plan is clearly structured and described?

What I think is unclear is the number of hours, 300 minutes for an entire semester(1.3.1)?

During the workshop 4 mentioned the three laws of robotics. They should be specified.

CONFERENCE:

1. Would you implement this activity in your class or school as it is described? Why? Why not? Any cultural aspects?

Good that the conference has the preparatory activity and that students receive feedback on their work.

2. Would you implement this activity by adapting it to your class' or school's needs? Why? Why not?

I would gladly shared with my students if I was sure what was expected of me and my students before the conference. It is a good approach.

3. If you have adapted the activity, would you use the activity plan to describe your version? Could you please elaborate if the activity plan is clearly structured and described?

I think it's unclear what more in addition to their scientific paper to be prepared. Is it just the competition that takes place during the conference?

4th Review: Thorbjørn Hartelius – Denmark

WORKSHOP 1A-C:

1. Would you implement this activity in your class or school as it is described? Why? Why not? Any cultural aspects?

1.a - I would not implement this activity as described. It lacks the help of figures/pictures or animations to teachers not familiar with robotics and technology. Also the fact that several parts must be purchased before is a complication to begin with.

But the actual guidance as described is well written and easy to follow - here in particular rules and helpful notes.

The grid in how the teacher should interact and help the students is unnecessary in Denmark as the teacher should already be fully qualified to do so - what is the main challenge here (for a Danish teacher) is the technology/robotics skills. Either it will be conducted by a Science/technology teacher already familiar with maker tech or a teacher eager to learn new things and willing to “risk” learning by him/her self along with the students.

So in order to work in Denmark - more focus must be put on an easy guidance into how -to-do with the robot - just a short video would do.

1.b - I would implement this activity and would like to do it with my own classes as soon as possible - this is more clear cut than 1.a - and easier to take on as a teacher.

This activity would work with science classes or after-school activity or in a club where the students have more time to go deeper into the activity and really understand the context. Again for teachers not familiar with robotics and technology it lacks the guidance of visible material - such as videos on how to do it - drawings or pictures etc. This would make it easier for teachers with different subject to take this activity to practice and it would be typical for a Danish teacher to withdraw this also in language sessions or art classes. The paper as it is presented is too academic for Danish teachers and students. And therefore we would turn to some of the many many Danish platforms that offer alternative activities similar to this.

1.c - This activity would be easy to implement as we already have similar activities in the Danish school system - but we would do this for the age group of 12 - 15 years old students as 15-18 aged Danish students would leave the primary/secondary school (which in Denmark is together in one place) and this would be high school. In Danish high schools this activity would already be known to the students and has been trained both with language teachers and science/math teachers - but this activity is well written and easy to start up with in our school system.

2. Would you implement this activity by adapting it to your class' or school's needs? Why? Why not?

- Would certainly work with an adaption because in Denmark we already do these kind of competitions but they would be Lego oriented or within a Maker/FabLab environment without being hosted by a single product manufacturer.
- In Denmark we do not have time to set up a whole week to this but would do it in two or three double-lesson-modules.
- Also it would not be possible in all classes to have two tutors as the teacher work alone without an assistant to help. But by coordinating it with more classes or classteams it could be done easily.

1.b - It would work well in my school and my classes but lack the visible / audio guides. It needs to be translated into Danish and it needs to take on the Visible learning targets implemented by the Danish educational department for each subject in our schoolsystem. Otherwise teachers would not use the time for the activity.

1.c - If I have to take on this activity in my classes or at my school - I would have to change the description and take out the first part until paragraph 5 - from there the description is well suited and functional for Danish teachers - if translated into Danish and followed up with modern digital material - such as a website / channel on youtube or similar - it is too academic to take into our classes - we already use digital material and visual learning environments.

3. If you have adapted the activity, would you use the activity plan to describe your version? Could you please elaborate if the activity plan is clearly structured and described?

Yes the activity plan could be used - but again the attention in Denmark and the main focus would be on the actual physical how-to - the introduction, the guidance of the students and the evaluation part would already be known to all teachers and therefore implemented.

Not all teachers would take on the task if the paper would not be translated into Danish.

In Denmark we have already many facilities within the area of robotics and technology so in order for any Danish teacher to fully take on these activities it would have to be in Danish.

We also have Visible learning targets within each subject and the activity plan should clearly describe witch Visible learning targets or competences within the subject - the student would come across and gain knowledge about.

It is stated in the activity plan that mathematic is part of this - but it would purely be a fraction and not something the students would take into consideration and learn much from - the focus on art and written/telling a story must also be pinned out to the students - in the way that it will be clear for each class what they learn and gain from this activity.

1.b - the activity plan is well written and could be used by Danish teachers as it is - but again pictures/drawings as guidance and even visible help as video and audio would be necessary in order to draw Danish teachers attention - they would search for Danish material and activities otherwise.

1.c - as described earlier - it needs to be digitalized, visual with audio etc. for Danish teachers to implement - and focus on more subjects - maybe with more math exercises - would be better for this age-group. But it would work if translated and done modern.

WORKSHOP 2:

1. Would you implement this activity in your class or school as it is described? Why? Why not? Any cultural aspects?

I would very much like to take on this activity and implement it. It is well written, clear in its instructions and has a direct line to follow from start to end.

Again for a Danish culture of learning - both teachers and students it would need to be digitalized and set up with visible guides - video and audio material - and to be able to stand out in Denmark it needs to have a pleasurable design - and be translated into Danish - otherwise Danish teachers would take on Danish material as we have many platforms for similar types of activities.

What I like in this activity plan is the well-written descriptions on how the student will gain knowledge and acquire new competences in coding and technology.

2. Would you implement this activity by adapting it to your class' or school's needs? Why? Why not?

As stated above - yes I would implement it with the changes stated above - I think my students has already done these activities and they are moving on - but these kind of activities and as described here in the plan I can use it for follow ups and sublimates in order to check if my students remember and uses their already acquired skill from earlier teachings.

We have laptops and iPads for each student so it would be easy to take on this task.

3. If you have adapted the activity, would you use the activity plan to describe your version? Could you please elaborate if the activity plan is clearly structured and described?

I would use the activity as described - but I would not need the description in details until the lesson plan and the reflections described and the evaluation - all the primary stuff I would leave out - a Danish teacher would know that it had solid background and then again we would need to put in the visible learning targets from the Danish educational ministry department for each subject included in the activity.

WORKSHOP 3:

1. Would you implement this activity in your class or school as it is described? Why? Why not? Any cultural aspects?

The activity plan - especially the workshop plan is very clear and well written and I would definitely use it in my class - but again in Denmark we would lower the age of the students and implement such an activity to students aged 13-16

It is very easy to follow and would suit the Danish teachers very well

2. Would you implement this activity by adapting it to your class' or school's needs? Why? Why not?

The description plan is well written -especially the workshop parts - but for Danish students and teachers it needs to be digitalized and followed up by visual guides - especially video formats- and again the form is too academic for Danish teachers - there must be more visual designs and pictures/drawings and again it must be translated into Danish.

3. If you have adapted the activity, would you use the activity plan to describe your version? Could you please elaborate if the activity plan is clearly structured and described?

The activity plan is clearly structured and the description of the workshops is very good. It is easy to follow and clear to all what is necessary for both students and teachers.

The focus on collaborative work and teamwork for students will make many Danish teachers choose this activity as it is great for this purpose.

WORKSHOP 4:

1. Would you implement this activity in your class or school as it is described? Why? Why not? Any cultural aspects?

This activity is too academic in its presentation for Danish teachers and students. The activity itself is very good and could easily be translated and performed in Danish school classes. - We would use students aged 13-16 as they have already gained knowledge of Arduino if they have had fablab classes.

But this activity plan lacks any help to teachers not familiar with Arduino - it must be followed up by guides in form of video and audio material for Danish teachers to use this.

The fact that some students in this activity suffers from ADD would make it very - very interesting for Danish teachers - IF followed up by specific helpful notes on what went well and what to pay extra attention to - or as an evaluation - what these students gained and learned from this activity. - It lacks from this paper.

2. Would you implement this activity by adapting it to your class' or school's needs? Why? Why not?

Not I would not use it - it would need adaption and a whole bunch of helpful notes and guides - again it is too academic and not going deep enough in the description of how-to.

3. If you have adapted the activity, would you use the activity plan to describe your version? Could you please elaborate if the activity plan is clearly structured and described?

The activity plan is not fulfilling - it lacks deeper thoughts and helpful notes especially if you are not already familiar with Arduino - in Denmark it would be suited for aged 13-16 and could be interesting for Danish teachers if focus had been on the students with ADD and evaluation on their progress in the activity.

WORKSHOP 5:

1. Would you implement this activity in your class or school as it is described? Why? Why not? Any cultural aspects?

This activity would suit my class and school very well - as we already work with these kind of assignments / activities - it could be functional and easy to implement in our culture.

The maker element is high and should be presented to the students so they know that they gain competences in this area.

It should be more thorough in its description of each lesson - again drawings, pictures, designs, video, audio would help Danish teachers choosing this activity instead of other local ones.

2. Would you implement this activity by adapting it to your class' or school's needs? Why? Why not?

It could be done in Danish classes without adaption - because it is not a very difficult activity - in Denmark it could be done by the younger students also - from 8 - 16 years - the collaboration and working together is great features in this activity.

3. If you have adapted the activity, would you use the activity plan to describe your version? Could you please elaborate if the activity plan is clearly structured and described?

In Denmark we would off course use Teachers reflections - but in most cases Danish students would be taught to student reflect after each activity - but otherwise it is a very nice activity that needs more depth and more digital design and guides in order to be taken on by Danish teachers.

WORKSHOP 6:

1. Would you implement this activity in your class or school as it is described? Why? Why not? Any cultural aspects?

The activity as described in the lesson-plan could easily be implemented as such. The walkthrough for the lessons are easy to follow and gives primary students a good introduction to robotics - but there is no written information on how to do the programming and coding. The focus here is the introduction of the robots to the children and use of you-tube videos for creating a basic pre-understanding of the subject in the minds of the students.

There are many missing parts in this activity plan as presented here.

Lots of - "to be defined" - so the grid is not finished and the team behind it has not completed their thoughts in writing.

2. Would you implement this activity by adapting it to your class' or school's needs? Why? Why not?

I could take the activity plan and implement it directly if I have the necessary Dash and Dot robotkits - so any school, class or teacher already in possession of the Dash and Dot would be able to follow the lesson-plan - but as the plan lacks sufficient helpful notes - you must adapt quite a lot - for instance you have to find videos on you-tube preferable in your own language as it is for primary students -

and you have to make up the introduction to robots by yourself - as there is no help guide here you also must be able to program the Dash and Dot and let the young learners do it afterwards.

It could be done with many types of digital “toys” such as Sphero, Lego Mindstorm, Sparki, Makey-Makey, Little Bits etc. - there are so many “toys” on the market that you do have to choose from your schools financial achievements - do you have the money to buy Dash and Dot - and would you use the money to buy less expensive materials. So each teacher must adapt here and choose for themselves - and their by maybe it would be just as easy to make up your own activity plan and not follow this one.

3. If you have adapted the activity, would you use the activity plan to describe your version? Could you please elaborate if the activity plan is clearly structured and described?

The lesson plan as described lacks the guidance for teachers not familiar with Dash and Dot and not familiar with programming or coding - there should be links or helpful notes for these areas - video material - etc.

This plan is fine for the first introduction for the students - but it could go further and add more digital skills and thereby push the learning levels for each students even more - the bar is not raised very high here - which in many cases also could be nice because the rate of success for each student will be very high - likely.

WORKSHOP 7:

1. Would you implement this activity in your class or school as it is described? Why? Why not? Any cultural aspects?

Yes I would implement this activity in my school. And it could very easily be taken into the classroom as described. But the part with the visit to the university lab and the introduction to the robot would of course have to be replaced - I will explain in question 2.

But this activity is great because it involves the entire class and it starts with giving the students an understanding of how different groups in a company collaborates. The whole idea of collaboration and teamwork is great in this activity. And very well suited for Danish teachers and students.

The time frame will have to be adjusted for each class and needs to fit the school activity plans. But the lesson plan and helpful notes for each group is very well written and easy to follow as such.

Especially the small notes that the teachers saw during the project - like the group who gained knowledge and help from a students with downs syndrome - and the notifications on larger groups creating chaos but could work with more tutors.

The first part with having the students work with clay is also very nice - because it makes the whole activity meaningful and complete for the students - and also it helps implement each students special learning competence - some students learn by listening, some by writing, some by doing etc.

2. Would you implement this activity by adapting it to your class' or school's needs? Why? Why not?

This activity needs to be adapted here in Denmark - to each class, because teachers work alone - we do not have an assistant to help, so we must work out how to get that "extra tutor", it could work with having older students helping younger students - and the time frame must be adapted to suit each schools activity plan.

Not having the university lab and the robot - it means everyone must adapt this to the facilities in your city. Here in Aarhus we would use the FabLab or Center For learning and visit them or they would come to us at the school and start the project - we have many different robots that we could let the students try out and research before starting the activity. We could use Sphero, Sparki, MakeyMakey, LittleBits, Lego Mindstorm, Rasperry Pi's, Dash and Dots, Arduinos, - so that the students would have come across different robots to gain a pre-understanding beforehand.

In the evaluation I think we would have a team of students in charge of video-production - making small films alongside, and at the end clipping a movie as a product showing the entire process of each team - specially with focus how they communicate and collaborate together. This film would be shown at the end and could be followed up by the evaluation forms already explained in the activity plan.

3. If you have adapted the activity, would you use the activity plan to describe your version? Could you please elaborate if the activity plan is clearly structured and described?

The activity plan is very fulfilling here - for Danish teachers it is not necessary with the first parts - but the explanations of how the groups work, the helpful notes, the lesson-plan and the evaluation will work well.

The top part is too academic and will work only if there must be a fixed form for all activity plans within the database.

There must be more focus on designs, pictures, drawings etc. - otherwise Danish teachers would choose local/national material.

CONFERENCE:

1. Would you implement this activity in your class or school as it is described? Why? Why not? Any cultural aspects?

This paper is clearly too academic for Danish teachers and students and would need to be formed as a competition poster - or a contest for teachers here in dk to take on. We already do legoleague and different forms of competitions. No school could use 10 hours a day for a week on such a project - not in Denmark. It would need to be adapted to younger students.

The written forms of competitions will work and could be suited for ours class and school and could be adapted for use.

2. Would you implement this activity by adapting it to your class' or school's needs? Why? Why not?

It could be adapted into a full day workshop with students from different schools either locally or national - it could be done with classes working on robots and creating their own robots for a period of maybe 2 lessons a week for four weeks and end up with a competition day.

The activities will work and could be used directly following the written material

3. If you have adapted the activity, would you use the activity plan to describe your version? Could you please elaborate if the activity plan is clearly structured and described?

The form in part 6 is well written and could be used well - in Denmark the part of Awards would not be used other by companies - as the school system don't use these types of rewarding individual students - more focus would be on collaboration and teamwork and on how each team solved the technical difficulties.

5th Review: Zuzana Christozova – Slovakia

WORKSHOP 1A-C:

1. Would you implement this activity in your class or school as it is described? Why? Why not? Any cultural aspects?

Workshop 1a

- Yes, I would implement this activity as it is described.
- The phases: Understanding, Exploration, Conceptualization a Conclusion

are methodologically and substantively correct and logical.

- The Explaining the role of sensors and comparison with the sense organs of man is fine.
- The basics of programming of robots create sequences of commands to move the robot forward and backward, rotation of a robot follow a prescribed trajectory.
- The independent task of solving and presentation of design solutions through “story” and “story presentation” is an important element for feedback for all participants of the workshop.
- I like the idea: “Possible changes in the workshop would be to give to each group colored paper, glue and some sticks so they can dress the robot up for their story telling part.”

Workshop 1b

- Yes, I would implement this activity as it is described.
- The Phases: Understanding, Understanding, Exploration, Conceptualization a Conclusion are methodologically and substantively correct and logical.
- The presentation truth Story design, Story rehearsal, Story presentation is inspiring.

Workshop 1c

- Yes, I would implement this activity as it is described.
- The Phases: Understanding, Understanding, Exploration, Conceptualization a Conclusion are methodologically and substantively correct and logical.

2. Would you implement this activity by adapting it to your class' or school's needs? Why? Why not?

Workshop 1a, Workshop 1b, Workshop 1c

- This activity is absolutely suitable for the age group.
- I would use it within hours Applied Informatics, Programming , Robotics...
- It can be classified as a work within the extra-curricular activities.

3. If you have adapted the activity, would you use the activity plan to describe your version? Could you please elaborate if the activity plan is clearly structured and described?

Workshop 1a , Workshop 1b, Workshop 1c

- I recommend to prepare a teacher's manual, it is important to encourage and help teachers get started with robotics.
- The activity plan is clearly described and structured.
- Motivational and creative approach in teaching of robotics.
- Correct didactics and learning approaches.
- I recommend creating electronic multimedia database of solved tasks.

WORKSHOP 2:

TITLE: Practical Educational Robotics Workshop

Author: ESI CEE Team: Ivaylo Gueorguiev with the support and direct contribution of Pavel Varbanova, Petar Sharkov, Prof. Galina Momcheva, Dr. George Sharkov, Prof. Maria Nisheva, Christina Todorova and Georgi Georgiev.

1. Would you implement this activity in your class or school as it is described? Why? Why not? Any cultural aspects?

- Yes, I would try to implement this activity in my class.
- It is very important, that the students have a possibility to use student's workbook and manual: „Visual Guide how to construct the robot; tasks and Illustrations“.
- Similarly, teachers have as well the opportunity to use Teacher's instruction book and manual: „Manuals How to connect and program the Robot“.

- I like the
 - aim of the workshop - building competitiveness,
 - rules (Everybody listen to the others and respect their ideas, No direct competition, Lets cooperate and have fun, Questions and strange ideas are highly encouraged, The researchers are facilitators and friends – everybody can argue with them regarding, The content but not regarding the discipline).
- 2. Would you implement this activity by adapting it to your class' or school's needs? Why? Why not?

- I would try to implement this activity in my class.
- I like platform, methodology and structure of the workshops.
- I like variable structure of workshop
- Module 1 Introduction and pre-evaluation (1/2 hour)
- Module 2 What is a robot (1/2 – 1 hour)
- Module 3 Construction (1-2 hours)
- Module 4 Robot's touch (1-2hours)
- Module 5 Let's imagine... (2 hours).
- Module 6 Programming (2-3 hours)
- Module 7 Evaluation (1 hour).

3. If you have adapted the activity, would you use the activity plan to describe your version? Could you please elaborate if the activity plan is clearly structured and described?

- I miss quantitative assessment.
- I think that robotics should be part of the curriculum of technical schools.
- An evaluation is still in the plan "we test".
- Workshops are most useful when the subject and may be used in the target group.
- We are in the phase of introducing robotics into the beginnings of education in primary schools and secondary schools, but we should think about quantitative assessment.

WORKSHOP 3:

TITLE: ECER-Botball-Preparation-Workshop

Author: Lisa Vittori

1. Would you implement this activity in your class or school as it is described? Why? Why not? Any cultural aspects?

- Yes, I would implement this activity in my class.
- This 2 days workshop has a good structure and is suitable for students aged 15 -18 years.
- It is useful that students have manual for the controller, the sensors and motors.
- It is good that the students have instructions for building first drivable robot.
- It is very important, that the teacher has their instructions and manual.

2. Would you implement this activity by adapting it to your class' or school's needs? Why? Why not?

- I would like to implement this workshop in technical school days.
- I would organized a summer school for students
- I have a subject about robotics with similar content and structure in my school.
- The sequence of activities (Introduction, first prototype, programming principles-simple movements, complex programming structures - using sensors, competition setup, Gather experience with different robotic parts, Workshop evaluation) is right.
- Programming language C is suitable.
- It is important that, the teacher has a possibility to discuss and reflect students' solutions (description of a situation, a construct or an ideas of others, to understand and /or to implement, provision of solutions to problems, provision of alternatives if a dead end is reached revision of other's constructs and ideas, identification of problems, challenge of ideas, sharing of resources, provision of ideas towards improving an existing construct or initial idea).

3. If you have adapted the activity, would you use the activity plan to describe your version? Could you please elaborate if the activity plan is clearly structured and described?

- The activity plan is clearly described and structured.
- Motivational and creative approach in teaching of robotics.
- Correct didactics and learning approaches.
- Perhaps it is a good supplement educational video material with the solution of tasks (teacher workshops slides).
- I recommend creating electronic multimedia database of solved tasks.
- It is good workshop for booth ball tournament.
- I use similar activity as extracurricular activity for preparation of my students for FLL (2 hours a week).

- I use similar activity in curricular activity as project-based learning.
- The student explain their projects as a part in the examination.
- My students prepare videos of solved tasks.

WORKSHOP 4:

TITLE: A ROBOTIC INSECT (ZOOMORPHIC)

Author: UoA

1. Would you implement this activity in your class or school as it is described? Why? Why not? Any cultural aspects?

- Yes, I would implement this activity.
- To design robots it is essential that they are inspired by the construction of the world of animals, humans and insects.
- Very interesting is the dialogue with children.
- Duration of activity is appropriate.
- It is important Student's workbook and manual(use a manual with step-by-step instructions for the, electronic and programming part) and Teacher's instruction book and manual(three incisive stages and five steps for the first two stages using workshop's slides).
- Sequence and description of activities (Pre-Phase : introduction, Phase 1: Group formulation – "What is going to occur concerning the construction?"
- Step 1 – Robot Task ("assignment"),
- Step 2 – Robot Interaction,
- Step 3 – Robot Morphology ("looks and materials",
- Step 4 – Robot Behavior,
- Step 5 – Robot Parts) are right.
- I like idea from Step 2 " Real robots are highly complex and designed by a team of experts from different disciplines (designers, human-robot- interaction experts, programmers, engineers, etc.)".
- Time duration is adequate.

2. Would you implement this activity by adapting it to your class' or school's needs? Why? Why not?

- Yes, I would implement this activity.
- I like inspiration from the world of insects, drones are now perspective.

3. If you have adapted the activity, would you use the activity plan to describe your version? Could you please elaborate if the activity plan is clearly structured and described?

- The activity plan is clearly described and structured.
- Motivational and creative approach in teaching of robotics.

WORKSHOP 5:

Introducing programming structures using LEGO NXT.

Author: UoA.

1. Would you implement this activity in your class or school as it is described? Why? Why not? Any cultural aspects?

- Yes I would implement this activity as it is described.
- Sequence and description of activities (Phase 1: Introduction and experimentation, Phase 2: Sequential programming, Phase 3: Using loops, Phase 4: Giving “smart” behavior: the usage of selection/switch blocks, Phase 5: Feedback and evaluation) are right.
- I like the short informal open interviews from students that want to share their experience.

2. Would you implement this activity by adapting it to your class’ or school’s needs? Why? Why not?

- Yes, I use Lego Mindstorm EV3.
- We need more elementary examples and solved tasks that will be published on the Internet (e-Library).

3. If you have adapted the activity, would you use the activity plan to describe your version? Could you please elaborate if the activity plan is clearly structured and described?

I would use LEGO MINDSTORMS EV3 .

We will participate in the competition FLL in Slovakia and we prepare students for this competition.

We solve tasks of FLL Slovakia.

<http://www.fll.sk/>

<http://www.firstlegoleague.org/>

<http://www.education.rec.ri.cmu.edu/content/lego/ev3/files/EV3%20teachers%20guideWEB.pdf>

We have special tables where students solve tasks.

WORKSHOP 6:

Author: AcrossLimits (AL) Malta

1. Would you implement this activity in your class or school as it is described? Why? Why not? Any cultural aspects?

Yes, I would implement this wonderful activity for 7-8 year old children.

The implementation of Didactic Method-Sequence and description of activities (Activity 1: Introducing Robots, Activity 2: Explaining Dot and Dash, Activity 3: Mini Programming, Activity 4: Evaluation and Conclusion) are right.

2. Would you implement this activity by adapting it to your class' or school's needs? Why? Why not?

The website <https://www.makewonder.com/> offers a collection of examples of varying difficulty.

The workshop is applicable in the pre-primary and primary education.

Time duration is adequate.

3. If you have adapted the activity, would you use the activity plan to describe your version? Could you please elaborate if the activity plan is clearly structured and described?

- This workshop will give to the primary school children more time to learn about the programming of Dash and Dot.
- The kit Dash and Dot is very nice (<https://www.makewonder.com/dot>).

WORKSHOP 7:

TITLE: Crazy robots – Robotic Product Development

Author: Lara Lammer

1. Would you implement this activity in your class or school as it is described? Why? Why not? Any cultural aspects?

- This workshop is a very good form of introduction to robotics.
- The most important moment of the workshop is the idea: "The researchers introduce themselves as robot experts and explain that in this workshop, the children will learn how to design robots while the researchers will learn from their ideas how to build better robots in the future is an appropriate form of brainstorming ideas for this age.
- Certainly, the position of dreaming and design characteristics of the robot makes sense.
- Sequence and description of activities (Workshop 1: Ideation, Step 1 – Robot Task ("assignment"), Step 2 – Robot Interaction, Step 3 – Robot Morphology ("looks and materials"), Step 4 – Robot Behavior, Step 5 – Robot Parts, Workshop 2: Prototyping, Phase 3: Evaluation) are right.

- Very interesting are visits to the Vision for Robotics Lab at the Vienna University of Technology and are shown a demonstration of the Romeo robot from the company Aldebaran (<http://projetromeo.com/>) where we introduce them to the robot's different capabilities and sensors including 3D cameras and computer vision.

2. Would you implement this activity by adapting it to your class' or school's needs? Why? Why not?

- I am not sure if I would implemented it, I haven't done anything like this yet.
- I was interested by exact things real robot, which can realistically be used to fulfill the robotic tasks.
- But if we consider that this workshop aims to develop creativity and imagination in children aged 10-12 years.
- I'd probably need training for this workshop.
- I would welcome some training on the methodology and process for this hour.

3. If you have adapted the activity, would you use the activity plan to describe your version? Could you please elaborate if the activity plan is clearly structured and described?

- I would implement this workshop for students aged 15-18.
- I would have invited scientists from the Technical University in Žilina for Workshop 1.
- Workshop 2, I would prepare on the workplace Technical University in Žilina.
- Perhaps we would visit the robotic workplaces in Kia Slovakia.
- Evaluation Phase 3, I would prepare this phase in the school again with the scientists from the Technical University of Žilina.

CONFERENCE:

European Conference on Educational Robotics (ECER)

Author: PRIA

1. Would you implement this activity in your class or school as it is described? Why? Why not? Any cultural aspects?

- Yes , this activity is usable in secondary (vocational) schools in European countries.
- It would be great to popularize this competition across Europe.

- Discussions of the students with researchers is very valuable.
- I like too all the awards:

Best Paper

Best Programming

Best Rookie Team

Best Subsystem

KISS Award

Man in Technology

Outstanding Engineering

Overall Documentation

Overall Judges' Choice

PRIA Judges' Choice

Spirit of Botball

Woman in Technology

- I think, that students have few similar opportunities.
- For the students is participation in the conference a strong motivation.

2. Would you implement this activity by adapting it to your class' or school's needs? Why? Why not?

- This activity is suitable for extracurricular education.
- This activity encourages children to study Engineering and Robotics.
- I would sign up my students for this activity.

3. If you have adapted the activity, would you use the activity plan to describe your version? Could you please elaborate if the activity plan is clearly structured and described?

- The action at European level is excellent, it would be great if you were able to participate also teams from other countries (more publicity).
- More opportunities for access to other European countries.

RECOMMENDATIONS FOR ALL WORKSHOPS:

- The workshops would be useful in Europe in primary and secondary education as part of curriculum, not only in the project.
- It is necessary to create a complex follow-up workshops.
- It is necessary to create manuals support for pupils, teachers.
- They are needed detailed manuals for teachers hardware and software that is use immediately with sufficient technical support on the Internet (Plug and Play) curriculum in

the subject applied informatics, computer science, programming a complex training for primary and secondary schools.

